

DAFNE

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Major abbreviations

CAPP	Central Africa Power Pool
COMELEC	Comité Maghrébin de l'Electricité
CON	Power Plant Under Construction
D3.3	Deliverable 3.3
EAPP	Eastern Africa Power Pool
EEP	Ethiopian Electric Power
GHCN	Global Historical Climatology Network
GRDC	Global Runoff Data Centre
HC	Operating Power Plant
ITCZ	Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone
KEN	Hydropower Plant Energetic Coefficient
KMD	Kenyan Meteorological Department
LU	Land unit
MASH	Moving Average over Shifting Horizon
NMA	National Meteorological Agency (of Ethiopia)
OTB	Omo-Turkana Basin
PLN	Planned Power Plant
SAPP	Southern Africa Power Pool
WARMA	WAter Resources Management Authority
WAPP	West Africa Power Pool
ZESCO	Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation
ZINWA	Zimbabwe National Water Authority
ZRA	Zambezi River Authority
ZRB	Zambezi River Basin

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable, D2.1, is expected to provide a “snapshot” of water resources use and management status quo in the two basins investigated by the DAFNE project. Such snapshot should highlight how much water is available and how it is used, by which actor, where and according to which strategy. This is necessary to build the so-called “alternative zero”, which will serve as comparison for the development pathways selected and analysed in other deliverables. The alternative zero is thus representing how water resources are used under historical climate, socio-economic development, market and regulatory conditions, which determine the baseline driver scenario.

To this purpose we used available data sources to describe the state of the Zambezi River Basin (ZRB) and of the Omo-Turkana Basin (OTB) in terms of water availability (chapters 2.2 and 3.2) production of hydropower (chapters 2.3 and 3.3), and of agricultural commodities (chapter 2.4 and 3.4) under present climate and hydrological regimes, hydraulic and hydropower infrastructure, as well as land cover and agricultural land use distribution. In chapters 2.8 and 3.8 the governing policy, legal and institutional frameworks are outlined. We compared the production levels of hydropower and food with the requirements for energy (chapter 2.3/3.3, 2.6/3.6 and 2.7/3.7) and food (chapters 2.4/3.4 and 2.6/3.6) of the current population and the economy as a whole, and came up with assessments of energy and food surpluses or deficits, as much as the space and time resolution of data allowed. In order to account for environmental conservation, we also identified environmental hotspots and their related pressures (chapters 2.5/3.5). For each chapter, not only the bibliographic sources were outlined, but also the numeric datasets identified, explored and used.

Data were acquired from local, national and supranational agencies and institutions, to the extent data exist or were made available. Whenever it was impossible to access existing data owned by national agencies, we complemented the necessary information by means of publicly accessible data, such as remotely sensed hydroclimatic and geodata, or socio-economic data available at international organisations, such as United Nations agencies and the like. Unfortunately, the data landscape proved to be extremely heterogeneous not only in terms of quality and quantity of data, but also in terms of accessibility. The resulting description of the baseline scenario and the related understanding of how water is used across different competing sectors and regional and national borders are not corresponding to the level of detail, which the project sought after, but still provide a reasonable basis to implement both the DAF and the WEF integrated model.

The data used to outline the baseline scenario encompass geodatasets describing the geospatial characterisation and state of the basins (e.g. soil, land cover, elevation and landforms, etc.), georeferenced time series (e.g. hydrometeorological data, river discharges, water levels in lakes and reservoirs, etc.), as well as hydroclimatic reanalysis and satellite retrieved data. In so far as data use licences allow, they have been gathered in a cloud-based project data repository, which this report makes throughout all sections reference to. The modelling work packages of DAFNE (WP3, 4 and 5) will use the acquired and collected data to develop, calibrate and validate the modelling framework combining the DAF (D5.2) and the WEF-Nexus integrated model (D3.5) for both basins. The complex interaction of the natural and infrastructural system will be modelled through a combination of distributed hydrological modelling and socio-economic modelling, which reproduce the present allocation of water resources across the sectors and its impact on key indicators identified in Milestone 33. The selection of the most interesting development pathways (MS32 and D5.4) will be carried out, in the context of the PIP approach adopted by DAFNE (Soncini-Sessa et al., 2007), by means of the DAF model (D5.2), which allows identifying the most robust and efficient pathways as measured by key indicators selected by the stakeholders throughout the NSL.

The formulation of the baseline scenario presented in this deliverable follows first a hierarchical and sectoral approach, which disentangles the WEF-nexus complexity through its major components, e.g. river basin hydrology, hydropower plants and production, land used for (irrigated) agriculture, water-dependent ecosystems, settlements, industrial estates and mining sites and pro-

cessing plants, as well as spatial coverage of legal instruments. Specific datasets are then associated to each component (e.g., land used for rainfed agriculture) and, where applicable and/or possible given the consistency of the data, coupled with time series (e.g., precipitation records at a given meteorological station) in order to quantify, as much as the available data allow, the nexus. The latter is finally summarised in section 3.9.

2. ZAMBEZI RIVER BASIN

2.1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The ZRB is the fourth largest basin of Africa with an area of 1.32 million km² shared by eight countries (Angola, Botswana, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Tanzania, Zambia, and Zimbabwe) and populated by almost 40 million inhabitants. In 2004 an agreement among the eight riparian states was signed to create the Zambezi Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM) with the purpose of enhancing the cooperation over the shared water resource of the ZRB to increase agricultural yields, hydropower production, and economic opportunities.

The Zambezi River originates in the regions of eastern Angola and north-west Zambia at elevations around 1600 m.a.s.l. and flows for 2,700 km through plains, gorges, marshlands into the delta in Mozambique (Figure 1). It discharges 2,600 m³/s on average into the Indian Ocean. Both temperature and rainfall follow the seasonal pattern associated with the Intertropical Convergence Zone: rainy season from November to April and dry season from May to October. The average annual rainfall in the basin is quite high, 950 mm, but it is unevenly distributed across the basin and the interannual variability is quite high. Up to 1,400 mm/yr are observed in the northern and eastern parts of the basin, whereas 400 mm/yr characterise the southern and western regions. A large amount of water is lost by evaporation due to the high evaporation rates (1600 mm-2300 mm). After the late 1970s the operation of dams changed the natural flow pattern significantly affecting some of the valuable wetland ecosystems in the middle and lower course, also favouring the expansion of irrigated agriculture.

Figure 1 - Topography of the ZRB based on the DEM derived from SRTM data.

Currently, the water requirements in the Zambezi basin as a whole are less than the available resource. Nevertheless, possible conflicts between riparian countries in the ZRB can arise due to the

asymmetry between resource availability and population density in addition to the fact that the riparian countries have different investment potential and river basin shares, thus determining a different capability to access and use the available resource. At present the largest consumptive water uses (15-20% of the annual runoff) are located in the middle and lower part of the basin, and correspond to the evaporation losses from the reservoirs, irrigated agriculture and, though minor, water supply. In the future, expansion of irrigated agriculture, additional hydropower schemes and expanding tourism in important areas of biodiversity (Lake Malawi, floodplains of Barotseland, Busanga and Kafue in Zambia, Zambezi delta and the protected areas in northern Zimbabwe and the Luangwa Valley in eastern Zambia) could spark regional and international conflicts over water use.

Figure 2 shows a large range of soil units occurring in the ZRB. The higher parts of the plains and plateaus formed by older geologic formations have highly weathered soils (*Ferralsols*), which are predominant in the northern part of the basin. Soils of the eastern part of the basin are strongly influenced by the formation of the rift valleys and related mountains and are predominantly found along steep slopes, and in part, along eroded parts of the plateaus (Figure 3). These soils are less weathered (e.g. *Luvisols*, *Lixisols*) or weakly developed (*Cambisols*) and are often rocky, stony or shallow (*Leptosols*, *Regosols*). In the driest part, particularly in northern Zimbabwe soils occur that are affected by the accumulation of soluble salts (*Solonchaks*, *Solonetz*). Relative fertile soils occur on the recent volcanoes (*Andosols*) in Tanzania, while where older volcanic or calcareous rocks have weathered fertile black soils of the cracking clay type have formed (*Vertisols*). These different soil units not only have their specific hydraulic properties, which has an implication for soil water availability throughout the basin, but also influence the type of land cover on top of the soils. Concerning the natural vegetation, as shown in Figure 4, forests and woodland still occupy large areas. Montane rainforest occurs on the highest mountains along the rift valley as on the Mbeya highlands in Tanzania, the Nyika plateau in Malawi or on the Eastern Highlands in Zimbabwe. On the plains and plateaus, on deep highly weathered soils, or sandy soils with low base saturation typically miombo woodlands are most commonly found. Shrublands are found on a variety of soils varying from shallow soils on hills and steep slopes to better drained soils on alluvial deposits. Vast areas of the floodplains, like the Buluzi and Barotse plains are covered by grasslands. Agricultural land is mostly done in a zone stretching from Kabwe to Livingstone for Zambia. It is more widespread and generalised in the more populated parts of Malawi and Zimbabwe.

Figure 2 - Dominant soil units of the ZRB following the 2nd edition of WRB (IUSS WRB Working Group 2007) (based on the Harmonised Soil Map of Africa (Dewitte et al., 2013) combined with the SOTER maps of Southern Africa (Dijkshoorn, 2003) and Malawi (Dijkshoorn et al., 2016)).

Figure 3 - Slope map of the ZRB at 200 m resolution (based on SRTM 90 m resolution data - <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>).

Figure 4 - Land cover of the ZRB (adapted from ESA, 2018).

2.2 WATER AVAILABILITY

The ZRB is generally a rich water source, comprising both surface water and groundwater. An average annual runoff of about 103 km³ is generated by the basin, however with high temporal and spatial variability across it.

The present section reports about water as a natural resource, on the basis of data compiled and analysed from three main sources: (a) ground observations made available from agencies responsible for data collection in their respective ambits of operation, (b) remote sensing and/or re-analysis data sets, which were collected by the DAFNE consortium from publicly available sources, and (c) data derived from literature reports. The resulting hydrometeorological data landscape is very

heterogeneous in terms of historical data available from local, regional and national agencies¹. The baseline scenario representing the current climate will therefore largely be based on global datasets of which the space and time (S-T) resolution is coarser than ideal. Calibrating and validation of the model with data at a higher resolution would allow investigation of some of the critical nexus interactions (e.g. intradaily deficit irrigation policies to minimize the agricultural water consumption, or flooding in small catchments).

The collected data are stored on the internal project data repository and organised in a hierarchical manner as indicated in Figure 5 and described in the text that follows.

Figure 5 – Illustration of the Hydro-meteorological database hierarchy in the DAFNE data repository. The same structure is followed for climate data.

Categories of data

gridded_data - contains gridded observations or spatially derived products on a regular grid. The data may either be static (fixed in time), or time varying map sequences. File formats are either a recognized geo-referenced raster format (e.g. GeoTIFF), or CF-compliant NetCDF. NetCDF is preferred for time-varying maps, but an appropriately named sequence of georeferenced raster files is used in some cases.

mapping_data - vector datasets in typical GIS formats for mapping and GIS based analysis procedures. Typically point, line or polygon shapefiles with appropriate attribute data.

station_data - contains punctual observations or measurements. Usually time-series data represented by a metadata file describing station locations and characteristics, as well as a csv format

¹ At the moment of compiling this deliverable, the project is still waiting for data that could be available at agencies, which so far did not provide access at their database.

table where individual station time-series are columns. The columns are linked to the metadata file using unique station identifiers.

General organization of data within primary categories

The data are organised according to various levels of elaboration that will allow the data to be available for different use cases in the project work, and to make tracing the processing steps more straightforward. This is useful because manual data cleaning (e.g. done by hand in spreadsheets) can be both time consuming and error prone, so structuring the processing steps makes it easier to revisit in case problems are discovered during the modelling process.

As far as possible we have organized the hydro-meteorological time-series data described according to the three level hierarchy described below and shown in Figure 5 (similar concepts are applied in the case of gridded and mapping data when relevant):

- *Level0_raw_data* - Raw data sets as received from stakeholder agencies, downloaded from internet sources and so on. The state of organization and format of level 0 data varies widely depending on the source.
- *processed_data/level1_cleaned_raw* - Level 1 reformatting of the level 0 data to consistently structured tables containing the time-series according to the tidy data principles of Wickham (2014). No treatment of missing data, outlier detection or other quality treatment is carried out at this level. The main purpose is to consistently structure the raw data to facilitate further analysis.
- *processed_data/level2_prepared_data* - Data prepared for use in simulations or model calibration/validation. At this level, various elaborations of the level 1 time-series have been carried out. An example would be to extend record length by combining different periods of record from the same station contained in level 1 data-sets sourced from different institutions, or extending records using water levels and rating curves. Missing data may have been infilled in some cases.
- *processed_data/processing* - Description of processing applied to produce level 2 data (when relevant). Includes processing tools like scripts, spreadsheets, intermediate results, sanity checks, etc.

The available data were first investigated to analyse their consistency, quality and suitability for further use in the project. Moreover, some elaborations were carried out to explore key statistical indicators (e.g. seasonal hydrographs, mean annual streamflow, probability distribution curves, and flow duration curves), which could provide proxy information about the nexus between water availability and its use in the different sectors. Accordingly, the following subsections illustrate some of the analyses that were carried out on the available data to characterise water availability and space-time variability. A level of detail providing a more complete and meaningful description of the water availability than that reported here will come from the model simulations that will be presented in the deliverable D3.5², where the WEF integrated model will be extensively described and its outputs will define the list of the hydrological output variables (indicators) that will be used to compare the baseline scenario and the alternative zero with the pathways and scenarios defined for the ZRB.

2.2.1 Climate

According to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification (Köppen, 1900; Geiger, 1954; Geiger, 1961; Kottek et al., 2006; Peel et al., 2007), in the Zambezi catchment three different climatic areas coexist (Figure 6). The most dominant climate, typical of the northern part of the catchment, is type “Cwa”, i.e. a temperate climate with warm temperatures and a dry season during the winter. The South-western part is characterized by a “Bsh” climate, i.e. steppe climate, distinguished by annual evapotranspiration exceeding the annual rainfall (Gerritz, 2000). Two regions, one in the Zambezi delta area and one in the western part on the border between Zambia and Angola, show tropical climate (“Am”), with high temperatures and a short dry period.

² DAFNE-Deliverable 3.5. Integrated model of the WEF nexus.

The most important underlying mechanism driving rainfall patterns in southern Africa is the movement of the inter-tropical convergence zone (ITCZ) (Gaughan and Wylen, 2012). The ITCZ oscillates extensively across the basin during the rainy season and produces widespread rainfall. The period from May to September is the typical dry season with very little precipitation in the basin, while from October through to April the Equatorial Trough brings unstable air that causes convective rainfall. An average annual rainfall of about 990 mm falls into Zambezi basin, with a strong south-north gradient of 700 mm to 1200 m per year (Figure 7).

Figure 6 - Köppen-Geiger climate classification in southern Africa adapted from Peel et al. (2007) (the climate zones are described in Table 1 of Peel et al., 2007 – interpreted here for climate zones in the figure). Af – Tropical Rainforest; Am – Tropical Monsoon; Aw – Tropical Savannah; BWh – Arid Desert Hot; BWk – Arid Desert Cold; BSh – Arid Steppe Hot; BSk – Arid Steppe Cold; Csa – Temperate Dry Summer Hot Summer; Csb – Temperate Dry Summer Warm Summer; Cwa – Temperate Dry Winter Hot Summer; Cwb – Temperate Dry Winter Warm Summer; Cfa – Temperate Without dry season Hot Summer; Cfb – Temperate Without dry season Warm Summer. The black box indicates the approximate extent of the ZRB.

Figure 7 - Mean annual precipitation map of the ZRB (Lautze et al., 2017).

Data on the basin hydrometeorology are scarce (Lautze et al., 2017) and limited meteorological data have been obtained from the in-situ agencies at the time of writing. Our analysis of meteorological data relies on the Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN) database (Menne et al., 2012), a collection of over 90,000 land-based stations worldwide. The number of GHCN stations included within the DAFNE project's Zambezi domain are about 60 and they are represented in Figure 8 (the approximate figure given is because number of available stations depends on the measured variable of interest). The meteorological stations are mainly located in the southern and eastern part of the catchment (Zambia, Zimbabwe and Malawi), while in the Upper Western Zambezi (Angola) very few data are available. The database includes daily precipitation, maximum and minimum daily temperature even if there are only a few stations at which temperature data are available. The precipitation and temperature time series span different periods of time (even at the same station), and for many stations records are not complete. From the 1960s to 1990, data records contain relatively little missing data. However, after 1990 there is an abundance of missing data and records during the last decades are almost empty at many of the stations.

Figure 8 - Map of GHCN meteorological stations available in the ZRB.

To illustrate the typical characteristics of the time-series, we selected 5 meteorological stations where the GHCN database reports the longest period of record, coloured in green in Figure 9. We computed the annual precipitation totals and the number of missing data per year in the available record and results are shown in Figure 10. The time period of each series are not complete from the first year to the last one of the monitoring period, but the available years in each time series are reported in Table 1.

All the stations are characterized by a significant lack of data during the most recent years of the monitoring period (that is usually from 1990 onwards). Moreover, the average annual precipitation for these years is much lower compared to the past years, thus suggesting a lower reliability of most recent data. An exception is represented by the meteorological station of Harare, which shows, in spite of a considerable number of missing values from 1989 to 2017, annual precipitation totals during this period that are consistent with those of the earlier years. At the Harare station most of the data are missing during the dry season, when, incidentally, precipitation is almost absent (this is an important observation, as it may be feasible to infill missing records with zeros during the dry season in some parts of the region). This last station is the only one of those we selected that we considered suitable for conducting a trend analysis, because it covers a relatively long period that includes also the most recent years. We compute the monthly average precipitation for each of the six decades of the time horizon (1959 – 2017) in order to explore possible trends or changes in seasonality.

Figure 9 - Map of the GHCN meteorological stations selected for the illustrative analysis. The stations with precipitation time series are shown by means of green symbols, while the stations with temperature data are shown by magenta ones.

Figure 11 shows the results and no visible trend is evident. Generally, the peak precipitation is recorded in January, but the decade 1999-2008 shows a particular intra-annual pattern, with an anticipated peak in December and lower precipitation in January-March. The decade 1989-1998 is characterized by the lowest precipitation amount, while during the period 1979-1988 the highest peak in January was recorded.

Only 7 GHCN stations include temperature data: Bulawayo, Gokwe, Gweru, Kariba, Kwekwe, Mutoko and Victoria Falls. Their location is shown by the magenta symbols in the map of Figure 9. Maximum and minimum temperature daily temperature records are available for different periods of time. The annual average maximum and minimum temperature is represented in Figure 12. Since the stations are located in the same region in the southern Zambesi River Basin, the patterns of temperature are consistent. The results seem to suggest a slight positive trend in the long-term, so that we conducted a Mann-Kendall statistical test of significance of the trend to confirm it. We fixed the significance threshold α to 0.05 and we tested the possible existence of trends in the annual average values of the min and max temperature. The trend is significant only in the stations of Bulawayo and Gweru for both maximum and minimum temperature, for the station of Gokwe only for minimum temperature and for the station of Victoria Falls only for the maximum temperature. Therefore, we conclude that temperature is likely to be registering an increase in the long period, but due to the lack of recent data we are not able to verify this.

Table 1 - GHCN meteorological stations selected for the analysis of precipitation time series.

Station ID	Station name	Country	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)	Time period
MZ000067217	Lichinga	Mozambique	-13.3	35.23	1'365	1952 - 1993 2003 - 2010 2013 - 2017
MZ000067261	Tete		-16.18	33.58	150	1953 - 1970 1974 - 1999 2017
ZA000067581	Chipata	Zambia	-13.55	32.58	1'032	1950 - 1995
ZA000067743	Livingstone		-17.82	25.82	986	1950 - 1990 2013 - 2016
ZI000067775	Harare	Zimbabwe	-17.92	31.13	1'480	1959 - 2017

Figure 10 - Annual precipitation totals and corresponding number of missing data in some selected GHCN stations. The figure highlights the large number of missing records in the later parts of the time-series. Consequently, the annual totals computed during these years cannot be considered as reliable.

Figure 11 - Average monthly precipitation at Harare in each of the six decades of the period 1959-2017.

Figure 12 - Average maximum and minimum annual temperature at some selected GHCN stations.

2.2.2 Hydrography and river flow regime

The ZRB is typically divided into 13 sub-catchments (e.g. FFEM, 2005), corresponding to the major tributaries and the main Zambezi as shown in Figure 13 and in Table 2.

The Zambezi River generates from the Kalen hills in Zambia in the Upper Zambezi sub catchment (Sahin, 2002) and crosses the border of Angola towards Zambia. Here, the River enters the Barotse flood plain and turns eastwards. Before crossing the Barotse flood plain two main tributaries, Lungue Bungo and Kabompo, flow into the main course, while afterwards, the main tributary is Lu-anginga River. The Barotse sub-catchment ends after the confluence with the mouth of the Cu-ando – Chobe subbasin. After Victoria Falls, the River Zambezi follows its way to the Kariba Reservoir, an artificial lake used for hydroelectric purposes. About 150 km downstream of the outlet of

Lake Kariba, the Zambezi River confluences with the tributary of the Kafue basin. In the Kafue sub-basin two dams affects the river streamflow: the Itezhi-Tezhi and the Kafue Gorge dam, both operated for hydropower generation purposes. After this confluence, the Zambezi enters Lake Cahora Bassa and downstream, before draining into the Indian Ocean, the River Shire, coming from lake Malawi, runs into the Zambezi. Surface water resources in the ZRB comprise thus of the Zambezi itself and its tributaries. Particularly, the runoff from the Upper Zambezi, Luangwa, Shire/Lake Malawi and Tete subbasins (43% of the total basin area) contribute for about 66% of the total runoff in the basin (Lautze et al., 2017; Matondo and Mortensen, 1998).

Figure 13 - Maps of Zambezi sub-catchments, according to the SADC delineation described in FFEM (2005). Note that the delineation of these subbasins is done to provide some structure to this section, and not linked to the Pfaffstetter system referred to elsewhere in this report.

Table 2 - Zambezi sub-catchments shown in Figure 13, according to FFEM (2005).

Subbasin ID	Sub – basin name
01	Zambezi Delta
02	Tete
03	Shire River/Lake Malawi
04	Mupata
05	Luangwa River
06	Kariba
07	Kafue River
08	Cuando/Chobe River
09	Barotse
10	Luanginga River
11	Lungue Bungo River
12	Upper Zambezi
13	Kabompo River

Continuous observations on hydrological stations in the ZRB started in 1950 (Gochayi, 2015), but the data quality is compromised mainly by deteriorating hydrological services, and inefficient data gathering programmes as a result of poor funding and constrained institutional capacity (World Bank, 1991). Various agencies operating in the ZRB are running monitoring programmes and collect data independently from each other. Figure 15 shows the area of interest of the main Agencies. Zambezi River Authority (ZRA) is responsible for the management of the Zambezi River in the area between Zimbabwe and Zambia, from the Kabompo sub-catchment to the main Zambezi until the outflow from Lake Kariba. The Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation (ZESCO) is a parastatal company working in the hydropower energy field, from generation to distribution and supply. Its main generation stations are at Kafue Gorge, Kariba North Bank and Victoria Falls. This implies that ZESCO monitors the hydrological fluxes mainly in the area of the Kafue sub-catchment, while Hidroeléctrica de Cahora Bassa (HCB) is the hydropower company operating Cahora Bassa power plant. The Zimbabwe National Water Authority (ZINWA) monitors the area of the Kariba sub-catchment as well as the Tete sub-catchment, while the Water Resources Management Authority (WARMA)³ of Zambia collects some hydrological data especially in the Luangwa sub-catchment, but owns all the hydrological stations in the Zambian territory. The area downstream Cahora Bassa as far as the Zambezi delta is monitored by ARA – Zambeze, the regional water Authority for Zambezi watercourse in Mozambique. The monitoring stations cover a large part of the domain, since only the Upper Zambezi (Angola) is not covered, but, probably due to transboundary issues, data sharing is still an open challenge. The main means of communications for data sharing are phones, fax or post (Gochayi, 2015), and past projects aiming at the establishment of platforms (e.g., ZAMWIS⁴, ADAPT⁵ (Matos et al., 2015)) for data sharing did not succeed in resolving the complex situation in the basin. This issue makes data collection for the entire ZRB a challenge, since it requires the establishment of relationships with each agency and collection of data by agreement with individual agencies. So far, following a meeting with ZRA⁶, and the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding with WARMA, a database with hydrological data was disclosed to DAFNE. Since the data provided by WARMA and ZRA are mainly in the Zambian territory, we integrated them with the data from the Global Runoff Database Center (GRDC). GRDC data have been analysed in MS15⁷, since an exhaustive dataset from agencies was not available at that time. For a more detailed description of the GRDC database we address the reader to MS15. Table 3 describes the stations we analyse for describing the baseline scenario from a hydrologic point of view. The last column of the table refers to the database the specific time series of discharge come from. Some data series come from the combination of different datasets (e.g., WARMA+ZRA or WARMA+GRDC). In these cases, we verified that the two time series coincide during the overlapping periods and combined them in order to have the most extensive time series possible. The location of the stations is represented in Figure 14, where the stations are marked in different colours representing the data source: WARMA only (red), ZRA only (green), a combination of WARMA and ZRA data (yellow) or GRDC only (blue).

The integrated monitoring stations cover most of the catchment, excluding only the western part of the basin, where no stations are available (i.e., Lungue Bungo and Cuando/Chobe sub-catchments). In the Kafue sub-catchment, discharge time-series of many gauging stations are available. Indeed, Kafue Flats are a wetland of particular ecological importance. The GRDC dataset covers a significant historical period starting from the 1960s until at most 2005, while the recently obtained WARMA and ZRA dataset cover the decades from 1980 to 2018. Therefore, the integration of all the time series provides a spatially and temporally significant representation of the hydrology of the ZRB. We used the Moving Average over Shifting Horizon (MASH) algorithm as a statistical tool (Anghileri et al., 2014), which enables inter- and intra-annual trend analysis, by averaging data with

³ Formerly Department of Water Affairs (DWA)

⁴ This is the database operated by ZAMCOM (<http://zamwis.wris.info>)

⁵ African Dams Project

⁶ Mr. Mwiinga and Mr. Namakando, respectively responsible for hydrology and water quality in activities in ZRA.

⁷ <https://polybox.ethz.ch/index.php/s/WK8WUTr2WkDA5T7>

shifting horizons at both timescales. The moving average windows are fixed at 2 weeks for the intra-annual analysis and 5-years for the inter-annual analysis. Results for the selected stations are presented in the following sections.

Figure 14 - Map of the analysed WARMA (red stars) ZRA (green star), integrated WARMA and ZRA (yellow stars) and GRDC (blue) discharge gauging stations in the ZRB.

Figure 15 - Areas of the ZRB monitored by the different Agencies. (Gochayi, 2015).

Table 3 - WARMA, ZRA and GRDC stations analysed.

Station ID	Country	River	Station name	Latitude	Longitude	Start year	End year	Data-base		
1992320	Malawi	Luweya	Majikapotwe	-11.78	34.23	1952	1991	GRDC		
1992401		South Rukuru	Phewzi	-10.9	34.05	1957	1991	GRDC		
1992700		Shire	Liwonde	-15.07	35.2	1965	1984	GRDC		
1891500	Mozambique	Zambezi	Cais	-16.15	33.59	1960	1990	GRDC		
1291100	Namibia	Zambezi	Katima Mulilo	-17.48	24.3	1942	2015	GRDC		
1292301	Tanzania	Ruhuhu	Mikula	-10.44	34.8	1971	1990	GRDC		
W1080	Zambia	Zambezi	Kaleni	-11.13	24.25	1980	2015	WARMA		
W1105			Chavuma-Pump house	-13.08	22.68	1980	2015	WARMA		
Z1			Chavuma-Mission	-13.09	22.68	1959	2017	ZRA		
W1150			Zambezi-Pump house	-13.55	23.10	1990	2012	WARMA		
W2030			Lukulu	-14.38	23.23	1950	2012	WARMA + GRDC		
W2400			Senanga	-16.12	23.25	1947	2013	WARMA + GRDC		
Z4			Ngonye	-16.67	23.62	2005	2017	ZRA		
W3045			Nana's Farm	-17.82	25.65	1990	2017	WARMA + ZRA		
Z7			Victoria Falls-Big Tree	-17.91	25.85	1924	2017	ZRA		
W3980			Chirundu Bridge	-16.03	28.85	2005	2015	WARMA		
1591231			Kabompo	Kabompo	Kabompo Pontoon	-13.6	24.22	1990	2005	GRDC
W1950					Watopa Pontoon	-14.02	23.60	1980	2017	WARMA + ZRA
W4005			Kafue	Kafue	Kipushi Road	-11.78	27.17	1980	2015	WARMA
W4350	Chilenga	-14.10			27.42	1980	2017	WARMA		
W4450	Lubungu	-14.57			26.45	1955	1991	WARMA + GRDC		
W4669	Hook Bridge	-14.93			25.92	1973	2005	WARMA + GRDC		
W4760	Namwal Pontoon	-15.68			26.45	1980	2017	WARMA		
W4890	Nyimba	-15.75			27.30	1980	2017	WARMA		
W4977	Kasaka	-15.82			28.22	1960	2017	WARMA + GRDC		
W5755	Lusemfwa	Lusemfwa	Chiwefwwe	-13.62	29.40	1980	2012	WARMA		
W5815			Mulungushi	-14.30	28.55	1980	2009	WARMA		
1591730	Luangwa	Luangwa	Road Bridge	-14.97	30.22	1951	1993	WARMA		

Kabompo subbasin

The Kabompo River is one of the main tributaries of the Zambezi and it is the most upstream tributary for which data are available. Two stations are available in this sub-catchment: Kabompo Pontoon and downstream Watopa Pontoon, a few kilometres before the confluence with the main Zambezi.

The average annual flow at the two stations over the corresponding monitoring period is 208 m³/s and 219 m³/s respectively. An increasing trend in the average daily discharge is detectable in the long-term time series, as the right-hand panel in Figure 16 shows. This explains the low difference in the average annual flow. Indeed, the first dataset spans the period 1990-2005, while the second one from 1980-2017. The first one does not include the period when the flows were lower and therefore the average annual flow is very close to the second one (this example illustrates the value of long time-series in characterizing the variability about the mean). A change in intra-annual seasonality also emerges. Indeed, from the 1980s to 1990s, the annual discharge pattern was characterized by a small peak in February and a second bigger peak in April, while in the 2000s the two peaks have combined into a single one that spans the period January – April, and the discharge volume is much higher in these later years⁸. These evident changes in the hydrological regime of the Kabompo might not be the result of varying precipitation, but rather due to changes in land use across the decades. Indeed, especially in the upper part of the Kabompo sub-catchment, a significant extent of forest disappeared while the surface dedicated to agriculture increased (Kampata et al., 2013).

Figure 16 - Average daily discharge at Kabompo Pontoon (left) and Watopa Pontoon (right) gauging stations computed with 14-days moving horizon, averaged over 5 years period.

Kafue

The Kafue system is one of the main tributaries of the Zambezi and it represents an area of particular ecological interest. During the rainy season the river swells and overtops its main channel. The flooded areas provide fertile spawning grounds for fish, breeding grounds for water dependent birds, and have important groundwater recharge functions, and, when the floods recede, fish migrate back to the channel, while the drying floodplains provide fertile soils for agriculture (WWF, 2017). Probably due to its ecological relevance, hydrological data from 7 stations of Kafue system are available. Figure 17 shows the average annual discharge in each gauging station, ordered from upstream to downstream from left to right on the figure.

⁸ Such changes in the flow regime are important from the point of view of environmental health and ecosystem services (one of the components of the WEF nexus that DAFNE aims to address).

Figure 17 - Average annual discharge in different gauging stations of Kafue subbasin. Note that the large flow rate at Kasaka is most likely related to a combination of significant lateral contributions, as well as the operation of the Ithezi-Tezhi dam upstream of this location. We speculate that the significant increase in mean annual discharge at the Kasaka gauging station might be related to back-water effects from the Kafue gorge sustaining a high water level, rather than a high flow rate (we are investigating the issue).

The Kipushi Road station is close to the source of the Kafue River and therefore it shows an average annual discharge of 2.5 m³/s only. The stations of Lubungu, Namwal Pontoon and Nyimba show an average annual discharge lower than the correspondent upstream stations and this is due to the overtopping of the main channel and subsequent loss of water from the channel, as explained above. Figure 18 represents the results of the trend analysis for the stations ordered from upstream (Kipushi Road) to downstream (Kasaka). Among these only Kasaka is downstream of Ithezi-Tezhi dam, while the others are upstream. Indeed, the seasonality of discharge at Kasaka is much less pronounced than in the upstream other sections. The Ithezi-Tezhi dam, represents an important discontinuity along the Kafue system and the most evident effect in terms of hydrology is the flattening of intra-annual variability, due to the release policies for hydropower generation. Even though the data records at the gauging stations cover different time periods, from the data recorded at Lubungu station, it is apparent that from the 1950s to 1970s, the average has continuously decreased from year to year, while from the 1960s to 1970s it has increased, at least at Kasaka station, which covers the longest period (due to the integration of GRDC and WARMA datasets). The discharge has then continuously decreased from the 1970s to 1990s and increased again from the 1990s to today. The Kasaka station might, however, suffer from measurement errors due to backwater effects.

In Figure 19, we compare the flow duration curves at the Kasaka gauging station, in the Kafue sub-catchment downstream of Ithezi-Tezhi for the periods before and after the construction of the Ithezi-Tezhi dam (completed 1978). After construction of the dam, there is a generally higher mean daily flow rate (higher low flows), and a reduction in the inter-annual variability of flows. The reduced inter-annual variability is supported by the discharge seasonality plots of Figure 18 which show a distinct difference in variability between years for the period before and after construction of Ithezi-Tezhi.

Luangwa

The Luangwa sub-catchment is located in eastern Zambia, it has an area of approximately 150'000 km² and in the upper part it has a relatively dense drainage network. One station on the main course of Luangwa River, i.e. Luangwa Road Bridge, and two on the main tributary to the Luangwa, the Lunsemfwa River (i.e., Chiwefwe and Mulungushi stations) monitor the river network. The average annual discharge for each station is reported in Figure 20. The discharge in the tributary stations is much lower than the discharge in the main Luangwa and the Luangwa Road Bridge station is located just downstream the confluence of the Lunsemfwa River. In Figure 21 the results

of a trend analysis are shown. Discharge of Chiwefwe shows a very smooth intra-annual pattern and a continuously increasing trend from 1980s until today, while the discharge at Mulungushi has a more pronounced intra-annual variability with a peak in March, which, in the last decade, had become bi-modal with a first peak in January and a second in March. Discharge of Luangwa River, instead, shows a rapid increase at the beginning of the wet season (November-December) and a rapid recession until May. The inter-annual pattern changes year-by-year (Beilfuss, 2001). The discharge shows an increasing trend until 1970s, which might be the result of changes in the vegetation and land cover, rather than a change in precipitation trend (Beilfuss, 2001).

Figure 18 - Average daily discharge at different gauging stations of Kafue subbasin computed with 14-days moving horizon, averaged over 5 years period.

Figure 19 – Empirical flow duration curves at the Kasaka station for the period before and after construction of the lthezi-Tezhi dam. It is clear that there is a reduction in the variability of flows, which is supported by the discharge analysis of Figure 18 that shows a significant reduction in the inter-annual variability after construction of the dam in the late 1970s.

Figure 20 - Average annual discharge at different gauging stations of Luangwa subbasin.

Figure 21 - Average daily discharge at Chiwefwe, Mulungushi and Luangwa gauging stations computed with 14-days moving horizon, averaged over 5 years period. Note the difference in scale of the discharge due to the range of catchment area upstream of each gauge.

Figure 22 – Empirical flow duration curves at gauging stations in the Luangwa subbasin. The Mulungushi and Luangwa road bridge stations show very similar general behaviour, with the main difference being an order of magnitude difference in flow volumes. The curve for Chiwefwe appears flat due to the much smaller volume of flow.

Shire River/ Lake Malawi

The Shire River and Lake Malawi sub-catchment is a predominantly independent system covering the entire Malawi, which joins the main Zambezi River upstream of the delta, before it runs into the Indian Ocean. Discharge data from four gauging stations were analysed, three on the main streams flowing into Lake Malawi (Ruhuhu at Mikula in Tanzania, south Rukuru at Phewzi and Luweya at Majkapotwe in Malawi) and one on the Shire River (at Liwonde), downstream from Lake

Malawi. For the latter only monthly data are available. In Figure 23 the average annual discharge for the four stations is represented. The discharge of the three tributaries to Lake Malawi is much smaller than the discharge of Shire River, the main outflow from the lake, variations in the lake level are strongly affected by the volume of rainfall on the lakes surface (Drayton, 1984). Figure 24 shows the results of the trend analysis, but for Shire river (Liwonde station) the monthly discharge values are simply plotted since no MASH algorithm was applied to the monthly time-series. The pattern of tributaries shows a strong seasonality with a peak in April, while the Shire shows an impressive variability in seasonality and magnitude of the monthly flows across the monitoring period. Indeed, in 1965 the Kazumo Barrage was built at the outlet of Lake Malawi and since then the level of the lake was maintained at a higher level. The barrage allows the lake operation between 473.2 and 475.32 m a.s.l (Shela, 2000a) and this might have an influence on the flattening of the intra-annual variability of the Shire discharge in the years following the construction of the barrage. Figure 25 shows the flow duration curves for the three main inflows to lake Malawi, with Mikula giving the most consistent contribution to volume despite having the lowest peak inflows during the wet season (see Figure 24).

Figure 23 - Average annual discharge at different gauging stations of the Lake Malawi subbasin.

Main Zambezi

Discharge data of twelve stations located on the main Zambezi River are available. From upstream to downstream they are: Kaleni, Chavuma – Pump house, Chavuma – Mission, Zambezi – Pump house, Lukulu, Senanga, Ngonye, Katima Mulilo, Nana’s Farm, Victoria Falls – Big Tree, Chirundu Bridge and Matundo - Cais. Figure 26 shows the annual average discharge at each station which, as expected, increases gradually in a downstream direction (an exception is the station Victoria falls – Big Tree, where the average annual discharge is lower than the upstream stations). This is most likely due to the significantly longer period of time, which flow measurements in this station span compared to the other stations. Indeed, for this station data are available from 1924 to 2017, the longest period of record available to us. In Matundo-Cais, the last gauging station before the Zambezi delta (also upstream of the confluence of the Shire river from Malawi), the annual average discharge is four times the discharge in the most upstream stations. Figure 27 shows the inter- and intra-annual patterns recorded at the twelve stations. The first station (i.e., Kaleni) is very close to the source of the Zambezi River and shows a smooth pattern, first decreasing from the 1980s to 1990s and then decreasing in 2000s. The other nine downstream stations (i.e., Chavuma – Pump house, Chavuma – Mission, Zambezi – Pump house, Lukulu, Senanga, Ngonye, Katima Mulilo, Nana’s Farm, Victoria Falls – Big Tree) have a more pronounced seasonality with a single peak around March, although in the most recent years the patterns show a bimodal tendency, with a small peak in February and a second peak in April. The discharge in Chirundu Bridge shows a smooth intra-annual variability and an irregular inter-annual variability, probably due to the presence of the Lake Kariba just upstream. The discharge at Matundo – Cais, instead, shows a more

pronounced intra- and inter-annual variability. This is likely influenced by its location downstream of the Cahora Bassa reservoir, the management policy of which alters the natural streamflow regime.

In Figure 28 we compared the flow distribution at the Matundo Cais gauging station, downstream of both Kariba (built in 1955) and Cahora-Bassa (end of building in December 1974), the time series span the period 1960-1990 (GRDC data) and therefore only the impact of Cahora Bassa can be seen in the data. There is no clear difference in the distribution before and after construction of Cahora-Bassa, which could be related to controlling effect of the upstream Kariba that was already in place at the beginning of the data record.

Figure 24 - Average daily discharge at three gauging stations in Lake Malawi subbasin computed with 14-days moving horizon, averaged over 5 years period and monthly discharge at Liwonde station.

Figure 25 – Empirical flow duration curves at gauging stations in the Lake Malawi subbasin. No curve was computed for the Liwonde station since only monthly data is available.

Figure 26 - Average annual discharge in different gauging stations of Main Zambezi.

Figure 27 - Average daily discharge at twelve gauging stations of Main Zambezi computed with 14-days moving horizon, averaged over 5 years period. Note that the indistinct seasonal pattern at the Chirundu gauge is due to the large number of missing data in the available record.

Figure 28 – Empirical flow duration curves at the Cais station for the period before and after construction of the Cahora-Bassa dam (commissioned 1974). There is no remarkable impact of the dam on the flow duration curve for the periods before and after construction. This is likely due to the controlling effect of lake Kariba on the flow distribution, which was already in operation prior to the start of the available flow record in 1960.

2.2.3 Lakes and wetlands

Natural Lakes

There are three major lakes in the Zambezi basin: Lake Malawi, Lake Kariba and Lake Cahora Bassa. Lake Malawi, with a maximum depth reported to be 695 m (Neuland, 1984), is the second deepest lake in Africa after Lake Tanganyika and the third deepest in the world, while Lake Kariba and Cahora Bassa are man-made lakes created by the construction of dams on the Zambezi River (Euroconsult Mott MacDonald, 2007).

The only large natural lake on the Zambezi watershed is Lake Malawi. It is the third largest lake in Africa with a maximum length of 580 km and a width of between 16 and 80 km, and a surface area of about 30'000 km². Its volume capacity is almost 8'000 km³. The hydrological balance of the lake is dominated by direct rainfall, which reaches 2'270 mm per year in the lake area. The lake is subject to abrupt annual and seasonal changes in its water level as a result of variations in rainfall. The Shire River in the southern part of the lake constitutes its outlet, further flowing through a small lake, the Malombe, before joining the Zambezi in its lower reach (Pinay, 1988).

Figure 29 - Lake Malawi historical level (Neuland, 1984).

Lake levels have been recorded since 1880s and some notable events happened since then (Figure 29). For more than 20 years, until 1935, a near cessation of the outflow took place, while

unusually high levels and outflows in the late 1970s and 1980 which caused floods of lakeshore and downstream areas were registered. In early 1990s, low levels and outflows were recorded, associated with a widespread regional drought (Sene et al., 2016, and Figure 30). Since 1965, the lake outflows have been controlled at a barrage – the Kamuzu Barrage – which is situated near Liwonde about 83 km downstream from the lake outlet. (Sene et al., 2016).

Lake Malawi and the Shire river system play a major role in Malawi’s economic sector. Lake Malawi is the main source of water for all country’s hydropower stations located along the Shire River with a total installation capacity of 280 MW. Further south, the Shire is the main source of water for the country’s largest sugar plantation at Nchalo and other irrigation schemes in the Lower Shire Valley and supplies water to the city of Blantyre. The Lake also serves as a medium for water transportation which is conducted by government owned Malawi Lake Services (Kumambala and Ervine, 2010).

Figure 30 - Lake Malawi level 1992-2018 estimated from satellite altimetry (Schwatke et al., 2015)⁹.

Wetlands

A number of large wetlands are present in the ZRB and have several direct and indirect benefits for rural communities. Direct uses include flood recession agriculture and grazing, fisheries and habitats for wild animals. Indirectly, wetlands benefit rural communities by attenuating flood peaks, preventing soil erosion and favouring groundwater recharge (Lautze et al., 2017).

Six main wetlands are found in the Zambezi basin:

- a) Barotse (area=5,550 km²);
- b) Chobe-Capriivi (2,200 km²);
- c) Kafue flats (6,500 km²);
- d) Lower Shire (1,620 km²);
- e) Luangwa floodplains (2,500 km²);
- f) Delta (12,750 km²).

The *Barotse floodplain* is a flat plateau at about 1000 m asl, slightly sloping to the south. It stretches from the Zambezi’s confluence with the Kabompo and Lungwebungu rivers to the south of Senaga, covering a length of 230 km with a width varying from 30 to 50 km. The vegetation of

⁹ Figure from dahiti.dgfi.tum.de – accessed 2018-05-28

the Barotse floodplain comprises extensive grasslands, rather than swamps, and trees are largely absent from the flooded areas. The area is an important ecosystem for wetland birds and various reptiles and amphibians. The land use is roughly divided into palm savannah (2%), floodplain grassland (40%), wet grass (40%), reeds and sedges (10%) and river channel (8%). Rainfall varies from about 1020 mm in the north to 730 mm in the south (Turpie et al., 1999).

The *Chobe-Caprivi wetland* is topographically flat, dominated by grassland and old river channels. The soil is predominantly clay-loam with small areas of sandy clay-loam and organic clay; the highly organic soils are extensively cultivated. 32 vegetation species have been identified in the flat, including reeds, sedges and grasses. Tall trees grow along the river and woodlands cover sandy soils. The land use has been roughly divided into palm savannah (2%), floodplain grassland (70%), wet grass (15%), reeds and papyrus (8%) and river channel (5%). Annual average rainfall decreases from about 750 mm in the north-east to about 500 mm in the south west (Turpie et al., 1999).

The *Kafue flats* are a shallow flood plain along the Kafue river about 240 km long and 50 km wide, flooded to a depth of less than a meter in the rainy season and drying out in the dry season. They consist of a complex pattern of floodplain, lagoons, ox-bow lakes and detached river channels, marshes and levees surrounded by grassland and woodland zones (Zambia Wildlife Authority, 2006). The hydrology of these flats has been significantly altered by the construction of the Kafue Gorge and Itezhi-Tezhi dams. Releases from Itezhi-Tezhi are very different from the natural flows of the Kafue river. While the natural regime was characterized by a yearly smooth rise and fall, which induced the natural dynamics of the wetland, the upstream dam (Itezhi-Tezhi) releases large volumes of water and significant discharge now flows also during the dry season, smoothing the peaks -and thus the inundation of the floodplain- during the wet season. Conversely, the downstream Kafue Gorge Dam has created areas of permanent inundation at the eastern end of the flats, which did not exist before the construction of the Kafue Gorge dam (Mumba and Thompson, 2005). Moreover, the lands around the Kafue Flats are an important agricultural area in Zambia; subsistence and small-scale farmers live here and large commercial farms use the flats as source for irrigation water.

The *Lower Shire wetland and marsh areas* are characterised by flowing channels, flooded backwaters and pools. The main vegetation types found in the area are grasses, reeds and sedges; cultivations of cereals, sugar and vegetables are located on the drier soils. The broader floodplain is characterised by grassland, sparse woodland and dryland agriculture. The land use is roughly divided into palm savannah (2%), floodplain grassland (20%), wet grass (45%), reeds and papyrus (27%) and river channel (6%). The Lower Shire valley and its immediate catchment receives an average annual rainfall of over 1000 mm in the south, decreasing to about 750 mm in the north (Turpie et al., 1999).

The *Luangwa floodplains*, located in the Eastern Province of Zambia, cover approximately 250,000 ha (Ramsar, 2007). The floodplains are characterized by rivers that are responsible for recharging many streams, springs, lakes and other water bodies. The main habitats in the area include evergreen miombo woodlands and the alluvial zone which sustains riverine vegetation. Further, over 50 mammal species are present in the Luangwa floodplains, including critical endangered species such as the Black Rhino (*Diceros bicornis*). The floodplains are an important breeding ground for birds like *Merops nubicoides*, *Merops bullockoides*, and *Hirundo paludicola*.

The *Zambezi delta* has been divided by Turpie et al. (1999) into 6 physiographic regions:

1. Tidally influenced areas occupied by mangrove swamps;
2. Seasonally flooded areas with tidally influenced drainage lines: found inland of the mangrove swamps, mostly occupied by hygrophilous grasslands and aquatic communities;
3. Seasonally flooded areas designated to rice cultivation in the south, due to the high wetness of the area and to other cultivations like sugar take place in the north (Sena Sugar estate);
4. Relatively elevated floodplains and back slopes of levees, periodically flooded, partially cultivated with sugarcane, with flooding of these areas decreased throughout years;

5. Elevated levee and water course areas, characterised by hilly landscape dominated by grassland and riverine woodland vegetation and well populated with traditional farmers;
6. Raised beaches, mainly located near the coast, characterised by low fertility and production potential. However, there are extensive coconut plantations in these areas north of the Zambezi.

The land use has been roughly divided by Turpie et al. (1999) into palm savannah (5%), floodplain grassland (40%), wet grass (25%), reeds and papyrus (10%), river channel (5%) and mangroves (15%). The Delta falls partly within the sub-humid and mostly within the sub-humid to humid regions. The annual average temperature is about 26°C, rainfall of 1000-1200 mm, and an average humidity of over 70% (Sweco, 1982). The hot and rainy summer season lasts from November to March or April, and the moderately warm and dry winter season is from May to August.

Figure 31 - Major wetlands of ZRB, from Turpie et al., 1999

2.2.4 Groundwater

Information regarding the occurrence and distribution of groundwater in the ZRB is limited and therefore only a partial description of the complexity of groundwater resources is possible. Most of the information in this and the following paragraphs are taken from the Hydrogeology Atlas of Africa by Kebede et al. (2018), where information about geology and aquifers is given for all African countries, supplemented by information from Lautze et al. (2017). No data, unfortunately, were made available by any of the contacted agencies in the ZRB.

Current knowledge shows the existence of at least 10 transboundary aquifers in and across the basin, covering an area that corresponds to 20% of the Zambezi basin area (Lautze et al., 2017). These aquifers can be grouped into 5 main types, which are shown in Figure 32 and described in the text hereafter:

Unconsolidated aquifers with low to high productivity (up to 15 l/s) are found mostly in the Zambian, Zimbabwean and Angolan parts of the basin. These aquifers mainly occur in alluvial soils (main river channel, old river channels and lake shores plains) and Tertiary sand deposits (as the Kalahari geological group) and are characterised by a dominant intergranular groundwater flow. In the Zambezi valley, these aquifers can reach up to 45 m of thickness and are directly recharged by rainfall and rivers. Their water quality is generally good, although they might suffer from water quality issues because of occasional presence of brackish water.

Basement aquifers with low to moderate productivity occupy extensive areas of the central and eastern ZRB. These aquifers are most productive in weathered or fractured rock; the weathered zone is best developed in the plateau areas, where it can be up to 15 to 30 m thick. The aquifer is

usually unconfined and the water table is 15 to 25 m below the ground. Water from these aquifers can be acidic, but it is in most cases neutral. Recharge is influenced by the geomorphology of the aquifer and the depths of its groundwater.

Figure 32 - Aquifer lithology of the Zambezi basin (Kebede et al., 2018).

Consolidated sedimentary aquifers with intergranular and fracture flow are relatively abundant in the Zambian, Zimbabwean and Mozambican areas of the ZRB. These aquifers are found in the upper and lower Karoo Group geological units and their productivity is highly variable in space. Where sandstone is present, aquifers have a high porosity and permeability and therefore high productivity (80 l/s); shales and mudstones instead form low productivity aquifers (2 l/s). The water table is often 15 to 20 m below ground and water is in most cases brackish. These aquifers are directly recharged by rainfall and rivers.

Consolidated high-productivity sedimentary aquifers with fracture flow, formed by the Katanga Supergroup geological formation, are a relevant part of the Zambian aquifers (Kafue and Kabompo subbasin). These aquifers are usually unconfined, mostly 15 to 50 m thick and their water table is usually found between 20 to 35 meters below ground. Water in these aquifers is sometimes hard because of high dissolved calcium.

Igneous aquifers are sporadically found in the Zambian and Zimbabwean region of the basin. Igneous aquifers form in the Karoo basalts and comprise basalts with interbedded sandstone. This aquifer is unconfined and the water table varies from 10 to 25 m depth. Their productivity can vary from low to high and water quality is usually good; recharge can occur through fractures.

The average yearly recharge of the Zambezi basin over the period 1960-2000 has been estimated at 94 mm by Van Beek et al. (2011). This value corresponds to 130 km³, which is more than the annual average surface runoff. However, this value is locally highly variable and varies from less than 30 mm in the southwest of the basin to more than 100 mm in the delta and north/northeast of the basin (Lautze et al., 2017).

In Zambia groundwater quality is usually good and groundwater is generally potable in rural areas, even though its quality has decreased because of the high rates of urbanization, high water demand and by intense rainfall events. Water is also threatened by pollution risks associated with metal mining (e.g. in the so-called “copper belt”).

Groundwater use

Groundwater in the ZRB is a vital resource for social, economic, and environmental sustainability and its use is rapidly increasing (Lautze et al., 2017).

Many urban areas, including major cities like Lusaka (Zambia) and Tete (Mozambique), rely on groundwater as their main source for domestic supply and for drinking water. Groundwater from basement aquifers is the main source of water supply for rural areas, where water is extracted with hand pumps through boreholes (Lautze et al., 2017).

In Zambia and Zimbabwe groundwater is also widely used for irrigation, livestock watering and industry. In Malawi and Mozambique, the use for irrigation is at the moment only sparse and limited to the use by smallholder farmers and for subsistence farming (Kebede et al., 2018).

In some countries of the basin, like Zimbabwe, Mozambique and Angola, the exploitation of the groundwater resource is still very limited compared for example to Zambia. It is estimated that in Zimbabwe groundwater only covers about 10% of the total water use (Kebede et al., 2018).

The limiting factor for groundwater use in Mozambique is identified in the limited knowledge of the status of the resource by the population. No quantitative information is available regarding either groundwater use or recharge, therefore groundwater is probably underutilized at the moment, as potential users do not have knowledge or access to the groundwater potential in their area (Kebede et al., 2018).

In Angola, the information about groundwater use is also very limited. However, it is assumed that the use of the available national resource is very limited and restricted to southern and coastal areas where surface water availability is limited.

2.2.5 Surface water quality

Usability of water is not only determined by the distribution in space and time of the quantity of the resource, but also by its quality. Different pollution sources can compromise water quality in the global south. In a general sense, we identify the following water-quality related risks for human health and ecosystem functions in river basins of low-income countries (i) untreated sewage containing pathogenic microorganisms, (ii) industrial wastewater specifically from mining sites, (iii) agricultural runoff with pesticides and excess nutrients, (iv) outflow from stratified hydropower reservoirs.

Gathering water quality data in the Zambezi river basin has proven, where data exist, to be challenging. Only recently the recent interaction between the DAFNE partners (UNZA and ETH Zurich) and some Zambian data holding agencies has resulted in the sharing of some water quality data for the Zambezi basin. For this reason, a targeted though limited field campaign was organised to complement the sparsely data available from water institutions.

Moreover, the landscape about national standards for quality measurements is unclear. For instance, no national standards for water quality measurements seem to exist in Zambia, but only few thresholds on some pollutant concentrations in limited areas. Therefore, the existing water quality data are fragmented and are often related to spot measuring campaigns carried out for specific purposes. To our knowledge, the Zambezi River Authority (ZRA) is the only environmental agency monitoring water quality in the ZRB on a regular basis (as far as we could verify some monitoring activities began at the end of 1990s). Following a meeting with ZRA in July 2018 a small database was disclosed to DAFNE, which consists of the following measurements:

- temperature
- pH
- electrical conductivity
- dissolved oxygen (DO)
- total suspended solids (TSS)
- total dissolved solids (TDS)

- total alkalinity
- turbidity
- total phosphorus (TP)
- ammonia
- orthophosphate (orthoP)
- chlorophyll
- chloride (Cl).

These data come from samples taken on the main channel of the Zambezi (10 stations), on the Lake Kariba (8 stations), on tributaries flowing into Lake Kariba (4 stations) and on tributaries of the main Zambezi (8 stations). The location of the in-stream stations is shown in Figure 33, while **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the water quality measuring stations in Lake Kariba. The time resolution spans from monthly to quarterly and the data cover mainly the period 2008-2017, since the monitoring programme started at the end of the 1990s, but measurements only became consistent around 2008. The observations represent an instantaneous measurement.

Within DAFNE we focus on the water-energy-food nexus and therefore we concentrate our efforts to identify changes in water quality related to agricultural activities, existing dams and by replacing natural river systems with reservoirs. To this end, we selected a network of existing surface water quality measurement stations which are run by the Zambezi River Authority (ZRA). The most important variables that will be considered are water temperature, dissolved oxygen concentration, particle loads and nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations. The location of the ZRA stations is shown in Figure 33. A reasonable coverage of water quality parameters is available for a sub-set of 8 stations (Table 4, below), where also flow measurements are available.

The water quality parameters such as temperature, electrical conductivity, alkalinity and turbidity are consistently available in the database, but the concentration data contains many missing data points, especially for the orthophosphate, chlorophyll and chloride concentrations. Moreover, these concentrations are not always given as an exact number, but by a threshold (e.g., <4.5 mg/L). In the absence of precise information, we assume that this is probably due to the procedure that is followed in the analysis of water samples. The concentration range provides us with some information, but requires additional post processing to achieve a quantitative assessment of the C-Q relation. This will be carried out while setting up the model of flowing water quality. Figure 35 and Figure 36 show the boxplots of two solutes (DO and TP) as plotted for the selected 8 stations, divided in clusters along Main Zambezi, of tributaries to the main Zambezi and along the Sanyati River, one of the tributaries to Lake Kariba.

Table 4 - Hydrometric stations with water quality data (Milestone MS07)

Station name	Concentrations		Flow data		Water quality data	
	Start year	End year	Start year	End year	Start year	End year
Damwall Downstream	2007	2018	2009	2016	2009	2016
Sanyati River	2007	2018	1997	2018	2007	2018
Victoria Falls	2010	2018	1999	2018	2010	2018
Chavuma	2007	2017	1959	2018	2007	2017
Kalabo	2006	2017	2013	2018	2013	2017
Watopa	2006	2017	2013	2018	2013	2017
Ngonye	2006	2017	2005	2018	2006	2017
Nana's Farm	2007	2017	2005	2018	2007	2017

Figure 33 - Water quality stations in the upper ZRB.

Figure 34 - Location of the water quality stations on Lake Kariba. Yellow markers represent the stations where samples at different depths are collected (profiles), while light blue markers represent stations where one sample only is collected.

Figure 35 - Boxplots showing the range of dissolved oxygen concentration data at the 8 selected measuring stations.

Figure 36 - Boxplots showing the range of total phosphorus concentration data at the 8 selected measuring stations.

So far, no pesticide measurements are available, but a limited effort will be made to analyse pesticides as part of subbasin analyses carried out in the Lunsemfwa Basin. In order to complement the

data available from ZRA and to quantify the impact of dams on water quality, we installed six sensor stations upstream and downstream of Kariba and Itzhi-Tezhi reservoir. The resulting time-series document the reference scenario of seasonal changes of stream water in the rather pristine upstream section of the Zambezi River. By analysing differences up- and downstream of reservoirs the sensors will quantify the water-quality impact of large hydropower dams.

Reference scenarios for water quality can be based on a detailed analysis of rather pristine runoff from the Barotse plains: Zuijgeest et al. (2016) analysed the impact of the Barotse floodplain wetlands on the water quality of the Zambezi (Figure 37). In a study covering a flooding cycle with high-resolution sensor measurements they found that long travel times of the water in the floodplain reduced oxygen and particle loads, while dissolved organic matter concentrations as well as CO₂ increased with contact time between the water and the floodplain soils and vegetation. As the Barotse plains are quite pristine, the data can also serve as natural reference for the on-impacted tributaries in the upper Zambezi system (Zuijgeest et al., 2016).

A comparative study of the Barotse Plains and the Kafue Flats by Zuijgeest et al. (2015) revealed significant production of dissolved inorganic carbon and nitrogen during the flooding season in these wetlands (Figure 38). The study lists average concentrations of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus along the two river reaches including the variability and seasonality.

Figure 37 - Results from seasonal monitoring of the flood expansion and contraction in the Barotse plains, upper Zambezi. The two sensor stations were maintained upstream in Lukulu and downstream of the Barotse Plains in Senanga (Zuijgeest et al., 2016).

Figure 38 - Comparative study of water quality parameters in the Barotse Plains and the Kafue Flats. Left panel: Measured concentration ranges in the two floodplains for the dry and wet season. Right panel: sampling sites along the two river reaches (Zuijgeest et al., 2015).

Sediments in the Zambezi River Basin

The Zambezi river is the dominant sediment source of the Mozambique Shelf, with an estimated annual sediment load of about 65 million tonnes, of which 10% is transported as bedload (Tjallingii et al., 2014).

No major problems of reservoir siltation are reported in the literature for the Upper and Middle Zambezi, suggesting that sediment concentrations do not reach excessively high values. Oral and written sources report instead the high sediment loads of the Luangwa River, which also determine siltation problems in the Cahora Bassa Reservoir (Ronco et al., 2010).

Hall et al. (1977) report the maximum and minimum suspended sediment concentration measured during a 2-year campaign in the middle Zambezi (upstream of Cahora Bassa) and in the Luangwa. The maximum value for the middle Zambezi (344 g/m^3) is much lower than the maximum concentration measured in the Luangwa River (1016 g/m^3), thus pointing at the Luangwa basin as the main sediment source of the basin.

2.3 HYDROPOWER

2.3.1 Africa Power Sector

Africa presents a very small power sector when compared with its geographic extension and population, and while its domestic energy production potential could overtop the internal energy demand, as of 2014 more than two-thirds of the African population did not have access to electricity (IEA, 2014).

If we focus on the demand side, total electricity demand in Africa was 605 TWh in 2012, 40% of which was represented by North Africa (IEA, 2014). The major power demand sectors are industry, commerce, and households. In Northern and Southern Africa, electric trains cover most of the electricity required by the transport sector. As far as agriculture is concerned, both large farms and agro-industries need electricity (UNIDO, 2009). In particular, in Sub-Saharan Africa the power consumption per capita is very low, namely 112.8 kWh excluding South Africa (The World Bank, 2003).

As for the supply side, Africa can be divided into five different macro-regions according to the major sources of energy supplying electricity to the main demand sectors of each region. Most of the oil and gas reserves are concentrated in North and West Africa, whose power sector is thus dominated by fossil fuel fired power production facilities. As for Eastern and Central Africa, the electricity supply system is dominated mostly by hydropower (and geothermal/biomass-based power plants only to a limited extent). In the end, the Southern African power industry is driven by coal power stations (and hydropower to a lesser extent). According to IEA (2014), installed grid-power generation capacity¹⁰ in Africa has been constantly increasing over the past years, reaching 158 GW in 2012, whose 75% is concentrated in the Republic of South Africa and North Africa. For instance, the total electricity production for Africa in 2000 was 441 TWh, whose main share was generated by thermal power stations due to the large coal plants in South Africa and oil-fired plants in Nigeria and North Africa. Although hydropower presents a massive exploitable generation capacity in Africa, its contribution to the total electricity produced is relatively low (i.e., 18% as shown in Figure 39) (UNIDO, 2009).

¹⁰ Installed capacity refers to the sum of gross (i.e., nameplate) electricity production capacity, including both power stations producing power mainly for sale and auto-producers generating electricity mainly for their own consumption. The total installed capacity might not be available all the time due to maintenance/repair works and other outages (IEA, 2014).

Figure 39 - Electricity production for Africa in 2004, divided into the main power production sources (i.e., thermal, hydropower, nuclear and geothermal) (IEA, 2004).

If we focus on the hydropower generation technology, the technical potential of the continent is estimated at 283 GW and may produce up to 1200 TWh/year (three-times the current electricity consumption in Sub-Saharan Africa). However, less than 10% of this potential is currently exploited. More than half of the remaining potential is concentrated in Central and East Africa, together with some opportunities in Southern and West Africa (IEA, 2014).

The five different macro-regions into which Africa has been divided according to the major sources of energy supplying electricity are usually called power pools, acting as specialized agencies of their respective Regional Economic Community (REC) (ICA, 2016):

- **Central Africa Power Pool (CAPP)** for the Economic Commission for Central Africa States (ECCAS): it consists of 10 member countries and experienced a growth in both installed power capacity (from 5,345 MW to 6,299 MW) and associated electricity consumption (from 15,238 GWh to 24,744 GWh) from 2008 to 2013. Based on its recent developments, it is likely that CAPP will start functioning as a power pool for the interconnected countries by the end of 2020;
- **Comité Maghrébin de l'Electricité (COMELEC)** for the Union of Maghreb Arab (UMA): it consists of 5 member countries and experienced a growth in both installed power capacity (from 24,027 MW to 36,367 MW) and associated electricity consumption (from 160,322 GWh to 120,200 GWh) from 2009 to 2013. COMELEC has the highest connectivity and best infrastructure compared to the other Power Pools. It could start operating as a power pool by the end of 2018, even though this depends more on political rather than technical considerations;
- **Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP)** for Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA): it consists of 11 member countries and experienced a growth in both installed power capacity (from 38,513 MW to 54,311 MW) and associated electricity consumption (from 162,322 GWh to 232,505 GWh) from 2008 to 2013. It might attain a centralized trading regime between 2020 and 2025;
- **Southern Africa Power Pool (SAPP)** for SADC: it consists of 11 member countries and experienced a growth in both installed power capacity (from 55,948 MW to 61,859 MW) and associated electricity consumption (from 260,081 GWh to 269,375 GWh) from 2008 to 2015. It was created in 1995 and is now the most developed power pool in Africa. For instance, it is the only regional African power market with a competitive energy market (i.e., Day-Ahead Market) established in 2009. In 2015, the SAPP started upgrading its market trading platform to develop both the intra-day market and forward physical markets. Based on its recent developments, it is likely that more operational members will take part in the SAPP by the end of 2018, together with the construction of an interconnection between EAPP and SAPP;
- **West Africa Power Pool (WAPP)** for ECOWAS (ICA, 2011): it consists of 14 member countries and experienced a growth in both installed power capacity (from 14,669 MW to 19,648 MW) and associated electricity consumption (from 46,936 GWh to 50,634 GWh) from 2008 to 2015. It

might attain a centralized trading regime between by 2019 if the regional interconnection projects will be completed.

Table 5 summarizes the installed capacities in each power pool, relating them to the number of inhabitants in each region. In particular, some countries are holding most of the share of the total installed capacity within their own power pool: Algeria owns 41% of COMELEC, Egypt 71% of EAPP, RSA 82% of SAPP and Nigeria 60% of WAPP (ICA, 2011). As already mentioned above and reported in Table 4, at the African continent level most of the existing power capacity is thermal due to the size of COMELEC and SAPP power pools, which mostly rely on thermal power stations (91% and 83% of their total installed capacity respectively). As for hydropower, it is predominant in CAPP (86%). In EAPP and WAPP, the share of hydropower installed capacity is 23% and 30% respectively, and it is likely to increase in the next few years as many future generation investments are being done within the hydropower generation sector (e.g., construction of Koysa dam in Ethiopia with its 2200 MW). This is also the case for SAPP, where 80% of the 13,015 MW future installed generation capacity refers to hydropower projects. According to future projections for the 2020-2025 time-period, a substantial share of the power generation mix within these power pools will be covered by the hydropower sector (ICA, 2011).

As for the power trade among these five power pools, it can be observed that it consists mainly in CAPP exporting power to SAPP (Table 6).

Figure 40 - Africa power pools (SAPP, 2018).

Table 5 - Installed capacity [MW] per thousand inhabitant in each of the five power pools Africa is divided into (ICA, 2011).

	CAPP 2009*	COMELEC 2009*	EAPP 2008*	SAPP 2010*	WAPP 2010*
Installed Capacity [MW]	6,073	27,347	28,374	49,877	14,091
Hydropower Share [%]	86	8	24	17	30
Thermal Share [%]	14	91	73	83	70
Population [mln]	123.9	85.6	385.6	160.5	260.6
kW/1000 inhabitants	49	319	74	311	54

*Base year: most recent year for which data is available for all countries of the power pool (ICA, 2011).

Table 6 - Power trade among the five African power pools (ICA, 2011).

	CAPP 2009*	COMELEC 2009*	EAPP 2008*	SAPP 2010*	WAPP 2010*
Consumption [GWh]	15,238	89,098	124,017	260,081	47,073
Imports [GWh]	38	5,491	513	19,565	3,247
Exports [GWh]	915	940	931	15,301	3,278
Electricity Traded [%]	0.2	6.2	0.4	7.5	6.9

*Base year: most recent year for which data is available for all countries of the power pool (ICA, 2011).

Despite the major progresses done towards the development of each one of the five African power pools, they still suffer from some limitations (ICA, 2016):

- CAPP: (i) lack of interconnections that limit the trade among countries; (ii) weak incentives for private sector investments; (iii) inadequate reliable data;
- COMELEC: (i) very limited power trade among member countries due to limited generation reserve margins; (ii) absence of a harmonized regulatory framework governing electricity trade and institutional weaknesses at regional level;
- EAPP: (i) lack of interconnections that limit the trade among countries; (ii) weak alignment of national development plans with the Master plan for electricity infrastructure development; (iii) weak incentives for private sector investments; (iv) inadequate reliable data;
- SAPP: (i) limited generation and transmission capacity; (ii) power shortages;
- WAPP: (i) lack of interconnections that limit the trade among countries; (ii) weak alignment of national development plans with Regional Master plan for electricity infrastructure development; (iii) weak incentives for private sector investments; (iv) high tariffs; (v) inadequate reliable data.

In the following sections, a closer look into the hydropower status of the two DAFNE case studies is proposed. The two chapters, one for each case study, begin with a description of the African Power Pools of interest, namely SAPP and EAPP, and progressively narrow the analysis to the countries, the river basin, and finally the power plants that are relevant to DAFNE project.

2.3.2 Southern African Power Pool (SAPP)

About SAPP

The Southern African Power Pool (SAPP) was created in August 1995 at the Southern African Development Community (SADC) summit held in Kempton Park, South Africa. It consists of twelve member countries, represented by their respective electric power utilities organized through SADC (Table 7) (SAPP, 2015).

The primary aim of the SAPP is to provide reliable and economical electricity supply to the consumers of each of its members, based on reasonable utilization of natural resources and the effect

on the environment. In particular, all its members have committed to create a common market for electricity in the SADC region and let their customers benefit from the advantages associated with this market. In doing so, the utilities from member countries work under the right of equal and fair participation, from sharing information and lessons learnt to technical wheeling and mutual support (SAPP, 2016a).

The SAPP is made up of different sub-committees, among which there is the Environmental Sub-Committee (ESC), whose main responsibility is to alert and advise the SAPP Management Committee on best environmental management practices and related issues. In fact, the ESC has to develop environmental management guidelines for the SAPP and review them from time to time. It is also its job to keep up with the most recent world and regional matters regarding air quality, water quality, land use, climate change impacts and sustainability endorsement (SAPP, 2016a).

Electricity Production Capacity

The total capacity in the SAPP could be classified into installed, available and operating. At the end of 2015:

- Installed capacity, i.e. total nameplate electrical generation capacity that is officially installed = 61,859 MW.
- Available capacity, i.e. total amount of electrical generation capacity that is potentially able to produce electricity at any one time (regardless of plants temporary closure periods due to maintenance works) = 52,598 MW.
- Operating capacity, i.e. total amount of electrical generation capacity that is actually operating (thus ready to produce electricity) at any one time = 46,910 MW.

Table 8 reports the installed capacities by member utility, whereas Figure 41 shows the contribution of each generation technology to the total installed capacity value (SAPP, 2015).

Table 7 - SAPP Membership. The countries marked with a “*” belong to the ZRB. The rows highlighted in grey show three different electric power utilities operating in the same country (i.e., Zambia).

COUNTRY	FULL NAME OF UTILITY	ABBREVIATION	STATUS
Botswana*	Botswana Power Corporation	BPC	OP
Mozambique*	Electricidade de Mocambique	EDM/HCB	OP
Malawi*	Electricity Supply Corporation of Malawi	ESCOM	NP
Angola*	Empresa Nacional de Electricidade	ENE	NP
South Africa (RSA)	Eskom	Eskom	OP
Lesotho	Lesotho Electricity Corporation	LEC	OP
Namibia	NamPower	Nam Power	OP
DRC	Société Nationale d'Électricité	SNEL	OP
Swaziland	Swaziland Electricity Company	SEC	OP
Tanzania*	Tanzania Electricity Supply Company Ltd	TANESCO	NP
Zimbabwe*	Zimbabwe Electricity Supply Authority	ZESA	OP
Zambia*	ZESCO Limited	ZESCO	OP
Zambia*	Copperbelt Energy Cooperation	CEC	ITC
Zambia*	Lunsemfwa Hydro Power Company	LHPC	IPPP

OP = Operating Member; NP = Non-Operating Member; ITC = Independent Transmission Company; IPP = Independent Power Producer

Table 8 - Total installed capacity [MW] of each SAPP utility, updated to 2015. The rows highlighted in grey show two different electric power utilities operating in the same country (i.e., Zambia).

UTILITY	TOTAL INSTALLED CAPACITY [MW]	% OF TOTAL
BPC	892	1.4%
EDM/HCB	2,724	4.4%
ESCOM	352	0.6%
ENE	2,210	3.6%
Eskom	46,963	75.9%
LEC	74	0.1%
Nam Power	501	0.8%
SNEL	2,442	3.9%
SEC	70	0.1%
TANESCO	1,380	2.2%
ZESA	2,045	3.3%
ZESCO	2,157	3.5%
LHPC	49	0.1%
TOTAL	61,859	100%

Figure 41 - SAPP total installed capacity contributions by generation technology, updated to 2015.

At the utility scale, it is important to note that the Republic of South Africa (RSA) presents the biggest contribution to the installed capacity in the SAPP amounting to 75.9% of the total. This means that the RSA is a fundamental stability factor for the regional grid system. At the SAPP level, after coal hydropower provides the second largest installed capacity, equal to 21% of the total.

Despite capacity is growing fast in some member countries (1,237 MW of new generation capacity on annual average over the last 11 years), there is still a relatively large shortfall at the SAPP level. As at 31st March 2015, SAPP had an operating capacity of 46,910 MW against a demand of 49,563 MW that includes peak demand, suppressed demand, and reserves. This corresponded to a generation capacity shortfall of 8,247 MW, i.e. 16.6% of demand was unserved, taking into account generation capacity reserve requirements.

In order to face this issue, a large amount of planned new capacity is supposed to be commissioned between 2015 and 2019, totalling 24,062 MW within the whole SAPP (SAPP, 2015).

As for the electricity demand, SAPP utilities' independent projections forecast an average annual growth of 3.1% until 2027, while the regional expectation is that the total final demand will exceed 85 GW of power by 2030 (SAPP, 2015; Cervigni et al., 2015).

Electricity Production

The percentage contribution of four different generation technologies (i.e., nuclear, thermal excluding nuclear, hydropower and other renewable sources) to the average annual electricity production in the SAPP is presented in Figure 42. On average, hydropower generates 14.1% of total electricity produced in the whole SAPP, nuclear 4.4%, whereas thermal (i.e., oil, gas and coal) is responsible for 81.4%. The contribution from other renewable sources (e.g., solar, wind) is negligible (Table 9).

Thermal power plants give the largest contribution to the total annual energy produced in the SAPP. This is mainly due to South Africa, because: (i) it is the main electricity producer in the SAPP, covering 84.6% of the total energy produced; (ii) thermal power plants (including nuclear) are responsible for 98.2% of its production.

Figure 42 - Contribution by generation technology (i.e., nuclear, thermal excluding nuclear, hydropower and other renewable sources) to the average annual electricity production in the SAPP. The data have been averaged over the 1971-2013 period (The World Bank, 2016).

Electricity Market Overview

In the early 1960's, only a few participants could take part in the electricity trading market of the Southern African region, which was typically governmental to governmental bilateral agreements. As the interconnections expanded (e.g., between Zambia and Zimbabwe after the construction of Kariba Dam), more participants entered the market, thus two primary electricity networks were created in the region (i.e., northern and southern system). These two systems experienced an increased energy trading starting from 1995, when the north-south interconnector was commissioned.

In 2001, the SAPP started the Short-term Energy Market (STEM), seen as a first step from a cooperative to a fully competitive electricity market. In fact, the STEM is a firm energy market where energy is traded a day-ahead, though bilateral contracts take precedence over STEM contracts on the transmission lines.

In 2004, the SAPP started developing a fully competitive, day-ahead electricity market (DAM) (Musa, 2005). This latter sets two goals:

1. To establish an efficient and competitive marketplace;

2. To ensure that consumers benefit from the market.

This is achieved by:

1. Developing consistent market mechanisms;
2. Assessing efficient price signals for the procurement and electricity transmission;
3. Assuring a fair and open access to the transmission system;
4. Optimizing generation and transmission capacity.

Table 9 - Annual energy production [GWh] averaged over the 1990-2013 period and divided by country belonging to the SAPP (International Energy Agency, 2016).

COUNTRY	ANNUAL AVERAGE ENERGY PRODUCTION [GWh]			
	HYDRO	NUCLEAR	OIL/GAS/COAL	OTHER RENEWABLE
South Africa	3,794	11,707	207,269	118
Namibia	1,249	0	55	0
DRC	6,482	0	31	0
Lesotho	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Swaziland	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Botswana	0	0	975	0
Mozambique	8,914	0	55	0
Malawi	n.a.	0	n.a.	n.a.
Angola	1,862	0	672	0
Tanzania	2,015	0	1,113	3.2
Zimbabwe	3,967	0	4,175	12.7
Zambia	8,892	0	47	0
TOTAL	37,175	11,707	214,392	133.9

Apart from the DAM, the SAPP Market Trading Platform (MTP) comprehends a Forward Physical Market (FPM) (Month and Week Ahead) and an Intra-Day Market (IDM). The former is open for market participants for trade of monthly and weekly products and is based on physical delivery of the traded power volume. It is an auction-trading model just as the DAM. The latter is open for trading of power after DAM and up to a configurable time before real-time, typically one hour ahead. It is a continuous market where trading is based on a first-come first-served principle and its main role is to:

1. Allow each individual market participant to adjust the power balance;
2. Be a tool to manage incidents and failures in the power system between the closing of the DAM and delivery the next day (SAPP, 2016b).

Transmission and Distribution System

Within the SAPP, electricity transmission and distribution (T&D) systems exist both at the national and international (i.e., among country members) level, allowing each state member to be – or have the potential to be – connected to neighbouring systems. Table 10 and Figure 43 summarize the capacity [MW] of the existing infrastructure at the international transmission scale. “Country 1” and “Country 2” are used to define the two neighbouring countries connected by the transmission project. In the future, new international transmission projects are planned, accounting for an additional line capacity of 9,730 MW (81% of the existing one) within the whole SAPP.

Table 10 - Capacity [MW] of the existing transmission infrastructure among different country members of the SAPP (Miketa et al., 2013).

COUNTRY 1	COUNTRY 2	CAPACITY [MW]
Botswana	South Africa	850
	Zimbabwe	650
Lesotho	South Africa	230
DRC	Zambia	260
Mozambique	South Africa	3,850
	Swaziland	1,450
	Zimbabwe	500
Namibia	South Africa	750
South Africa	Swaziland	1,450
	Zimbabwe	600
Zambia	Zimbabwe	1,400
TOTAL		11,990

Figure 43 - Existing transmission projects among different neighbouring countries in the SAPP. The coloured lines identify different voltages of the transmission infrastructure, whereas the numbers represent its associated capacity [MW] (Adapted from: SAPP, 2016a).

2.3.3 Hydropower infrastructures: dams and hydropower plants

Seven of the state members of the South African Power Pool (SAPP) belong to the ZRB, namely Angola, Botswana, Mozambique, Malawi, Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe. Hereafter, we present an overview of: (i) the current and future installed hydropower capacity in the basin; (ii) the contribution of the different generation technologies to the total electricity production in the basin.

Within the ZRB, the current installed hydropower capacity sums up to 5,415 MW, updated at 2016. By the end of 2023, an additional 8,394 MW new hydropower generation capacity will be commissioned (Figure 44), corresponding to 155% of the current operating one. The existing hydropower plants are illustrated in Figure 45, Figure 46, and Figure 47, where we distinguish between *hydropower reservoirs*, namely regulated natural/artificial lakes that can be operated either annually (e.g., Itezhi-Tezhi) or as carry-over reservoirs for several years (e.g., Cahora Bassa), and *pondages*, i.e. smaller regulated reservoirs that can be operated only over relatively short periods (e.g., weekly, such as Tedzani) (The World Bank, 2010).

As it can be observed from the rows highlighted in red in Table 11, the existing hydropower plants within the Lunsemfwa sub-catchment (i.e., Mulungushi and Mita Hills dams located on the Lunsemfwa river entering the Zambezi right upstream of Lake Cahora Bassa) can be neglected as their installed capacity sums up to only 1% of the total installed hydropower capacity of the ZRB.

Figure 44 - Planned new hydropower capacity [MW] to be commissioned by the end of 2023 in each of the states belonging to the ZRB (Cervigni et al., 2015).

Technical sheets for the existing hydropower plants

The technical sheets that have been collected for the existing hydropower plants in the ZRB are available on the internal project data repository and in Annex I of this report. Variables highlighted in red refer to either missing data or data that still needs to be validated by the utility managing the power plants. It must be noticed that the list of hydropower stations here classified is not exhaustive but reflects the availability of information that could be collected from both scientific papers and grey literature (e.g., technical reports) via traditional information channels. The covered stations are:

- Kafue Gorge Upper (Zambia);
- Victoria Falls (Zambia);
- Itezhi-Tezhi (Zambia);
- Kariba (Zambia/Zimbabwe);
- Cahora Bassa (Mozambique);
- Tedzani (Malawi);
- Nkula Falls (Malawi);
- Kapichira (Malawi).

Figure 45 - Overview of the existing hydropower infrastructures within the ZRB (red line). The marker size is proportional to the power plant installed capacity [MW].

Table 11 - Existing and future hydropower plants within the ZRB. The rows highlighted in orange identify the projects that were supposed to be operating by 2016 but that are still in the planning phase. The rows highlighted in red refer to the two existing hydropower plants (i.e., Mulungushi and Mita Hills) on the Lunsemfwa river that can be neglected due to their irrelevant installed capacity.

COUNTRY	HYDROPOWER NAME	CAPACITY [MW]	STATUS	EXPECTED COMPLETION
<i>EXISTING HYDROPOWER</i>				
Mozambique	Cahora Bassa	2,075	HC	-
Malawi	Nkhula Falls	122	HC	-
Malawi	Kapichira	132	HC	-
Malawi	Tedzani	88	HC	-
Zambia	Victoria Falls	108	HC	-
Zambia	Kafue Gorge Upper	990	HC	-
Zambia	Itezhi-Tezhi	120	HC	-
Zambia	Mulungushi	32	HC	-
Zambia	Mita Hills	24	HC	-
Zambia/Zimbabwe	Lake Kariba	1,470	HC	-
Zambia/Zimbabwe	Kariba North Extension	360	HC	-
<i>FUTURE HYDROPOWER</i>				
Malawi	Khlolombizo	240	PLN	2018
Malawi	Songwe I,II and III	340	PLN	2014
Malawi	Lower Fufu	100	PLN	2015
Tanzania	Rumakali	222	PLN	2019
Mozambique	Mphanda Nkuwa	1,500	PLN	2017
Mozambique	Boroma	444	PLN	2025
Mozambique	Lupata	654	PLN	2025
Mozambique	HCB North Bank	850	PLN	2015

(Table 11 continued)

COUNTRY	HYDROPOWER NAME	CAPACITY [MW]	STATUS	EXPECTED COMPLETION
Zimbabwe	Batoka Gorge	1,600	PLN	2022
Zambia	Kafue Gorge Dam Lower	750	CON	2018
Zambia	Mulungushi Expansion	80-100	PLN	n.a.
Zambia	Muchinga	240-330	PLN	n.a.
Zambia	Ndevu Gorge	235-240	PLN	2022
Zambia/Zimbabwe	Devils Gorge	1,240	PLN	2019
Zambia/Zimbabwe	Kariba South Extension	300	CON	2018
Zambia/Zimbabwe	Mpata Gorge	543	PLN	2023

HC = Operating; CON = Under Construction; PLN = Planned

Figure 46 - Elevation profile of the major existing (grey) and planned (red) hydropower plants along the ZRB (SADC, 2007).

2.3.4 Hydropower production

At the ZRB scale, the percentage contribution of three different generation technologies (i.e., thermal, hydropower and other renewable sources) to the average annual electricity production is presented in Figure 48. On average, hydropower generates 78.4% of total electricity produced in the whole basin, whereas thermal sources are responsible for 21.5%. Other renewable sources contribution is negligible (Table 12). The lion share of the electricity produced in the ZRB comes from Mozambique (27.4%), Zambia (27.3%) and Zimbabwe (24.9%).

Figure 47 - Topologic scheme of the ZRB showing the current state of the system.

Table 12 - Annual energy production [GWh] averaged over the 1990-2013 period and divided by country belonging to the ZRB (International Energy Agency, 2016).

COUNTRY	ANNUAL AVERAGE ENERGY PRODUCTION [GWh]		
	HYDRO	THERMAL	OTHER RENEWABLE
Botswana	0	975	0.03
Mozambique	8,914	55	0
Malawi	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Angola	1,862	672	0
Tanzania	2,015	1,113	3.2
Zimbabwe	3,967	4,175	12.7
Zambia	8,892	47	0
TOTAL	25,650	7,037	15.93

Total Production per Technology [%] - Average

Figure 48 - Contribution of each generation technology (i.e., thermal, hydropower and other renewable sources) to the average annual electricity production in the ZRB. The data have been averaged over the 1971-2013 period (World Bank, 2016).

2.3.5 Electricity surplus/deficit

Methodology

The surplus/deficit of electricity (hydropower) is calculated as the difference between hydropower demand and production. This indicator is evaluated at the national scale as well as at the single hydropower plant level (for those plants located within the ZRB).

Data about the historical production were collected from available resources (e.g., International Energy Agency, 2018). In the absence of official data on the electricity demand, we estimated the hydropower demand for each country (power plant) by using the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS, Howells et al., 2011).

OSeMOSYS is a dynamic, bottom-up, multi-year energy system model applying linear optimization techniques to determine the optimal investment strategy and production mix of technologies (including hydropower) and fuels required to satisfy an exogenously defined energy demand at the power pool scale.

The OSeMOSYS model was employed to develop an open-source model of the entire African electricity system, called TEMBA¹¹ (Taliotis et al., 2016). TEMBA includes the Southern African Power Pool, to which the hydropower plants in the ZRB are connected. To estimate the hydropower demands, we run the power pool optimization over the 2000-2013 historical period. The resulting optimal production mix is designed to always satisfy the energy demand at the power pool level. The simulated production at the power plant scale therefore represent a good estimate of the allocated demand of each power plant.

The following sections are devoted to the analysis of the surplus and deficit trends at the national and power plant scale for the ZRB. Figure 49 provides a general overview of the situation reporting the average deficit or surplus conditions at the national scale.

Electricity surplus/deficit in ZRB

In this section we report the results of the electricity surplus/deficit historical analysis in the ZRB, first aggregated at the national scale and then at the power plant scale. In each table, the last row reports the average data and is coloured in green and red in case of electricity surplus and deficit, respectively.

Angola hydropower sector is characterized by a remarkable growth in the energy demand, which almost doubles from 2000 to 2006, while remaining constant from 2006 to 2013. As for the energy production, it keeps increasing throughout the entire historical period considered, recording a five-fold increase from 2000 to 2013. Up to 2009, however, an electricity deficit is observed, which turns into an energy surplus after 2009, when the demand remains constant and the production keeps increasing. On average, Angola experiences an electricity deficit in hydropower production with respect to demand across the 13-year period analysed (Table 13).

Such detailed considerations cannot be made for Malawi, since only yearly average hydropower production and demand data are available. However, it can be observed that the country experiences an electricity surplus on average (Table 14).

All the other countries (namely, Mozambique, Namibia, Tanzania, Zambia, and Zimbabwe) are characterized by a constant electricity demand from 2000 to 2013. In particular, Mozambique and Zambia present an electricity demand that is approximately nine times bigger than the one recorded for Namibia and Tanzania, and about three and a half times the demand in Zimbabwe.

As for electricity production, Mozambique experiences a 50% growth from 2000 to 2007 – while in an electricity deficit condition –, after which the production keeps somewhat constant as the country

¹¹ The Electricity Model Base for Africa

reaches an electricity surplus steady-state condition. However, the country experiences an electricity deficit on average (Table 15).

Figure 49 - Summary of the average deficit or surplus conditions of Hydropower production with respect to demand in the countries in the OTB and ZRB.

Namibia is characterized by variable electricity production values, thus variable electricity deficit/surplus conditions throughout the 2000-2013 historical period. On average, the country experiences a relatively small electricity deficit (Table 16).

Tanzania keeps its electricity production constant and around 2000/2500 GWh/yr, recording an electricity surplus for most of the years. 2006 is the only exception, when a 24 GWh/yr small deficit is observed (Table 17).

Electricity production steadily increases in Zambia, recording a 71% increase from 2000 to 2013. Conversely, the electricity demand being constant for all years, the country experiences a decrease in the electricity deficit from 2000 to 2011, which turns into a surplus in the last two years of the historical period (2012 and 2013). On average, Zambia experiences an electricity deficit in hydropower production with respect to demand across the 13-year period analysed (Table 18).

Zimbabwe is characterized by a two-fold increase in electricity production from 2000 to 2010, after which it experiences a slight 10% decrease. 2000 and 2001 recorded electricity deficit, which turned into an electricity surplus that steadily increases up to 2010. Beginning 2011, the electricity demand being constant for all years and the production decreasing, the electricity surplus decreases as well. However, the country experiences an electricity surplus on average (Table 19).

Botswana is not presented here since no existing hydropower plants could be found in the country.

At the hydropower plant level, both Cahora Bassa and Kariba South go against the national trend of Mozambique and Zimbabwe, as they respectively record surplus and deficit in production with respect to the allotted demand. As for Kafue Gorge Upper and Kariba, they follow the average national Zambia trend of electricity deficit (Table 20).

Table 13 - Hydropower demand (Howells et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Angola. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	1,648	912	736
2001	1,870	1,017	853
2002	2,013	1,143	870
2003	2,280	1,241	1,039
2004	2,558	1,750	808
2005	3,005	2,219	786
2006	3,344	2,665	679
2007	3,344	2,497	847
2008	3,344	3,134	210
2009	3,344	3,094	250
2010	3,344	3,703	-359
2011	3,344	4,007	-663
2012	3,344	3,772	-428
2013	3,344	4,767	-1,423
Average	2,866	2,566	300

Table 14 - Hydropower demand (Howell et al., 2011), production (Government of Malawi, 2010) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Malawi. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand. In the absence of annual production data, only the average surplus/deficit was computed using data from Government of Malawi, Ministry of Natural Resources, Energy and Environment, (2010).

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
Average	1,346	1,455	-109

Table 15 - Hydropower demand (Howell et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Mozambique. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	14,976	9,652	5,324
2001	14,976	11,841	3,135
2002	14,976	12,674	2,302
2003	14,976	10,870	4,106
2004	14,976	11,668	3,308

(Table 15 continued)

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2005	14,976	13,264	1,712
2006	14,976	14,717	259
2007	14,976	16,063	-1,087
2008	14,976	15,114	-138
2009	14,976	16,950	-1,974
2010	14,976	16,647	-1,671
2011	14,976	16,810	-1,834
2012	14,976	15,145	-169
2013	14,976	14,546	430
<i>Average</i>	<i>14,976</i>	<i>13,997</i>	<i>979</i>

Table 16 - Hydropower demand (Howell et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Namibia. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	1,441	1,396	45
2001	1,441	1,211	230
2002	1,441	1,423	18
2003	1,441	1,419	22
2004	1,441	1,367	74
2005	1,441	1,656	-215
2006	1,441	1,512	-71
2007	1,441	1,542	-101
2008	1,441	1,395	46
2009	1,441	1,409	32
2010	1,441	1,247	194
2011	1,441	1,404	37
2012	1,441	1,607	-166
2013	1,441	1,272	169
<i>Average</i>	<i>1,441</i>	<i>1,419</i>	<i>22</i>

Table 17 - Hydropower demand (Howell et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Tanzania. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	1,460	2,135	-675
2001	1,460	2,640	-1,180
2002	1,460	2,720	-1,260
2003	1,460	2,549	-1,089
2004	1,460	2,001	-541
2005	1,460	1,778	-318

(Table 17 continued)

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2006	1,460	1,436	24
2007	1,460	2,524	-1,064
2008	1,460	2,649	-1,189
2009	1,460	2,640	-1,180
2010	1,460	2,701	-1,241
2011	1,460	1,993	-533
2012	1,460	1,767	-307
2013	1,460	1,717	-257
<i>Average</i>	<i>1,460</i>	<i>2,232</i>	<i>-772</i>

Table 18 - Hydropower demand (Howell et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Zambia. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	12,187	7,750	4,437
2001	12,187	7,893	4,294
2002	12,187	8,102	4,085
2003	12,187	8,257	3,930
2004	12,187	8,460	3,727
2005	12,187	8,883	3,304
2006	12,187	9,669	2,518
2007	12,187	9,631	2,556
2008	12,187	9,522	2,665
2009	12,187	9,881	2,306
2010	12,187	10,435	1,752
2011	12,187	11,483	704
2012	12,187	12,350	-163
2013	12,187	13,281	-1,094
<i>Average</i>	<i>12,187</i>	<i>9,686</i>	<i>2,501</i>

Table 19 - Hydropower demand (Howell et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Zimbabwe. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	3,803	3,194	609
2001	3,803	2,965	838
2002	3,803	3,809	-6
2003	3,803	5,344	-1,541
2004	3,803	5,501	-1,698
2005	3,803	4,915	-1,112
2006	3,803	5,310	-1,507

(Table 19 continued)

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2007	3,803	5,383	-1,580
2008	3,803	5,708	-1,905
2009	3,803	5,458	-1,655
2010	3,803	5,799	-1,996
2011	3,803	5,201	-1,398
2012	3,803	5,390	-1,587
2013	3,803	4,996	-1,193
Average	3,803	4,927	-1,124

Table 20 - Average hydropower demand, production and surplus/deficit at the hydropower plant level in the ZRB. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand. Demand and production data for the single plants are from Howells et al. (2011) and Spalding-Fecher et al. (2014) respectively.

Power plant	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
Cahora Bassa	14,495	14,729	-234
Kafue Gorge Upper	5391	5160	231
Victoria Falls	612	612	0
Kariba North	5882	2859	3043
Kariba South	3800	3584	216

2.4 AGRICULTURE, LIVESTOCK AND FISHERIES

2.4.1 Land used for rainfed and irrigated crop production and livestock production and water bodies used for fisheries

More than 60% of the population of the ZRB is active in agriculture (Lautze et al., 2017). Small-scale subsistence agriculture dominates throughout the basin. Animal husbandry and fisheries are also prominent, especially in the floodplains and dambos (World Bank, 2010a). Although the majority of the agriculture in the ZRB is rainfed, irrigated agriculture is the second largest consumptive water user in the ZRB, using ca. 1.5 km³ of water per year (Beck and Bernauer, 2010). Consumptive water usage has transboundary implications since water abstracted from the river at an upstream location is no longer available for usage more downstream along the river. In the following, we delineate the river basin areas currently used for food production in the ZRB and more specifically, those used for crop production, livestock production and fish catch and aquaculture.

Crops

For crop production, we make a distinction between rainfed and irrigated agriculture. The latter was done by identifying and –where possible– georeferencing individual irrigation schemes within the ZRB by using literature and open source satellite imagery provided by Google Earth. Further, information on the size of the irrigated perimeters and the crop types cultivated was collected if available. This information can later on be used in the WEF integrated model and in the AquaCrop crop growth model in order to better quantify the amount of water abstracted from the river and the corresponding crop yields. The irrigation schemes that could be georeferenced are mapped in Figure 50. Most of them are situated within the Kafue subbasin and in the Shire subbasin around Lake

Malawi. The perimeters of the irrigation schemes were digitized on the basis of Google Earth imagery. By subtracting the calculated area of the schemes from the total area under crops as determined in Deliverable 3.3 (D3.3)¹² through spatial disaggregation of agricultural statistics per administrative unit, the biophysical land units at least partially used for rainfed agriculture were found. The ensemble of these land unit is presented in Figure 51. Most rainfed agriculture is situated in the Kafue subbasin, in the Kariba/Tete subbasin around Lake Kariba and Cahora Bassa and in the Shire subbasin around Lake Malawi. In the western part of the ZRB, almost no rainfed agriculture was identified.

Livestock

In D3.3, statistics on livestock were collected from national reports. Alike the crop statistics, these statistics were available on various administrative levels, depending on the country. They were assigned to biophysical land units throughout the ZRB based on land use type (Figure 52). The ensemble of these land units is considered to be land that is -at least partially- used for livestock production. It is apparent from Figure 51 and Figure 52 that throughout the ZRB land units are present to which both rainfed crop production and livestock production are assigned.

Fisheries

D3.3 reported also statistics on fish catch and aquaculture production between 2012 and 2015 in the ZRB. Whereas no data were available about the location and characteristics of individual aquaculture production units, fish catch was assigned to the major surface water bodies in the ZRB (Figure 53).

Figure 50 - Operational irrigation schemes in the ZRB. Size of the dots reflects the size of the scheme.

¹² DAFNE-Deliverable 3.3. Agricultural productivity in the Zambezi and Omo-Turkana basins. April-2018.

Figure 51 - Land under rainfed agriculture in the ZRB.

Figure 52 - Land used for livestock production in the ZRB.

2.4.2 Food production from crops, livestock and fisheries

Food production from harvested crops, livestock products, and fish catch and aquaculture is discussed for the Pfaffstetter 5 subbasin level in the HydroSHEDS database¹³ (Figure 54). In the ZRB, 67 of such subbasins are present. Each one is characterised by a unique code, based on the Pfaffstetter coding system. For each of the 67 subbasins, the magnitude of annual food energy and proteins as available from harvested crops, livestock products, and fish catch and aquaculture was computed and compared with the required food energy and proteins needed to feed the local population within that subbasin. In this way, an estimate of food surplus or deficit per subbasin was obtained.

Crops

In D3.3, statistics on the production of the 20 major crops were disaggregated and assigned to biophysical land units (LUs) defined in terms of land use type and slope class covering the ZRB. Crop production was expressed in tonnes per year. In the case of multiple cropping cycles during one year, the corresponding production values were summed up. Of these 20 major crops, only 18 were retained here because seed cotton and tobacco were not considered to be food crops. The production values per LU of these 18 crops were summed per subbasin and converted into amount of calories (Figure 55) and proteins (Figure 56) based on the energy and protein contents of the produced crops published by FAO (2001) and USDA (2018) and presented in Table 21. Crop energy and protein production is highest in the Kafue and Luangwa subbasin and in the Shire subbasin around Lake Malawi.

Figure 53 - Major surface waterbodies associated with fish catch in the ZRB.

¹³ <https://www.hydrosheds.org>

Figure 54 - HydroSHEDS Pfaffstetter level 5 subbasins of the ZRB. The HydroSHEDS subbasin numbers are displayed for each of the 67 subbasins.

Figure 55 - Energy content of harvested crops in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the ZRB.

Figure 56 - Protein content of harvested crops in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the ZRB.

Table 21 - Energy content (kcal) and protein content (g) per 100g retail weight for 18 crops considered (from FAO (2001) and USDA (2018)).

Crop	Energy content [kcal/100g]	Protein content [g/100g]	Crop	Energy content [kcal/100g]	Protein content [g /100g]
Bambara groundnuts	567	25.7	Pigeon peas	343	20.9
Barley	332	11	Potato	67	1.6
Beans	341	22.1	Rice	357	7.5
Cassava	109	0.9	Sorghum	343	10.1
Cow peas	342	23.4	Soybeans	335	38
Groundnuts	567	25.7	Sugarcane	30	0.2
Maize	356	9.5	Sunflower seeds	308	12.3
Massango	340	9.7	Sweet potato	92	0.7
Millet	340	9.7	Wheat	334	12.2

Livestock

Head numbers for five categories of livestock (cattle, sheep, pigs, goats and poultry) reported for a given administrative unit in a given year were assigned to LUs in the ZRB as reported in D3.3 (Figure 52). In order to convert these livestock head numbers into livestock product offtake per animal per year, we estimated meat, milk and egg offtake from cattle, sheep, pigs, goats and poultry per livestock class and per year. The offtake values are dependent on the region and the corresponding dominating livestock production system (Otte and Chilonda, 2001). Therefore, for each of the 67 subbasins, the main livestock production system was determined based on the map about ruminant production systems in sub-Saharan Africa created by Otte and Chilonda (2001, Figure

57). Finally, we computed an estimate of the annual offtake of products per livestock class for each of these livestock production systems (Table 22). For cattle, goats and sheep, the values are based on Otte and Chilonda (2001). For pig and poultry products, they are based on Jahnke (1982) and no distinction could be made between the different livestock production systems.

Per subbasin, the total offtake of livestock products (in kg/year) was calculated and converted into amounts of calories (Figure 58) and proteins (Figure 59) based on the nutrient contents of the animal products derived from FAO (2001) and presented in Table 23. Livestock energy and protein production is highest in the Barotse floodplains, in the southern part of the Kafue subbasin, in the western part of the Luangwa subbasin, and in the Shire subbasin around Lake Malawi. In the western part of the ZRB, livestock energy and protein production is rather low.

Fisheries

The quantities of fish catch and aquaculture production calculated in D3.3 were summed per subbasin and converted into amounts of calories (Figure 60) and proteins (Figure 61) based on nutrient content of fresh fish as derived from FAO (2001). It was assumed that all fish caught and produced is pelagic fish. The energy and protein content is presented in Table 24.

Energy and protein production through fish catch and aquaculture is obviously the highest in the subbasins containing the major waterbodies from the ZRB, i.e. in the region of Lake Kariba, Lake Cahora Bassa and Lake Malawi. Energy and protein production from fish catch and production is, however, also high on the Barotse floodplains and in the southern part of the Kafue subbasin.

Crops, livestock and fisheries combined

For each of the 67 subbasins in the ZRB, the total annual agricultural output in terms of amounts of calories (Figure 62) and proteins (Figure 63) was calculated by summation of the amount of calories respectively proteins produced through harvested crops, livestock products, and fish catch and aquaculture. This production is highest in the Kafue subbasin, in the Shire subbasin around Lake Malawi and in the Luangwa subbasin.

Figure 57 - Main livestock production systems in the ZRB.

Table 22 - Annual livestock product offtake in kg per animal for the main agricultural zones (Figure 57) in the ZRB (from Otte and Chilonda (2001) and Jahnke (1982)).

Annual offtake [kg/animal]	Livestock production system		
	Agropastoral/ semi-arid mixed	Subhumid mixed	Humid mixed
<i>Cattle</i>			
Meat	10.9	12.1	13.2
Milk	40	26.4	25.5
<i>Sheep</i>			
Meat	2.9	2	2.1
Milk	3.3	3.1	1.6
<i>Goats</i>			
Meat	3	2.9	2.4
Milk	1.8	1.8	1.1
<i>Pigs</i>			
Meat	33	33	33
<i>Poultry</i>			
Meat	1	1	1
Eggs	1	1	1

Figure 58 - Energy content of produced livestock products in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the ZRB.

Figure 59 - Protein content of produced livestock products in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the ZRB.

Table 23 - Energy (kcal) and protein (g) content per 100g retail weight of livestock products considered (from FAO (2001)).

Livestock product	Energy content [kcal/100g]	Protein content [g proteins/100g]
<i>Cattle</i>		
Meat	150	18.5
Milk	61	3.3
<i>Sheep</i>		
Meat	263	13.5
Milk	94	5.9
<i>Goats</i>		
Meat	123	14.0
Milk	69	3.6
<i>Pigs</i>		
Meat	220	13.4
<i>Poultry</i>		
Meat	185	17.1
Eggs	139	10.7

Table 24 - Energy (kcal) and protein (g) content per 100g retail weight of fresh fish (from FAO (2001)).

	Energy content [kcal/100g]	Protein content [g/100g]
<i>Pelagic fish</i>	86	12.6

Figure 60 - Energy content of fish caught and produced in ZRB in terms of Teracalories per year per sub-basin.

Figure 61 - Protein content of fish caught and produced in ZRB in terms of tonnes protein per year per sub-basin.

Figure 62 - Total energy content of harvested crops, livestock and fish products in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the ZRB.

Figure 63 - Total protein content of harvested crops, livestock and fish products in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the ZRB.

2.4.3 Water use associated with irrigated crop production and livestock production

Crops

Although a proper assessment of crop water consumption will be provided through modelling results reported in D3.5, we carry out in this section a first attempt to estimate water requirements for irrigated agriculture by considering only areas that were identified as irrigated (Figure 50). We aggregate them by subbasin (Figure 64) and compute their corresponding gross irrigation water requirement.

D3.3 identified maize as the most produced crop in the ZRB. To calculate the gross irrigation water requirement in a subbasin, we therefore assumed that all irrigation schemes produced maize, and this all year round. Net irrigation water requirement was calculated by subtracting annual rainfall from annual crop water need. For each identified irrigation scheme, annual rainfall was derived from the FAO Global average annual precipitation map (FAO, 2000). Annual crop water need for maize was computed to be 1,551 mm. This value was calculated by assuming a growing period of 153 days and a crop water need of 650 mm per growing period and thus an average crop water need of 4.25 mm per day (Brouwer and Heibloem, 1986). Net irrigation water requirement was converted into gross irrigation water requirement by taking into account an irrigation efficiency of 70%. Finally, the gross irrigation water requirement of all irrigation schemes located in a subbasin, was summed within each subbasin (Figure 65). Following the distribution of the irrigated agricultural fields, irrigation water consumption is concentrated in the southern part of the Kafue subbasin and in the subbasins around Lake Kariba, Lake Cahora Bassa and Lake Malawi.

Figure 64 - Total area under irrigation (in hectares) per subbasin in the ZRB based on identified irrigation schemes.

Livestock

The total annual water requirement for livestock (Figure 66) was calculated by multiplying the average daily water requirement per animal with the total livestock head count per subbasin. The average daily water requirement for livestock is based on estimates available for Zambia (Kachunga, 2018) and can be found in **Error! Reference source not found.** In contrast to water consumption for irrigation but in line with the spatial distribution of livestock head counts (D3.3), water consumption for livestock production is relatively low around Lake Kariba and Lake Cahora Bassa, whereas it is higher in the Barotse floodplains, in the southern part of the Kafue subbasin, in the western part of the Luangwa subbasin and in the Shire subbasin around Lake Malawi.

Table 25 - Daily water requirement for livestock (from Kachunga (2018)).

Livestock	Average daily water requirement (l)
Cattle	52.5
Sheep	10.0
Goats	10.0
Pigs	20.0
Poultry	0.4

Figure 65 - Annual gross irrigation water requirement in hm³/yr per subbasin in the ZRB.

Figure 66 - Annual livestock water requirement in hm³/yr per subbasin in the ZRB.

2.5 ENVIRONMENT

2.5.1 Major water capturing and water dependent ecosystems

The ZRB includes 82 key biodiversity areas (BirdLife International, 2018). We identified 24 of those natural areas that are most relevant for the hydrological cycle as water dependent ecosystems such as lakes, rivers, streams, waterfalls, gorges, wetlands (floodplain grasslands, deltas) and riparian forests. Also included in this are areas that have an important role in supplying water from the upper catchments such as forests and dambo grasslands (Figure 67, Table 26).

2.5.2 Water-related services provided by water dependent ecosystems and indicators

Ecosystem services overview

Water-dependent ecosystems provide a variety of provisioning, regulating, supporting and cultural services. The estimated economic value for the biggest wetlands in the ZRB is given in Table 27. In terms of direct use value, the most important ecosystem services in both basins are the cultural service tourism and the provisioning services fisheries and flood recession agriculture. All of them are services that depend on the availability of sufficient water and this in competition for the resource that need to be shared with agriculture and hydropower.

Figure 67 - Location of the key natural areas with the biggest importance for the hydrological cycle. Areas are classified according to whether they are more water dependent or have a more water supplying function. The areas are listed in Table 26.

Table 26 - Name and characterization of the key natural areas with importance for the hydrological cycle.

Map ID	Name	Country	Protected	Area [km ²]	Type	Water
1	Cameia National Park	Angola	Whole	14,587	wetland	supplying
2	Minyanya Plain	Zambia	Little/ none	1,552	wetland	supplying
3	West Lunga NP and Lukwakwa GMA	Zambia	Whole	4,499	forest	supplying
4	Liuwa Plain National Park	Zambia	Whole	3,274	wetland	supplying
5	Barotse Floodplains	Zambia	Some	7,391	wetland	dependent
6	Mashi River	Angola/ Zambia	Little/ none	3,391	wetland	dependent
7	Chobe-Caprivi wetlands	Namibia	Most	6,704	wetland	dependent
8	Mosi-Oa-Tunya National Park (Victoria Falls)	Zambia	Most	89	wetland	dependent
9	Batoka Gorge	Zimbabwe	Little/ none	119	wetland	dependent
10	Kafue National Park	Zambia	Whole	22,476	wetland	supplying
11	Lukanga Swamp	Zambia	Little/ none	3,418	wetland	supplying
12	Kafue Flats	Zambia	Whole	6,547	wetland	dependent
13	North Swaka	Zambia	Whole	1,110	wetland	supplying
14	Wonder Gorge	Zambia	Little/ none	225	wetland	dependent
15	Lower Zambezi National Park	Zambia	Whole	4,323	wetland	dependent
16	Middle Zambezi Valley	Zimbabwe	Whole	10,240	wetland	dependent
17	North Luangwa National Park	Zambia	Whole	4,662	openland	dependent
18	South Luangwa National Park	Zambia	Whole	8,738	openland	dependent

(Table 26 continued)

Map ID	Name	Country	Protected	Area [km ²]	Type	Water
19	Lufirio catchment	Tanzania	Little/ none	2,054	forest	supplying
20	Lake Malawi catchment (Malawi)	Malawi	Little/ none	22,935	wetland	dependent
21	Lake Malawi catchment (Mozambique)	Mozambique	Little/ none	7,069	wetland	dependent
22	Lower Shire	Malawi/ Mozambique	Unknown	2,438	wetland	dependent
23	Zambezi Delta RAMSAR	Mozambique	Unknown	9,230	wetland	dependent
24	Zambezi Delta	Mozambique	Unknown	6,072	wetland	dependent

Tourism

Natural beauty and wildlife are the most important drivers for tourism in the ZRB. For example, more than 50% of tourists primarily come to Zambia to see Victoria falls (ID #8 in Figure 67) and an additional 30% to see wildlife in national parks (World Bank, 2010b). At Victoria falls, an estimated flow of 1000 m³/s are required for the most spectacular scenes for tourists (Shela, 2000b). Due to natural seasonal variability, these flow values are only reached for about half of the year, from February to July (World Bank, 2010b; Zambezi River Authority, 2018)). Therefore, various other activities have been added to the portfolio of the region, mostly related to adventure tourism. The gorges between Victoria falls and Lake Kariba (ID #9 in Figure 67) have gained a reputation as the best place in the world for whitewater rafting. Given the high prices tourists are willing to pay for this activity (around 135 US\$ per person), it generates an estimated 10 million US\$ per year (World Bank, 2010b). This activity can be carried out year round, as it requires a minimum flow of 500 m³/s (World Bank, 2010b). The planned Batoka gorge dam would lead to impoundment of the gorge and thus the loss of all fast current and rapids in this gorge, meaning this important part of the tourism industry will be lost (ERM, 2015).

Table 27 - Annual use values in Zambezi System Wetlands (summary of direct use values for six wetlands in the ZRB, and indirect use and existence values for four wetlands) (World Bank, 2010b).

Attribute	Barotse	Chobe-Caprivi	Kafue Flats	Lower Shire	Luangwa Wetlands	Zambezi Delta
Area of study [ha]	550,000	220,000	650,000	162,000	250,000	1,275,000
Direct use value [10 ⁶ \$ y ⁻¹]	11.0	5.0	28.3	24.0	10.8	15.0
Indirect use value [10 ⁶ \$ y ⁻¹]	43.9	22.0	—	36.6	—	79.9
Total annual value [10 ⁶ \$ y ⁻¹]	55.0	27.0	—	61.0	—	96.0
value/ha [\$ y ⁻¹]	100.0	123.0	—	377.0	—	75.0
Existence value [10 ⁶ \$ y ⁻¹]*	4.2	1.7	—	1.2	—	9.7

* Existence values refer to “intrinsic” non-use values based on the subjective valuation by individuals

National parks are the other main tourist attraction in the ZRB. The most visited are Chobe-Caprivi (ID #7 in Figure 67) and Kafue National parks (ID #10). Together with Victoria falls and other parks

in the region they form part of the Kavango-Zambezi Trans-frontier conservation area. Other well visited national parks are Lower Zambezi (ID #15), Middle Zambezi (ID #16) and Luangwa (ID #17, 18). Lake Malawi (ID #20, 21) and Lower Shire (ID #22) are becoming increasingly popular. The Zambezi delta (ID #23, 24) does not have a well-developed tourism infrastructure yet, but the potential is high due to large wildlife populations. Any upstream activity leading to a regulated flow in the delta (even more than what is already in place) can harm this potential.

Flood-recession agriculture

About 15,000 km² of cropped areas in the ZRB overlap with wetlands (based on the analysis in deliverable D3.4¹⁴). Hotspot areas are the Barotse plains (1,222 km²), the Kafue flats (1,003 km²) and the Lower Shire (1,396 km²). These numbers indicate the major importance of seasonally and permanently inundated areas for agriculture (Table 28). Regular flooding provides fresh plant nutrients and can maintain high water tables, making these areas much more reliable for small-scale food production than rainfed agriculture, as irrigation schemes are often too expensive for smallholders. Seasonally inundated areas are therefore of high importance for food security in the ZRB (McCartney and Nyambe, 2017). Dams typically reduce the occurrence of seasonal high and low flows and may thus lead to a loss of suitable areas for flood recession farming. Environmental flows therefore need to maintain seasonal, but also decadal variations in flow, to make sure inundation intervals are maintained or restored.

Fisheries

Fish is the main source of proteins for the majority of rural communities in riparian regions of the ZRB. The most important fishing ground is Lake Malawi (ID #20, 21), with the highest fish species diversity in the world (most of them endemic). Here, fish are caught for food as well as to sell them for ornamental reasons (Sturmbauer, 2008). Other important fishing grounds are the Barotse plains (ID #5), the Kafue flats (ID #12), the Lukanga wetlands (ID #11), Chobe-Capri (ID #7), Lower Shire (ID #22) and the Delta (ID #23, 24) as well as the three main reservoirs Kariba, Cahora Bassa and Itezhi-Tezhi (Table 29).

Major population declines have been reported for larger, most valuable fish species (Tweddle et al., 2015). The main reasons for this are unsustainable fishing practices and overfishing. In addition to that, fish depend on seasonal variation in surface waters, as inundated wetlands provide food, shelter and spawning habitats. Occasional high flows are also important to provide spawning cues to fishes. Streamflow regulation due to hydropower operation is therefore a direct competitor for this type of provisioning ecosystem service, especially in the Zambezi delta (affected wetlands ID #23 and 24 in Table 26), the Kafue flats (ID #12), the Lower Shire (ID #22) as well as the middle Zambezi (ID #15,16).

2.5.3 Impact of water-dependent ecosystems on water availability and water quality

Ecosystems have an integral role in the WEF nexus, as they not only depend on water availability, but their degradation also creates negative feedbacks on water availability and quality. Dambos and other upstream wetlands have an important role in regulating water supply to downstream river networks (von der Heyden, 2004). The most important areas in the ZRB that provide water supplying and supporting functions are those denoted in Figure 67 with the IDs 1, 2, 3, 4, 10, 11, 13 and 19.

Water filtration is another function, commonly associated with wetlands (Kadlec and Wallace, 2009). Sources of water pollution are so far very spotty across the ZRB. Water quality is mostly affected in areas of intensive agricultural, urban, mining and industrial activities, as well as where impoundments reduce flow speed and favour the accumulation of nutrients. In these cases, wetlands can have a mitigating role in filtering nutrients and pollutants. Depending on plant growth, wetlands can, however, also contribute to increasing nutrient levels in surface waters (Verhoeven et al.,

¹⁴ DAFNE-Deliverable 3.4. Models of demographic, cultural and social developments in the Omo-Turkana and Zambezi River Basins. August-2018.

2006). Biological invasions, such as the mass-expansion of exotic floating plants species, can become a major problem in areas with low flow-speed and high nutrient loads.

Low and ground layers of vegetation are essential in mitigating soil erosion, especially in areas of sloping terrain and seasonally heavy rainfalls (Labrière et al., 2015). Ecosystems providing dense vegetation cover, such as grasslands and multi-layered forests, therefore have a crucial role in avoiding loss of top soils and accumulation of sediments in rivers and reservoirs.

Table 28 - Overlaps between wetlands and recession agriculture areas within each of the key natural areas (own analysis based on D 3.3 and D 3.4).

Map ID	Name	Cultivated area [km ²]	Proportion of the overall area [%]
1	Cameia National Park	10.39	0.02
2	Minyanya Plain	3.55	0.07
3	West Lunga NP and Lukwakwa GMA	0.22	0.00
4	Liuwa Plain National Park	48.71	0.43
5	Barotse Floodplains	1,222.83	4.96
6	Mashi River	80.09	0.68
7	Chobe-Caprivi wetlands	591.15	2.58
8	Mosi-Oa-Tunya National Park (Victoria Falls)	1.88	0.61
9	Batoka Gorge	6.35	1.55
10	Kafue National Park	209.81	0.27
11	Lukanga Swamp	34.93	0.29
12	Kafue Flats	1,003.60	4.58
13	North Swaka	0.00	0.00
14	Wonder Gorge	1.40	0.18
15	Lower Zambezi National Park	13.51	0.09
16	Middle Zambezi Valley	37.35	0.10
17	North Luangwa National Park	24.54	0.15
18	South Luangwa National Park	69.86	0.23
19	Lufirio catchment	242.15	3.49
20	Lake Malawi catchment (Malawi)	153.51	0.19
21	Lake Malawi catchment (Mozambique)	12.76	0.05
22	Lower Shire	1,396.52	19.57
23	Zambezi Delta RAMSAR	38.11	0.12
24	Zambezi Delta	287.74	1.37

Table 29 - Fisheries (without Kapenta) in the ZRB. Source: (McCartney and Nyambe, 2017), based on (Tweddle, 2010; Tweddle et al., 2015).

Map ID	Fishery	Annual yield [t]	No. of fishers	Value [10 ⁶ \$]	Comment
5	Barotse floodplain	6,000-7,000	>1,000	4.94	Excessively overfished - shift from large high value to small low-value fish
NA	Lake Kariba	8,000-9,000	~1,300		Evidence of severely degraded fishery particularly on the Zambian side of the reservoir

(Table 29 continued)

Map ID	Fishery	Annual yield [t]	No. of fishers	Value [10 ⁶ \$]	Comment
12	Kafue Flats	6,000	~4,000	13.30	In recent years catch per unit of effort has declined significantly: 20 fish per gillnet set in the mid-1980s to 2 fish per set in 2005
11	Lukanga	1,000-2,600	N/A		The relative inaccessibility of the wetland has prevented the development of commercial fishing but overfishing is still a threat
NA	Itezhi-tezhi	1,200	1,250		Inshore lake fisheries are heavily exploited and the numbers of fishers have declined
NA	Lusiwashi	2,000-2,450	N/A		
NA	Lake Liambezi	~2,700	N/A		Illegal fishing methods by fishers from outside the locality mean that fishing levels are unsustainable
7	Caprivi	~1,500	>2,000	1.49	Estimated stock decline in large commercial species by >90% between 2010 and 2012
NA	Cahora Bassa	>6,000	>1,200		
22	Lower Shire	5,000-7,000	N/A	3.27	
23. 24	Delta	10,000	N/A	5.00	Declines associated with the reduced flooding caused by the Cahora Bassa Dam
NA	Marine	22,000**		21.70	Since the mid-1980s declines in shallow water landings are attributed to over-fishing in combination with environmental effects, including flow regulation

2.6 DEMOGRAPHY

2.6.1 Major urban centres

Characterised by large populations, intensive economic activity and infrastructural development, major urban centres inevitably constitute a disproportionately greater strain on natural resources, and water in particular. The demand for water, to sustain not just the income generating activities (D4.1 and D4.6 identify the major economic sectors as industry and mining, tourism, agriculture, and energy) associated with these centres but also the day to day needs of the population, creates resource stress both in form of quantity as well as quality due to the waste generated by these anthropological pressures. In reviewing the demography of the region, this report considers key urban centres (cities with a population greater than 100,000 inhabitants) within each of the eight riparian countries of the ZRB (Table 30). Of the 56 urban centres identified, nineteen are geographically located within the boundaries of the ZRB (shown in grey within Table 30). Three of these cities, Lilongwe, Lusaka, and Harare, are capital cities of Malawi, Zambia and Zimbabwe respectively. Harare with a population of 1,542,813 inhabitants, and Lusaka with a population of 1,267,440 inhabitants are by far the largest cities within the ZRB. Both cities host considerably larger populations than Bulawayo in Zimbabwe, which is a distant third at 699,385 inhabitants (World Population Review, 2018). Though not a national capital, Tete in Mozambique is the provincial capital of the Tete region. Located on the Zambezi, Tete is of significance to the WEF-Nexus discourse as not only is the province rich in coal resources, making it a key area of mining activity

within the region, but the Cahora Bassa dam is also located in the province. Furthermore, developments in the form of the Industrial Free Zone in the province announced by the Mozambique Ministry of Industry and Trade, is already drawing investment from major international funders such as the Metallurgical Corporation of China and the International Finance Corporation of the World Bank Group (Hellenic-African Chamber of Commerce, 2016). Another area of WEF-Nexus significance is the Copperbelt region of Zambia, within which lie the cities of Kitwe, Ndola, Chingola, Mufulira and Luanshya, all of which are major mining and industrial sites. Livingstone, the major urban centre with the least population at 109,203 inhabitants, is also heavily dependent on the waters of the Zambezi to sustain its thriving tourism industry and hydropower production, both of which are of major economic importance to Zambia as a whole. Africa is currently undergoing the highest rate of urbanisation globally, and with the population of the continent set to triple by 2030 (Hoelzel and Akisnete, 2015), additional strains and competition for the shared resource of the Zambezi are anticipated.

Table 30 - List of Major Urban Centres in ZRB Countries: ZRB Urban centres in grey (Source: World Population Review, 2018).

Country	City Name	Population (2018)	Location (Google Map link)	Coordinates	
Angola	Luanda	2,776,168	Link	-8.83682	13.23432
	N'dalatando	383,100	Link	-9.29782	14.91162
	Huambo	226,145	Link	-12.77611	15.73917
	Lobito	207,932	Link	-12.36440	13.53601
	Benguela	151,226	Link	-12.57626	13.40547
	Cuito	113,624	Link	-12.38333	16.93333
	Lubango	102,541	Link	-14.91717	13.49250
Botswana	Gaborone	208,411	Link	-24.65451	25.90859
Malawi	Lilongwe	646,750	Link	-13.96692	33.78725
	Blantyre	584,877	Link	-15.78499	35.00854
	Mzuzu	175,345	Link	-11.46556	34.02071
Mozambique	Maputo	1,191,613	Link	-25.9655	32.5832
	Matola	675,422	Link	-25.9622	32.4589
	Beira	530,604	Link	-19.8436	34.8389
	Nampula	388,526	Link	-15.1165	39.2666
	Chimoio	256,936	Link	-19.1164	33.4833
	Nacala	224,795	Link	-14.5626	40.6854
	Quelimane	188,964	Link	-17.8786	36.8883
	Tete	129,316	Link	-16.1564	33.5867
	Xai-Xai	127,366	Link	-25.0519	33.6442
	Maxixe	119,868	Link	-23.8597	35.3472
	Ressano Garcia	110,000	Link	-25.4428	31.9953
	Lichinga	109,839	Link	-13.3128	35.2406
	Pemba	108,737	Link	-12.9740	40.5178
Namibia	Windhoek	268,132	Link	-22.55941	17.08323

(Table 30 continued)

Country	City Name	Population (2018)	Location (Google Map link)	Coordinates	
Tanzania	Dar es Salaam	2,698,652	Link	-6.82349	39.26951
	Mwanza	436,801	Link	-2.51667	32.90000
	Zanzibar	403,658	Link	-6.16394	39.19793
	Arusha	341,136	Link	-3.36667	36.68333
	Mbeya	291,649	Link	-8.90000	33.45000
	Morogoro	250,902	Link	-6.82102	37.66122
	Tanga	224,876	Link	-5.06893	39.09875
	Dodoma	180,541	Link	-6.17221	35.73947
	Kigoma	164,268	Link	-4.87694	29.62667
	Moshi	156,959	Link	-3.35000	37.33333
	Tabora	145,292	Link	-5.01622	32.82663
	Songea	126,449	Link	-10.68333	35.65000
	Musoma	121,119	Link	-1.50000	33.80000
	Iringa	111,820	Link	-7.76667	35.70000
	Katumba	108,558	Link	-9.23333	33.61667
Shinyanga	107,362	Link	-3.66393	33.42118	
Zambia	Lusaka	1,267,440	Link	-15.40669	28.28713
	Kitwe	400,914	Link	-12.80243	28.21323
	Ndola	394,518	Link	-12.95867	28.63659
	Kabwe	188,979	Link	-14.44690	28.44644
	Chingola	148,564	Link	-12.52897	27.88382
	Mufulira	120,500	Link	-12.54982	28.24071
	Luanshya	113,365	Link	-13.13667	28.41661
	Livingstone	109,203	Link	-17.84194	25.85425
Zimbabwe	Harare	1,542,813	Link	-17.82772	31.05337
	Bulawayo	699,385	Link	-20.15000	28.58333
	Chitungwiza	340,360	Link	-18.01274	31.07555
	Mutare	184,205	Link	-18.97070	32.67086
	Gweru	146,073	Link	-19.45000	29.81667
	Epworth	123,250	Link	-17.89000	31.14750

2.6.2 Population number by subbasin

Population distribution within the ZRB was calculated by first disaggregating the river basin into the DAFNE subbasins (67 within the ZRB, see Figure 68). Using a combination of satellite and other geodatasets, total area, population density, and consequently total population was calculated for each of the subbasins within the ZRB (Linard et al., 2012; worldpop, 2015). The results of this exercise are depicted in Figure 68, Figure 69 and Figure 70, and summarised in Table 31. The average population density across the ZRB is calculated at 30.86 inhabitants per km², with a total population of 40,026,804 inhabitants within the entire river basin. This number is validated by existing reports by the Zambezi Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM), which estimates the total population of the river basin at approximately 40·10⁶ inhabitants (ZAMCOM, 2016). The population density has been calculated using observed night-light occurrence based on a normalised scale of 1-100. While it is believed that this methodology provides a more sensitive analysis of population density,

further research would be required to fully address divergences in population estimates available from the literature.

Figure 68 - Population density per subbasin within the ZRB (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Figure 69 - Night light index per subbasin within ZRB (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Figure 70 - Night Light Intensity across the ZRB (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Table 31 - Population Density ZRB: Breakdown by Pfaffstetter level 5 subbasin (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Subbasin Number	Normalised night light index [-]	Mean population density [1/km ²]	Area [km ²]	Total population [-]
1	1.92	32.31	4,455	143,955
2	6.81	17.05	11,260	192,038
3	26.91	150.42	43,169	6,493,504
4	93.63	299.41	8,537	2,556,041
5	7.43	95.36	12,851	1,225,415
6	8.85	147.87	11,776	1,741,302
7	2.35	29.44	3,538	104,154
8	9.20	71.41	8,355	596,617
9	3.21	54.77	21,474	1,176,123
10	3.41	58.65	40,318	2,364,467
11	15.69	79.51	12,382	984,446
12	2.35	19.89	26,371	524,474
13	11.80	41.14	55,185	2,270,559
14	100.00	22.25	1,186	26,385
15	21.69	53.27	16,517	879,784
16	26.41	30.01	9,465	284,010
17	4.15	20.68	29,468	609,488
18	4.27	14.06	34,589	486,473
19	82.17	101.98	25,323	2,582,401
20	3.43	7.74	773	5,985

(Table 31 continued)

Subbasin Number	Normalised night light index [-]	Mean population density [1/km ²]	Area [km ²]	Total population [-]
21	1.28	8.54	7,823	66,802
22	11.79	13.24	44,872	594,045
23	4.42	19.91	23,342	464,778
24	28.49	50.60	10,565	534,545
25	1.11	8.35	15,918	132,848
26	1.84	4.69	6,316	29,639
27	1.00	2.27	2,748	6,233
28	8.93	45.66	4,660	212,789
29	1.51	9.16	34,534	316,446
30	50.98	68.63	19,229	1,319,637
31	28.41	35.60	64,466	2,294,882
32	2.51	3.14	10,608	33,294
33	1.00	8.47	2,110	17,877
34	14.30	6.08	24,872	151,331
35	1.00	6.56	4,725	31,012
36	2.91	12.50	13,618	170,270
37	1.00	16.19	2,793	45,213
38	1.02	8.47	9,514	80,585
39	83.73	80.07	25,136	2,012,608
40	24.51	26.04	4,483	116,747
41	10.93	25.20	51,478	1,297,108
42	2.60	18.95	3,917	74,217
43	3.20	53.71	6,911	371,158
44	1.92	14.24	4,071	57,963
45	1.07	15.56	10,304	160,359
46	7.66	18.54	19,966	370,193
47	19.33	30.33	43,815	1,328,934
48	18.70	17.42	22,065	384,317
49	5.76	3.60	13,461	48,526
50	1.03	0.90	21,402	19,256
51	1.17	1.34	13,045	17,505
52	1.00	0.67	38,581	25,741
53	1.00	2.14	32,267	69,080
54	1.00	0.34	7,917	2,727
55	1.00	0.55	9,832	5,424
56	1.00	0.86	10,197	8,723
57	1.00	1.07	9,811	10,501
58	4.36	7.26	82,523	599,115
59	1.20	2.67	42,448	113,383
60	2.37	7.99	25,184	201,184
61	1.00	4.23	47,436	200,707
62	1.00	18.45	258	4,760

(Table 31 continued)

Subbasin Number	Normalised night light index [-]	Mean population density [1/km ²]	Area [km ²]	Total population [-]
63	3.76	5.76	72,895	420,000
64	1.00	3.16	28,164	89,041
65	1.08	2.37	42,141	99,827
66	4.65	7.93	24,280	192,422
67	1.31	21.01	5,683	119,386
<i>Mean Population Density</i>		30.86		
<i>Total Area (km²)</i>			1,399,376	
<i>Total Population</i>			1,399,376.00	40,026,804

2.6.3 Water consumption by private households

Making use of the water consumption in the domestic sector for each country of the ZRB, computed as a percentage of the annual total water withdrawals per country, it is possible to estimate the annual water consumption per capita for the domestic sector (withdrawals for domestic uses include drinking water, municipal use or supply, and use for public services, commercial establishments and homes). For the purpose of this estimation, it is assumed that this percentage remains stable from 2002. Additionally, using the ZRB share (%) of each riparian country (Beck and Bernauer, 2011) and assuming that the domestic consumption per capita is homogeneous across each country, the total water consumption of the part of each riparian country within the ZRB can be estimated. The results of this estimation are summarized in the following Table 32.

Table 32 - Annual water consumption per capita in m³ for private households in the ZRB countries (Source: World Bank, 2018).

Country	ZRB Share (%)	Water Use per Capita	Water Use In ZRB [m ³]
Angola	18.2	13.99	70,974,127
Botswana	1.5	44.38	1,470,662
Malawi	7.5	9.95	13,114,304
Mozambique	11.6	8.88	28,850,380
Namibia	1.1	36.42	971,728
Tanzania	2.2	14.6	17,308,475
Zambia	41.9	26.08	175,947,818
Zimbabwe	15.9	47.13	118,225,143

The diversity among the numbers in Table 32 can be attributed to the percentage of the population that uses at least basic drinking water services. More specifically, in Botswana, Namibia and Zimbabwe, which show a much bigger water consumption per capita than the rest of the countries, this percentage is quite high (about 70%) in comparison with the other countries of the river basin whose percentage ranges from 30%-50%.

Based on the estimates of the total annual private households water consumption per capita of the ZRB countries (Table 32) and the population density for each of the ZRB subbasin (Table 31), it is

possible to compute the total water consumption of the private households disaggregated by sub-basin in each country. In the case of transboundary subbasins, an average consumption value per capita of the subbasin countries was used. The resulting values are reported in Table 33.

Table 33 - Total annual water consumption by private households accessing basic water services in the ZRB: Breakdown by subbasin.

Subbasin Number	Water Use [m ³]	Subbasin Number	Water Use [m ³]
1	167,036	35	227,676
2	222,828	36	1,250,039
3	9,698,969	37	331,934
4	4,669,756	38	591,616
5	1,830,331	39	14,775,568
6	3,181,270	40	992,007
7	155,567	41	12,520,605
8	1,089,989	42	716,393
9	2,148,715	43	12,893
10	10,996,112	44	20,734
11	1,798,531	45	24,963
12	608,565	46	2,911,282
13	21,917,040	47	550,962
14	30,615	48	1,476,994
15	1,607,319	49	975,295
16	329,546	50	34,942
17	707,210	51	2,040,907
18	564,471	52	432,678
19	24,927,160	53	485,088
20	6,944	54	457,407
21	490,427	55	138,527
22	4,361,181	56	12,893
23	3,412,164	57	20,734
24	3,924,365	58	24,963
25	975,302	59	2,911,282
26	217,593	60	550,962
27	45,760	61	1,476,994
28	1,562,190	62	975,295
29	2,323,188	63	34,942
30	11,213,094	64	2,040,907
31	16,847,881	65	432,678
32	244,428	66	485,088
33	131,242	67	457,407
34	1,110,994		
<i>Total Water Use [m³]</i>			<i>201,710,099</i>

Figure 71 shows that in Zambia the water use in the Private Households sector exhibits a slightly increasing trend of 0.18% from 1990 to 2015, with only a slight decrease of 0.021% in 2009. It is worth mentioning that between 1990 and 2003 the fluctuations are minor and thus the water use over this period can be considered relatively stable. Overall, there are no extreme variations from

the average water use in this sector. A similar increasing trend is also exhibited by almost all the other countries of the ZRB (Angola 1.95%, Botswana 0.09%, Malawi 0.23%, Mozambique 1.15%, Namibia 0.35%, Zimbabwe 0.11%) largely as a result of population growth, improved water services and sanitation infrastructure (World Bank, 2018).

Figure 71 - Trend plot of annual water use by private households in Zambia (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

The singular exception to this trend is Tanzania; which as shown in Figure 72, exhibits a minor increasing trend of 0.02% from 1990 to 2003, where it reaches a water use steady state till 2011, and then experiences a decrease of -0.08% from 2012 to 2015. As yet, a review of the literature has failed to explain this pattern of consumption, however it is worth noting that since 2009, the country has witnessed a slight decrease in its population growth rate. While this does not in itself explain the observed consumption trend, it potentially hints at wider changes within the dynamics of the socio-economic system of the country (World Bank, 2018).

Figure 72 - Trend plot of annual water use by private households in Tanzania (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

2.6.4 Energy consumption and access to electricity by private households

As in the preceding subsection, the energy consumption in the domestic sector for each country of the ZRB is used to estimate the annual energy consumption per capita for the domestic sector. In this case, energy consumption refers to energy usage from coal, petroleum, natural gas, and biomass & waste electricity. Additionally, using the ZRB share (%) of each riparian country (Beck and Bernauer, 2011) and assuming that the domestic energy consumption per capita is homogeneous across each country, it is possible to estimate the total energy consumption of the respective portion of each river basin country within the ZRB. The resulting values are summarized in Table 34.

Table 34 - Private households energy consumption per capita in KWh per year of the ZRB countries (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017 and World Bank, 2018).

Country	ZRB Share (%)	Energy Use per Capita 2015	Energy Use In ZRB [TJ]
Angola	18.2	2,552.12	46,585
Botswana	1.5	2,748.52	328
*Malawi	7.5	11.06	52
Mozambique	11.6	2,336.10	27,326
Namibia	1.1	1,016.62	98
Tanzania	2.2	2,772.82	11,832
Zambia	41.9	3,173.35	77,068
Zimbabwe	15.9	4,034.96	36,440

* "Energy use per capita" includes use of coal only

The figure for 'energy use per capita' in Malawi depicted within Table 34, is observably low as the value refers only to energy consumption per capita from coal due to data availability. Based on the estimates of the total annual private households energy consumption per capita of the ZRB countries (Table 34) and the population density for each of the ZRB subbasin (Table 31), the total energy consumption of the private households disaggregated by subbasin in each country has been calculated. The resulting values are reported in Table 35.

Table 35 - Energy consumption in the ZRB subbasins

Subbasin ID	Energy use [TJ]	Subbasin ID	Energy Use [TJ]
1	1,210.66	35	354.29
2	1,615.03	36	1,945.18
3	27,434.34	37	516.52
4	101.79	38	920.61
5	5,177.24	39	22,992.18
6	69.34	40	1514.78
7	440.04	41	18,841.61
8	23.76	42	1,078.06
9	46.84	43	5,391.39
10	11,848.32	44	752.062
11	39.20	45	2,329.35
12	4,410.80	46	4,803.24
13	32,981.81	47	19,303.91
14	221.90	48	4,986.50
15	35.03	49	177.60
16	2,388.51	50	145.97

(Table 35 continued)

Subbasin ID	Energy use [TJ]	Subbasin ID	Energy Use [TJ]
17	5,125.77	51	141.62
18	4,091.22	52	236.50
19	37,511.59	53	711.93
20	50.33	54	25.05
21	763.15	55	49.83
22	6,786.41	56	80.14
23	5,309.65	57	96.48
24	6,106.68	58	6,174.39
25	1,517.66	59	1,168.51
26	338.60	60	2,298.34
27	71.21	61	2,068.46
28	2,430.92	62	54.3743
29	3,615.10	63	4,328.46
30	17,122.24	64	917.66
31	26,216.89	65	1,028.80
32	380.35	66	1,767.90
33	204.23	67	1,004.03
34	1,728.81		
<i>Total Energy Use [TJ]</i>			<i>316,110.5</i>

Figure 73 shows that in Zambia the energy use within private households exhibits a considerable upward trend of 85.3% from 1990 to 2015. It is worth mentioning that after 2008 the energy consumption reaches levels that are close to twice the average energy use of this sector for the observed period (1990-2015). As at 2012, it was estimated that 95% of energy used by rural Zambian households, was derived from woody biomass and charcoal (REEEP, 2012). With both national and international efforts made to improve access to energy under programs such as the United Nations’ Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL) which was launched in 2011 (Prasad, 2011; SE4ALL, 2018), this figure had dropped to 58.62 % of total number of households by 2016 (World Bank, 2016). This rapid increase in the numbers of households substituting woody biomass for alternative forms of energy coupled with a high rate of population growth explains the observed trend in energy consumption patterns in Figure 71. A similarly increasing trend is also exhibited by all the other countries of the ZRB (Angola 122.74%, Botswana 180.5%, Malawi 106.46%, Mozambique 77.8%, Namibia 187.7 %, Tanzania 151.6%, Zimbabwe 112,77%).

Access to electricity by private households

Access to electricity still remains a challenge in much of Sub-Saharan Africa, with 55% of the population living without access to electricity (Rehman et al., 2012). Most countries in this region have average electricity access rates of about 20%, several million people are connected to an unreliable grid that does not meet their daily energy service needs, and two out of three people lack access to modern energy services (Avila et al., 2017). Taking into account both the current pace of electricity grid expansion, as well as projected population growth in the region, no more than half a billion Africans (out of a total projected population of well over 8.5 billion) will have access to electricity by 2040 (UN, 2015; IEA, 2016); full electricity access in the region is not expected earlier than 2080 (Africa Progress Panel, 2015).

Table 36 depicts the levels of electricity access across the riparian countries of the ZRB, expressed as a percentage of the total population (World Bank, 2018). It is not surprising that in 2016 only two countries, Botswana and Namibia, have electricity access rates exceeding 50%, while the remainder of the region has an average access rate of just 24.84%. Furthermore, each

country exhibits a slightly increasing trend of electricity access rate, which cannot meet the growing demand from the total population; as such electricity production from alternative energy sources is a key priority for sustainable development in the region.

Figure 73 - Trend Graph of annual energy use for private households in Zambia (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

2.6.5 Food surplus/deficit at subbasin scale

Food production versus food requirements

By comparing at subbasin scale the amount of calories and proteins obtained from harvested crops, livestock and fish products, as derived in section 2.4.2, with the amount of calories and proteins required by the private households, we calculated the food deficit or surplus.

Daily food energy and protein requirement numbers (in kcal/capita and g proteins/capita) were available per country for the year 2000-2013. From these data we computed the average daily food energy and protein requirement for each country. In the case of a subbasin being shared among multiple countries, we calculated the weighted average of daily food energy and protein requirement per capita and subbasin by assuming a weight proportional to the fraction of the area of the country within the subbasin. By multiplying the average daily food energy requirement per capita for each subbasin with the population number within that subbasin (see section 2.6.2), we calculated the total food energy and protein requirement per day. These numbers were converted to annual requirements by simply multiplying by 365 days.

The absolute food production surplus or deficit was calculated by subtracting the annual food energy (and protein) requirement from the annual produced food energy (proteins). A positive value indicates a food production surplus within the subbasin, while a negative value indicates a food production deficit (Figure 74 and Figure 75). The daily food production deficit/surplus per subbasin was calculated by dividing the absolute food production deficit or surplus by the number of people living within the subbasin and by 365 days (Figure 76 and Figure 77).

It can be seen that in a large part of the ZRB, there is an overproduction of food calories and proteins compared to the requirements for that basin. This is especially true for proteins which are predominantly coming from livestock products. Food deficit (both in terms of calories and proteins) is mainly situated in the north-west of the ZRB (i.e. in the upper Zambezi, Luengue Bungo and Luanganga basins), and in the southern part of the ZRB in the Kariba-Tete subbasin.

Table 36 - Fraction (%) of population with access to electricity within ZRB (Source: World Bank, 2018).

Country	2013	2014	2015	2016
Angola	36.99	32.00	42.00	40.52
Botswana	54.21	56.37	58.53	60.69
Malawi	9.00	11.90	10.80	11.00
Mozambique	20.70	21.86	24.00	24.20
Namibia	47.40	49.62	50.70	51.78
Tanzania	16.40	18.91	18.50	32.80
Zambia	25.47	27.90	31.10	27.22
Zimbabwe	37.08	32.30	33.70	38.15
<i>ZRB Average</i>	<i>30.91</i>	<i>31.36</i>	<i>33.67</i>	<i>35.79</i>

The food production deficit in the upper Zambezi, Luengue Bungo and Luanginga river basins can be explained by the lack, relative to population density, of agricultural developments in this area. Almost 65% of the land is covered by forest and over 30% by shrub and grassland (ESA, 2018). Further, an important key ecosystem, the Cameia National Park is located in the area (Figure 67), in which only a very limited proportion (0.02%) is cultivated (Table 28). This lack of agricultural developments can also be seen in the low number of operational irrigation schemes in the area (Figure 50), and is not caused by a shortage of water. With an annual precipitation between 800 and 1400 mm/year, the area is characterised by a humid climate (Figure 6 and Figure 7). Therefore, this area has the potential to increase its agricultural production in the future but trading off with other ecosystem services is at stake. Further, with the lack of any major water bodies in the upper Zambezi, Luengue Bungo and Luanginga river basins, fish catch and fish production in this part of the basin is also limited (Figure 53). Despite the relatively high amount of annually applied irrigation water in this area, the Kariba-Tete subbasin is characterized by a food production deficit. It is speculated this deficit is the result of the dry character of the area. Annual precipitation is in the majority of this part of the ZRB lower than 800 mm with some areas receiving even less than 600 mm precipitation per year (Figure 7). However, with the availability of water from Lake Kariba and Lake Cahora Bassa, there is a potential to further develop the irrigated agriculture and reduce the food deficit.

The food production surplus in terms of calories per capita per day is largest in the Luangwa subbasin (Figure 76). In the southern part of the Shire subbasin, there is a relatively large food production surplus in terms of both calories (Figure 76) and proteins (Figure 77). The food surplus in the Luangwa subbasin can be explained by the high amount of food calories produced through crop production (Figure 55), livestock products (Figure 58) while the area is characterized by a relatively low population density (Table 31). Food surplus in the southern part of the Shire subbasin can be explained by the availability of water from Lake Malawi resulting in a high amount of food calories and proteins produced through irrigated crops (Figure 55 and Figure 56), livestock products (Figure 58 and Figure 59), and fish catch and production (Figure 60 and Figure 61). While in the Luangwa subbasin, most of the crop calories and proteins are produced through rainfed agriculture, the extent of irrigated agriculture in this part of the Shire subbasin is relatively high (Figure 64).

Figure 74 - Food production deficit/surplus (in Teracalories per year) per subbasin in the ZRB.

2.7 ECONOMY, INDUSTRY, MINING

2.7.1 Major industrial and mining sites

The manufacturing sector plays a prominent role in all developing countries which have succeed in growing their economy to attain upper-middle or high income status. The main challenge for these countries is to transition from an economic growth pathway built on consumption and commodity imports to a more sustainable developmental pathway based on environmentally and socially conscious industrialization. To this end, these countries need to formulate and implement national policies and strategies for stimulating and enhancing their productive capacities, enhancing economies of scale and scope, and maintaining the competitiveness of industries; all while striving to meet the targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SADC, 2013; United Nations, 2016).

This section presents key industrial and mining activity within the ZRB. The eight riparian countries of the ZRB represent a wide range of economic conditions. The annual economic growth of the region is more than 6%, its annual gross domestic product (GDP) is \$100 bn while the GDP per capita ranges from \$122 in Zimbabwe to more than \$7,000 in Botswana. Angola, Botswana, and Namibia have healthy current account surpluses, mainly due to their oil and diamond resources (World Bank, 2010).

Major industrial sites

In the industrial sector of Zambia, there has been a gradual, but sustained, expansion of the manufacturing sector particularly in the processed food sub-sector which provides extensive linkages with the agricultural sector. The past decade it has also shown noticeable growth in some non-traditional export sectors, notably the horticultural, cement and sugar industries.

Table 37 outlines major industrial and mining sites in the ZRB, based on information collected from stakeholders as well as a review of literature and official reports. *Zambian Breweries Plc (Zambrew)*, listed on the Lusaka Securities Exchange, has a virtual monopoly on clear brew products in Zambia. The company has two breweries and three bottling plants in Zambia with more than 200 beer brands in its international product portfolio (*Zambian Breweries Plc*, 2012). *Dangote Cement* is a fully-fledged integrated cement manufacturing operation in Zambia, whose business is organised into two strategic regions: Nigeria and the Rest of Africa (*Dangote Cement Plc*, 2016). *Kafue*

Sugar is sits on a 9,000 hectare estate with its processing mill along the banks of the Kafue River, and currently holds a 30% share of the sugar industry in Zambia (Sable Transport and Construction Ltd, 2018).

Figure 75 - Food production deficit/surplus (in tonnes proteins per year) per subbasin in the ZRB.

Figure 76 - Food production deficit/surplus (in kcal per capita per day) per subbasin in the ZRB.

Figure 77 - Food production deficit/surplus (in grams proteins per capita per day) per subbasin in the ZRB.

Table 37 - List of major industrial sites in ZRB (Source: World Industrial Information, 2017; Avior Capital Market, 2018; Lusaka Times, 2017, World Industrial Information, 2018a).

Site	Type	Annual Production	Location	Coordinates	
Dangote Plant I	Cement Manufacturing Plant	1.50 · 10 ⁶ t	Masaiti, Ndola, Copperbelt, Zambia	-13.025408	28.778664
Zambia Breweries	Alcoholic and non-Alcoholic beverage production	1.75 · 10 ⁶ hl	Plot Number 6438 Mungwi Road	-15.391653	28.247620
			Heavy Industrial Area Lusaka, Zambia Ndola, Zambia	-13.0170293	28.6475258
Kafue Sugar Refining Mill	Sugar Refining Mill	23,000 t	Kafue Flats, Kafue District, Lusaka, Zambia	-15.583347	27.959217

Major mining sites

The mining sector is one of the major users of water in the ZRB, with predominantly copper and coal mining taking place within the ZRB regions of Zambia and Mozambique. The mining industry has been the most important driving force of economic development in Zambia for over 70 years (AfDB/OECD, 2003). Zambia is well endowed with mineral resources and derives most of its foreign earnings from the export of minerals. The heart of the Zambian mining industry, the Copperbelt Province, is situated within the ZRB. Mining activity in the region predominantly involves copper, but also includes coal and a few other minerals, such as zinc, silver, gold and cobalt. The Kansanshi mine in Zambia is the eighth largest copper mine in the world and the largest in Africa. Having undergone several expansions since it began operating in 2005, from an initial production capacity of 110,000 tonnes of copper, Kansanshi is now capable of producing 400,000 tonnes of copper and more than 120,000 ounces of gold per year. Despite the importance of mining in terms of contributions to Zambia’s national export earnings (over 70%), the industry employs less than 2% of the population (UN-Zambia, 2015). In Mozambique, the mining activity predominantly centers around coal. Benga is one such coal mine which is situated in the ZRB, and is a greenfield

coking and thermal coal mine located in the Tete Province of Mozambique. The mine has coal reserves amounting to 1.9 billion tonnes of cooking coal. This is one of the largest coal reserves; not just in Africa, but in the world (Dutt, 2013; Mining Technology, 2018). Table 38 outlines major industrial and mining sites in the ZRB, based on information collected from stakeholders as well as a review of literature and official reports.

Table 38 - List of major mining sites in ZRB (Source: World Industrial Information, 2018b; 2018c; Mining for Zambia, 2018; Zambia Chamber of Mines, 2018).

Site	Type	Annual Production	Location	Coordinates	
Chambishi 2	Copper mine	800,000 t of Copper Ore	Chambishi, Copperbelt, Zambia	-12.659640	28.375844
Mopani-Mufulira	Copper mine	n/a	Mufulira, Copperbelt, Zambia	-12.514777	28.209825
Mopani-Nkana	Copper mine	n/a	Kitwe, Copperbelt, Zambia	-12.836491	28.199087
Konkola (KCM)	Copper mine	n/a	Chingola, Copperbelt, Zambia	-12.379608	27.829210
Kansanshi	Copper mine	245,000 t of Copper	Kanshanshi, North West, Zambia	-12.088106	26.427656
Lumwana Mine	Copper Mine	97,000 t of Copper	Lumwana Mine, T5 Highway, Solwezi, North-Western, Zambia	-12.231352	25.820742
Benga	Coal Mine	5 million t of Coking Coal	Benga, Changara District, Tete Province, Mozambique	-16.173253	33.673475
Chirodzi	Coal Mine	10 million t of Coal	Caurisa, Tete Province, Mozambique	-15.914093	33.013188
Minas Moatize	Coal Mine	11 million t of Coal	Moatize, Tete Province, Mozambique	-16.173529	33.810205

Employment in industry (including mining)

The level of employment within a country remains a key indicator for economic development. National and regional strategies geared towards industrial development, economic diversification, and productive capacity, are aimed at creating employment in order to reduce poverty. With a focus on the productive use of water, and its impacts therein (in the form of employment opportunities within the major WEF sectors), this section reviews employment within industry and mining across the eight riparian countries of the ZRB (SADC, 2013).

Figure 76 shows that in Zambia a decreasing trend of -42.37% for the employment in the Industry (including mining) sector is exhibited from 1991 to 2000. Following this a considerable increasing trend of 103.24% occurred from 2000 to 2017. That aside, there are no extreme variations from the average employment of 7.99% in this sector. The mining and quarrying sector registered high economic growth between 2005 and 2012 (13% per year) but created relatively little employment. Average monthly earnings of employees in this sector increased by almost 25% between 2005 and 2012, while productivity increased by 7.3% per year over the same period. A similar increasing trend behaviour is also exhibited by Mozambique (48.8%), Namibia (30.33%) and Tanzania (17.4%).

On the other hand, countries such as Botswana, Malawi and Zimbabwe exhibit decreasing trends of employment in industry and mining (-49.4%, -22.16% and -50.6% respectively). Figure 70 illustrates the extreme case in Zimbabwe with a decreasing trend of -50.6% for the employment in the Industry (including mining) sector from 1992 to 2017. Furthermore, except for the high employment

rate time period of 1991-1995, there are no extreme variations from the average employment of 10.71% in this sector. During the structural adjustment period from 1991 to 1998 there was a slight decline in manufacturing employment, because of firm re-structuring and high competition on the domestic market, which forced firms to reduce capacity utilisation or shut down production entirely. Manufacturing employment continued to decline through to 2005 due to foreign currency shortages and government price controls. As controls increased from 2000 onwards, there was also an out-flow of foreign capital, thus reducing the level of investment in the economy (Chimhowu, 2010).

Figure 78 - Trend graph for employment in industry (including mining) in Zambia (Source: World Ban, 2018).

Figure 79 - Trend graph for employment in industry (including mining) in Zimbabwe (Source: World Bank, 2018).

Figure 80 - Trend graph for employment in industry (including mining) in Angola (Source: World Bank, 2018).

2.7.2 Water use by industry and mining

This section reviews the use of water within the ZRB in the context of industrial and mining activity. As indicated in previous sections of this report, the riparian countries of the ZRB have witnessed considerable economic development in recent years, spurred by activities within the industrial and mining sectors. A review of the economies of these countries conducted within Deliverable 4.1¹⁵, indicates the varying degrees of importance of each sector to their respective GDPs. Consequently, variations in the total water use within industry and mining for each of the riparian countries is set out in Table 39.

Table 39 – Annual water consumption for Industry and Mining in the ZRB countries (Source: Lautze et al., 2017).

Country	Mining Water Use In ZRB [Mm ³]	Industrial Water Use In ZRB [Mm ³]	Total [Mm ³]
Angola	1.43	0.67	2.1
Botswana	0.33	0.28	0.61
Malawi	0.05	0.23	0.28
Mozambique	41.9	86.9	128.8
Namibia	31.2	64.7	95.9
Tanzania	0.42	0.86	1.28
Zambia	18.8	39	57.8
Zimbabwe	5.56	11.5	17.06
<i>Zambezi River Basin [10⁶ m³]</i>	<i>99.69</i>	<i>204.14</i>	<i>303.83</i>

¹⁵ DAFNE-Deliverable 4.1. Models of the economic development in the Zambezi river basin. December-2017.

Figure 81 and Figure 82 depict trends of water use within the industrial sector (mining included) for Zambia and Zimbabwe. Figure 81 presents a decreasing trend of -2.6% from 1990 to 2000 for the water use in the industrial and mining sector, where the pattern was disrupted by an increase of 1.12% from 1996 to 1997, followed by a decrease of -1.87% in 1998. The water use then exhibits an increase of 1.94% from 2000 to 2013. Except for the year 2000 with the minimum water use, there are not extreme variations from the average water use in this sector. Similar water use trends are observed for the remaining countries of the ZRB (Angola, Botswana, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Tanzania). The only exception is Zimbabwe, as seen in Figure 82, where the industrial and mining sector exhibits a minor decreasing trend of -1.87% from 1990 to 2000 and then an increasing trend of 2.78% to 2010. This is followed by a major decreasing trend of -12% to 2015. Other than the period of time between 2011 and 2015, there are not extreme variations from the average water use in this sector.

When considered in the context of economic activity within these countries, links to the consumption patterns are observed. The manufacturing sector in Zambia recorded positive growth during the 2000-2015 period (averaging 6.0%) with the highest growth rate of 10.6% percent recorded in 2011 before dropping to 6.2%, 4.0% and 4.4% in 2013, 2014 and 2015 respectively. The manufacturing sector growth was mainly attributed to the significant growth recorded in the food, tobacco and beverages sub-sector; basic metals and fabricated engineering products subsectors; chemicals, plastic, synthetic rubber other chemical products; and wood and wood products subsector (Zambian Development Agency, 2018). Zambia is also well endowed with mineral resources and the country derives most of its foreign earnings from the export of minerals. As earlier mentioned, the mining industry has played a vital role in the country’s development in the past 70 years. However, owing to decreasing world prices in copper, poor investments in new and existing mines and unsupportive management practices, copper production has declined and its contribution to the sector in terms of GDP has progressively diminished, from 19 per cent in 1992 to around 4 per cent since 1999. However, in 2001 the sector recorded a real growth of 14% compared to a growth of only 0.1% in 2000 and a decline of 24.8% in 1999, (AFDB/OECD, 2003). Zimbabwe on the other hand, is experiencing a structural regression characterised by deindustrialisation and informalisation. The share of the manufacturing sector in GDP peaked at 26.9% in 1992 before collapsing to 7.2% by 2002 and averaging 11.7% between 2009 and 2014. Between 2011 and 2014, 4,610 firms have been forced to closed down, retrenching 55,443 workers (Kanyenze et. al. 2017).

Figure 81 - Trend graph for water use by Industry (including mining) in Zambia (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

Figure 82 - Trend graph for water use by industry (including mining) in Zimbabwe (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

As earlier mentioned, a majority of the mining activity within the ZRB is concentrated around the Copperbelt Province in Zambia. In Zambia, four major mines known as the “Big Four” ([Barrick Lumwana](#), [FQM Kansanshi](#), [Mopani](#) and [KCM-Konkola Copper Mines](#)) account for approximately 80% of the country’s annual copper production; producing 200,338 metric tonnes in the first quarter of 2018 (Mining for Zambia, 2018). Based on this, it is possible to extrapolate the total production output of the Zambian copper industry in the first quarter of 2018 as 250,423 metric tonnes.

Using this estimated figure of total copper production as an approximation for total mining production in Zambia, an indication of the m³ of water used per tonne of production may be deduced. Taking into account the amount of water used in the mining and quarrying sectors for Zambia - 108,111,300 m³ (EORA Global MRIO, 2017), it is possible to arrive at an indicative figure of 432 m³ of water used per tonne of production.

As cited within Deliverable 4.1¹⁶, the most riparian countries of the ZRB have witnessed significant economic growth in recent years (ZAMCOM, 2016), with an average GDP estimated at six percent over the past 10 years (World Bank, 2017). Plans are being made by Zambia to increase production of existing industrial sites, with major industrial actors such as Zambian Breweries having recently increased production from 750,000 to 1.750 million hectolitres per annum (Lusaka Times, 2017). With the production of one hectolitre of beer by Zambian Breweries requiring as much as five times the amount of water (Zambian Breweries Plc, 2017), this increase in production could translate into as much as an additional 5 million hectolitres of water. A 2016 study conducted by ZAMCOM indicates that approximately 20% of the total ZRB runoff is used, with an estimated 0.02% and 0.12% used by industry and mining respectively (as compared to 16.46% used by the hydropower sector). It is projected that these shares of consumption will rise to 0.08% and 0.4% respectively by 2025, by which time a total 40% of the ZRB will be used (ZAMCOM, 2016). The increase in the use of water within mining and industry could lead to significant risks in terms of water quality, with point pollution around centres of industrial and mining activity as well as ground water contamination having been identified as an issue within the ZRB (ZAMCOM, 2016). This potentially holds severe consequences for other users dependent on good water quality and habitat ecosystem services provided by the Zambezi waters such as fisheries sector, agriculture sector, private households and tourism sector. That said efforts are also being made on the part of the

¹⁶ DAFNE-Deliverable 4.1. Models of the economic development in the Zambezi river basin. December-2017.

major users to develop more efficient systems, with corporations such as the aforementioned Zambia Breweries reporting improvements in their water efficiency rates of close to 20% between 2015 and 2016 (Zambian Breweries Plc, 2017; Avior Capital Market, 2018).

2.8 INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF WATER GOVERNANCE

2.8.1 Overview of applicable legal texts

Global legal instruments and applicability to ZRB

The primary framework convention governing transboundary freshwater is the 1997 UN Convention on the Non-navigational Uses of International Watercourses (UNWC).¹⁷ For full details of its scope and application, please refer to Milestones 4¹⁸ and 57¹⁹ (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2017; 2018).

The substantive principles contained in the UNWC, which are used to identify good governance of transboundary watercourses are:

1. Equitable and reasonable utilization of the resource;²⁰
2. The obligation to prevent significant harm to other watercourse states;²¹
3. The protection and preservation of ecosystems;²²
4. The prevention, reduction and control of pollution.²³

Among the key provisions that link governance of water to other issues found in the WEF nexus are:

1. The general duty to cooperate on the basis of sovereign equality, territorial integrity, mutual benefit and good faith²⁴ ;
2. The realization of equitable use and participation through considering the factors relevant to determining equitable and reasonable utilization.²⁵

The UNWC also contains a number of procedural principles for planned measures which are extremely relevant to the WEF Nexus with regard to any planned actions. Planned measures are generally understood as intended projects or programmes that, according to Article 12, “may have a significant adverse effect on other watercourse States”.²⁶ As well as the general obligation to exchange information and consult each other on the possible effects of planned measures,²⁷ it stipulates that before a project is implemented, there should be notification accompanied by available technical data and information, including the results of any environmental impact assessment, in order to enable the notified State to evaluate the possible effects of the planned measures.²⁸

Notification triggers a process of consultation, which the notified State has six months to respond to the notifying State or extend the period for another six months.²⁹ Articles 14-16 elaborate upon the obligations of States during this period, while Article 17 details the nature of consequent consultations and negotiations as occurring “with a view to arriving at an equitable resolution”. Although conducting a transboundary environmental impact assessment (EIA) is not a requirement under the UNWC, it is arguably an important step in complying with Article 7 regarding the duty to

¹⁷ UN Convention on the Non-navigational Uses of International Watercourses (UNWA) (36 ILM 700; signed 21 May 1997; in force 17 August 2014).

¹⁸ DAFNE-Milestone 4. Identification of water governance structures in the Zambezi river basin. September-2017.

¹⁹ DAFNE-Milestone 57. Identification of water governance structures in the Omo river basin. February-2018.

²⁰ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 5.

²¹ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 7.

²² (UNWC, n.d.), Article 20.

²³ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 21.

²⁴ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 8.

²⁵ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 6.

²⁶ Alistair Rieu-Clarke, Ruby Moynihan and Bjørn-Oliver Magsig, ‘UN Watercourses Convention - User’s Guide’ (CWLPS 2012).

²⁷ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 11.

²⁸ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 12.

²⁹ (UNWC, n.d.), Article 13.

take appropriate measures not to cause significant harm, as well as Article 12 on notification concerning planned measures with possible adverse effects. Further, there is a duty to compensate enshrined under Article 7 of the UNWC if significant harm does occur.

In relation to the UNWC, only Namibia of the ZRB States has signed and ratified the agreement, meaning that other States are not bound by the convention. However, a number of the ZRB States voted in favour of its adoption when voting in the UN General Assembly, it can therefore be inferred that the majority of the ZRB States were in support of its principles, objectives, and aspirations. A number of legal scholars also argue that the Convention mostly codifies customary law, in which case the key principles could be argued to be binding upon all States. Further details on the applicability of customary law can be found in Milestones 4 and 57 (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2017; 2018).

Regional legal instruments

All ZRB States are members of the Southern African Development Community (SADC), an inter-governmental organization and Regional Economic Community³⁰ established by the 1992 Treaty of the Southern African Development Community.³¹ The SADC has been a key player in developing regional law of shared water resources, most clearly evidenced by the 2000 Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses (SADC-PC),³² signed by all ZRB States, with only Angola and Zimbabwe yet to ratify the agreement.³³ The SADC-PC largely aligns with the substantive and procedural rules of the UNWC, as detailed below. At a regional level, the SADC-PC has stronger legal force than the UNWC, as it has been signed by all ZRB States, with only Angola and Zimbabwe left to ratify.

In addition to the SADC-PC, the SADC has adopted a number of policies and plans for the development of regional watercourses, a summary of these is also provided below.

Basin legal instruments

1987 Zambezi River Authority (ZRA) Agreement. This Agreement focuses on the sharing of “all the available energy from the Kariba Dam equally” and is therefore of little relevance to the governance of the basin as a whole. For further details of the agreement, please see Milestone 4 (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2017).

1987 Agreement on the Action Plan for the environmentally sound management of the Common Zambezi River System (ZACPLAN). The ZACPLAN Agreement³⁴ sets out four principal elements for the environmental management and sustainable development of the basin: environmental assessment, environmental management, environmental legislation, and supporting measures.

2004 Agreement on the Establishment of the Zambezi Watercourse Commission. All ZRB States have now signed the Agreement of the Zambezi Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM), which entered into force in 2011, and only Malawi is yet to ratify the agreement, although it is reportedly finalising its accession process.³⁵ ZAMCOM became fully established in 2014 with its offices in Harare, Zimbabwe. It is noteworthy that the ZAMCOM Agreement’s scope covers the “Zambezi Watercourse”, which describes the hydrology of the river basin as a “unitary whole” with its common terminus at the Indian Ocean (Article 1), rather than the “Zambezi River Basin”. Thus,

³⁰ Treaty Establishing a Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) (Signed November 1993; in force 8 December 1994)

³¹ SADC Agreement (n 68).; ‘Southern African Development Community: Towards a Common Future’ (sadc.int) <<http://www.sadc.int/>> accessed 4 September 2017.

³² Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses in the Southern African Development Community (signed 7 August 2000; in force 22 September 2003).

³³ ‘Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses’ (ecolex.org) <<https://www.ecolex.org/details/treaty/revised-protocol-on-shared-water-courses-tre-001360/?q=sadc+revised+protocol>> accessed 12 September 2018.

³⁴ Agreement on the action plan for the environmentally sound management of the Common Zambezi river system (ZACPLAN) (signed at Harare, 28 May 1987; in force 28 May 1987)

³⁵ ‘Publications - Zamcom’ (Zamcom) <<http://zambezicommission.org/newsite/index.php/downloads/>> accessed 1 September 2018.

the ZAMCOM Agreement governs the hydrological aspects of the river basin, but not the environmental and ecosystem management aspects that would be incorporated into the entire river basin or catchment environment.³⁶

The ZAMCOM Agreement covers the scope of substantive rules for water governance in Articles 12-15, procedural rules in Articles 16, 17 and 20, dispute settlement arrangements in Article 21-22 and institutional mechanisms in Article 6. It principally establishes a Commission for the Zambezi Watercourse,³⁷ setting out the institutional arrangements that comprises a Council of Ministers,³⁸ a Technical Committee (ZAMTEC)³⁹ and a Secretariat (ZAMSEC).⁴⁰

The main Articles in the ZAMCOM Agreement are consistent with both the SADC-PC and the UNWC, with the substantive rules of equitable and reasonable utilization, no significant harm to member States, the protection of associated ecosystems, and the duty of cooperation. Article 13 sets out the factors relevant to equitable and reasonable utilization, identical to those set out in the SADC-PC. Significantly, Article 10 of the Agreement gives ZAMTEC the responsibility to “develop and propose for consideration and approval by the Council, rules of application to facilitate equitable and reasonable use of the Zambezi Watercourse pursuant to Article 13”. This is noteworthy, since it provides a mechanism for institutionally implementing a markedly subjective and political provision that is usually dependent upon high level *ad hoc* deliberative processes. The ZAMCOM Agreement also provides for the obligation not to cause significant harm to any member State, and specifically to prevent, eliminate, mitigate or control adverse transboundary impacts in Article 14(3). Notably, this is a lower threshold to the UNWC since it does not refer to “significant” harm. Like the SADC-PC, this obligation is extended to human health and safety in Article 14(2) (although, unlike the SADC Protocol, it does not include the environment). The principle of assessment of trans-frontier impacts in Article 12(f) is key to achieving this principle in the planning and execution of projects likely to have an adverse transboundary impact.

The procedural rules in the UNWC and the SADC-PC regarding information sharing and notification and consultation for planned measures are included in detail in Articles 15 and 16 of the ZAMCOM Agreement. Both of these provisions are further supported by ZAMCOM publications adopted by the ZAMCOM Council elaborating upon these provisions, as further tools for cooperation: the 2016 Rules and Procedures on Information sharing,⁴¹ and the 2017 Procedures for Notification of Planned Measures.⁴²

The 2017 Procedures for Notification and Planned Measures reinforce the requirement in the ZAMCOM Agreement, Article 16(1) that notification must take place if an activity will “adversely affect the Zambezi Watercourse or any other Member State”. This is significant, as it provides for a lower threshold than both the SADC-PC and the UNWC, which require notification in relation to “significant adverse effects”, only upon other watercourse States, in Article 4(1)(b) and Article 12 respectively.⁴³

³⁶ A Dan Tarlock, ‘The Potential Role of International Environmental and Water Law to Prevent and Mitigate Water-Related Disasters’ in Jacquelinne Peel and David Fisher (eds), *The Role of International Environmental Law in Disaster Risk Reduction* (Brill Nijhoff 2016).

³⁷ (ZAMCOM, n.d.) Article 3.

³⁸ (ZAMCOM, n.d.), Article 7.

³⁹ (ZAMCOM, n.d.), Article 9.

⁴⁰ (ZAMCOM, n.d.), Article 11.

⁴¹ ZAMCOM, ‘Rules and Procedures for Sharing of Data and Information Related to the Management and Development of the Zambezi Water-course’ (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, adopted by the ZAMCOM Council on 25 February 2016).

⁴² ZAMCOM, ‘Procedures for Notification of Planned Measures’ (Zambezi Watercourse Commission, adopted by the ZAMCOM Council on 23 February 2017).

⁴³ Further detail available in Milestones 4 and 57 (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2017; 2018)

Table 40 - Overview of regional legal instruments in the ZRB.

Instrument	Status	Key Principles/Aims
2000 Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses (SADC-PC) ⁴⁴	Signed by all ZRB States, with only Angola and Zimbabwe yet to ratify the agreement. ⁴⁵	Sets out key substantive principles for shared water governance: i. Equitable and reasonable utilization (Article 2) ii. Factors relevant for determining equitable and reasonable utilization (Article 3(8)) these factors expand on those in the UNWC to add environmental needs of Watercourse States iii. Obligation not to cause significant harm to other watercourse states (Article 3(10)) iv. Expands on provision in the UNWC to include not only the direct interests of watercourse states, but also harm to individuals (Article 4(2)) v. Protection and preservation of ecosystems (Article 4(2)) vi. Duty to cooperate (Article 3(7)) The SADC-PC also reinforces UNWC Procedural Obligations and establishes an institutional framework for implementation.
2005 Regional Water Policy for the SADC ⁴⁶	Policy document	Developed to further the implementation of the SADC-PC and to provide the framework for sustainable, integrated and coordinated development, utilization, protection and control of national and trans-boundary water resources regionally, whilst also representing the aspirations and interests of member States.
2006 Regional Water Strategy for the SADC ⁴⁷	Policy document	Provides the framework for the implementation of the Protocol and the Policy
2010 SADC Guidelines for Strengthening River Basin Organisations ⁴⁸	Policy document	Aims to establish a set of procedures to assist governments with establishing proper institutions, such as river basin organisations, to facilitate the cooperative management of shared watercourses
2012 Regional Infrastructure Development Master Water Sector Plan ⁴⁹	Policy document	Guides the implementation of cross-border infrastructure projects
Regional Strategic Action Plan for Integrated Water Resources Development was approved in 2015 ⁵⁰	Policy document	Presents targets for the SADC to particularly address challenges relating to the water and energy crisis in the region, rainfall distribution, and regional transmission in the region. This Importantly, this Strategy highlights nexus approaches.

⁴⁴ Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses in the Southern African Development Community (signed 7 August 2000; in force 22 September 2003).

⁴⁵ Revised Protocol on Shared Watercourses (ecolex.org) <<https://www.ecolex.org/details/treaty/revised-protocol-on-shared-water-courses-tre-001360/?q=sadc+revised+protocol>> accessed 12 September 2018.

⁴⁶ Southern African Development Community Regional Water Policy (adopted August 2005).

⁴⁷ Southern African Development Community Regional Water Strategy (adopted June 2006).

⁴⁸ SADC, 'Guidelines for Strengthening River Basin Organisations' (Southern African Development Community 2010).

⁴⁹ Southern African Development Community Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan, Water Sector Plan (adopted August 2012).

⁵⁰ Southern African Development Community Regional Strategic Action Plan on Integrated Water Resources Development and Management Phase IV (2016-2020).

Under ZAMCOM, several cooperative programmes have been established, including the ZAMCOM Water Resources Information System (ZAMWIS),⁵¹ ZAMCOM Institutional Development and Basin-wide Cooperation (ZICP),⁵² and Zambezi Basin Strategic Planning (ZSP).⁵³ ZAMWIS is an important implementation of Article 15 of the ZAMCOM Agreement, in regard to the furnishing of data and information. The 2016 ZAMCOM publication on the Rules and Procedures on Information sharing is therefore an important implementation document, as it sets out the technical procedures and specifications for data and information sharing in relation to ZAMWIS.

The Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) Strategy and Implementation Plan for the ZRB (ZAMSTRAT) was adopted in 2008,⁵⁴ originally formulated under a ZACPLAN Project, and was intended as a starting point for further negotiations.⁵⁵ It presents the main challenges for the management of ZRB water resources and recommends strategies and actions to address them with detailed projects and timelines. With the overall objective to achieve “equitable sustainable utilization of water for social and environmental justice, regional integration and economic benefit for present and future generations”, a challenge includes “basin wide cooperation and integration”, with the strategic objectives of strengthening operationalisation of ZAMCOM as well as organisational, financial and human resource capacities of water management institutions at regional, national and local levels.⁵⁶ According to a 2016 ZAMCOM report, only the short term action of strengthening coordination with ongoing programmes in the basin has thus far been achieved for this objective.⁵⁷

National legal instruments

A full analysis of relevant national and policy documents relating to water, environmental and other relevant laws and policies in the eight ZRB States is contained in Milestone 4 (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2017). A summary of the main findings and key points from the national legislations are listed hereafter:

The Key Points from National Legislation can be summarised as follows:

1. All ZRB States have in place legislation which necessitates the prevention of pollution and the duty to conduct EIAs for developments which are likely to cause harm to the environment.⁵⁸
2. Most States have provisions for the protection of ecosystems within their environmental protection legislation.⁵⁹

⁵¹ 'ZAMCOM Water Resources Information Systems (ZAMWIS)' (zambezicommission.org) <<http://zambezicommission.org/newsite/index.php/zamcom-water-resources-information-systems-zamwis/>> accessed 2 September 2017.

⁵² 'ZAMCOM Institutional Development and Basin-Wide Cooperation (ZICP)' (zambezicommission.org) <<http://zambezicommission.org/newsite/index.php/zamcom-institutional-development-and-basin-wide-cooperation-zicp/>> accessed 2 September 2017.

⁵³ 'Zambezi Basin Strategic Planning (ZSP)' (zambezicommission.org) <<http://zambezicommission.org/newsite/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/ZSP.pdf>> accessed 2 September 2017.

⁵⁴ Zambezi River Authority (n 102).

⁵⁵ (Tvedt et al., 2015) p.593.

⁵⁶ (Zambezi River Authority, 2008) p.2.

⁵⁷ ZAMCOM, 'Integrated Water Resources Management Strategy and Implementation Plan for the Zambezi River Basin: At a Glance' (Zambezi Watercourse Commission 2016).

⁵⁸ **Angola:** 2002 Law No. 6/02 on Water Use; Presidential Decree No. 261/11 approving the Regulation on the quality of water; 2014 Presidential Decree No. 82/14 approving the Regulation of General Use of Water Resources; 2004 Water Sector Development Program (PDSA); **Botswana:** 1968 Water Act [Chapter 33:01], Article 36; 1962 Waterworks Act [Chapter 34:03], Article 22; 1971 Public Health Act [Chapter 63:01], Article 46; **Malawi:** 2013 Water Resources Act (No. 2 of 2013), Articles 88-103; 1996 Environment Management Act (No. 23 of 1996), Articles 42-44; 1995 Waterworks Act (No. 17 of 1995), Article 50; **Mozambique:** 1991 Act No. 16/91 regulating water resources belonging to the public domain; 2007 Decree No. 43/2007 approving the Regulation for licensing the concessions of water use; 2004 Decree No. 15/2004 approving the Regulation on municipal water supply and wastewater treatment; **Namibia:** 2013 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2013), Articles 68-84; 1997 Namibia Water Corporation Act (No. 12 of 1997), Article 11(b); **Tanzania:** 2009 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2009), Article 39-42; 2009 Water Supply and Sanitation Act (No. 12 of 2009), Article 52; **Zambia:** 2011 Water Resources Management Act (No. 21 of 2011), Articles 46-50; 2011 Environmental Management Act (No. 12 of 2011), Article 46; 1990 Environmental Protection and Pollution Control Act (No. 12 of 1990), in part repealed, Article 23(h); **Zimbabwe:** 1998 Water Act [Chapter 20:24], Article 7(3)(1) and Article 13(1)(a)(iii); 1998 Zimbabwe National Water Authority Act [Chapter 20:25], Article 5(1)(a)(ii); 2002 Environmental Management Agency Act [Chapter 20:27], Article 57.

⁵⁹ **Angola:** 1998 Environmental Law No. 5/98; 2002 Law No. 6/02 on Water Use; Presidential Decree No. 82/14 approving the Regulation of General Use of Water Resources; **Malawi:** 2013 Water Resources Act (No. 2 of 2013), Article 4; 1996 Environment Management Act (No. 23 of 1996), Articles 31-41; **Mozambique:** 1991 Act No. 16/91 regulating water resources belonging to the public domain; 2007 Decree No. 43/2007 approving the Regulation for licensing the concessions of water use; 1997 Act No. 20/97 approving the Environment Act; **Namibia:** 2013 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2013), Articles 3 and 45; 1997 Namibia Water Corporation Act (No. 12 of 1997), Article 12; 2007 Environmental Management Act (No. 7 of 2007), Article 3(2)(g); **Tanzania:**

3. Only Tanzania and Zambia have actively incorporated their international commitments and specific principles into their national legislation.⁶⁰
4. Angola, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia and Zimbabwe merely provide in their water or environmental laws that international agreements which they are party to must be implemented.⁶¹ Both Zambia and Zimbabwe have incorporated the ZRA by annexing it to national legislation.⁶² Botswana does not mention any consideration of international obligations.
5. Equitable and reasonable use and no significant harm have been integrated into the legislation of Zambia and Tanzania.⁶³ However, similar provisions have been adopted in some other states.⁶⁴
6. Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe have taken measures for adopting and implementing the principle of no significant harm.⁶⁵
7. Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe also require measures to be taken to avoid, minimise or mitigate transboundary impacts. Botswana also requires transboundary impact requirements, although the legislation does not specifically provide for the mitigation of transboundary impacts.⁶⁶ Although not conclusive, there is some policy mandate for a transboundary impact assessment in Mozambique.⁶⁷ Angola, Namibia and Malawi do not require transboundary EIAs, but do require EIAs to be conducted nationally.⁶⁸
8. All ZRB States implement the international duty to establish joint bodies through their cooperation in ZAMCOM and the national steering committees. This obligation is also implemented by Zambia and Zimbabwe through the establishment of the ZRA.
9. Namibia, Tanzania and Zambia provide for information and data exchange procedures in regard to shared water resources.⁶⁹ Botswana and Malawi do not make provision for data exchange, but they do have monitoring procedures that can in part facilitate meeting this international obligation in the future.⁷⁰ Angola and Mozambique's legislation also include provisions regarding international cooperation and exchange.⁷¹ Zimbabwe merely "promote[s] such mechanisms for the co-operative management of international water resources" in Article 5(1)(l) of its 1998 Zimbabwe National Water Authority Act.
10. No ZRB State has implemented procedures in regard to notification and consultation obligations for planned measures (although this cannot be confirmed for Angola and Mozambique).

2009 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2009), Articles 4(f), 5(c), 49(c) and 72(2)(c); 2005 Environmental Impact Assessment and Audit Regulations, (G.N. No. 349 of 2005), Article 11(1)(c); **Zambia**: 2011 Water Resources Management Act (No. 21 of 2011), Articles 57(2)(i) and 83(1)(e); 2011 Environmental Management Act (No. 12 of 2011), Articles 6(e) and 27; **Zimbabwe**: 1998 Water Act [Chapter 20:24], Article 6(1)(b); 2002 Environmental Management Agency Act [Chapter 20:27], Articles 4(2)(i), 9(1)(vii) and 36(c)(i).

⁶⁰ **Tanzania**: 2009 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2009), Articles 5(e) and 98-100; 2001 Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority Act (No. 11 of 2001), Article 7(2); **Zambia**: 2011 Water Resources Management Act (No. 21 of 2011), Articles 56-57; 2011 Environmental Management Act (No. 12 of 2011), Article 84-85; 1990 Environmental Protection and Pollution Control Act (No. 12 of 1990), in part repealed, Article 23(h);

⁶¹ **Angola**: 2002 Law No. 6/02 on Water Use; 1998 Environmental Law No. 5/98; **Mozambique**: 1991 Act No. 16/91 regulating water resources belonging to the public domain.; **Malawi**: 2013 Water Management Act (No. 2 of 2013), Article 141; 2001 Irrigation Act (No. 16 of 2001), Article 18(2)(g); **Namibia**: 2013 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2013), Article 28-29; 2007 Environmental Management Act (No. 7 of 2007), Article 48; **Zimbabwe**: 1998 Water Act [Chapter 20:24], Article 6(2)(f); 1998 Zimbabwe National Water Authority Act [Chapter 20:25], Article 5(1)(l); 2002 Environmental Management Agency Act [Chapter 20:27], Article 5(2)(b), 87 and 132.

⁶² **Zambia**: 1987 Zambezi River Authority Act [Chapter 467]; **Zimbabwe**: 1987 Zambezi River Authority Act [Chapter 20:23].

⁶³ **Tanzania**: 2009 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2009), Article 98(1); **Zambia**: 2011 Water Resources Management Act (No. 21 of 2011), Articles 2 and 57

⁶⁴ See Milestone 4, pg 51

⁶⁵ **Tanzania**: 2005 Environmental Impact Assessment and Audit Regulations (G.N. No. 349 of 2005), Article 59; **Zambia**: 2011 Water Resources Management Act (No. 21 of 2011), Article 60(1)(c); **Zimbabwe**: 2002 Environmental Management Agency Act [Chapter 20:27], Article 99(e)

⁶⁶ **Botswana**: 2011 Environmental Assessment Act (No. 10 of 2011), Article 10(2)(a)(iv) and 18(1).

⁶⁷ (Golder Associates, 2014) p.40.

⁶⁸ **Malawi**: 2013 Water Resources Act (No. 2 of 2013), Articles 44, 95 and 112; 1996 Environment Management Act (No. 23 of 1996), Articles 24-29; **Namibia**: 2007 Environmental Management Act (No. 7 of 2007), Articles 27-28.

⁶⁹ **Namibia**: 2013 Water Resources Management Act (No. 2 of 2013), Article 28(a); **Tanzania**: 2009 Water Resources Management Act (No. 11 of 2009), Article 99(a) and 100; **Zambia**: 2011 Water Resources Management Act (No. 21 of 2011), Article 56(1)(c)(ii).

⁷⁰ **Botswana**: 1956 Boreholes Act [Chapter 34:02], Articles 4-7; 2011 Environmental Impact Assessment Act (No. 10 of 2011), Article 18-19; **Malawi**: 2013 Water Resources Act (No. 2 of 2013), Articles 16-18; 1996 Environment Management Act (No. 23 of 1996), Article 25-28.

⁷¹ **Angola**: 2002 Law No. 6/02 on Water Use; 1998 Environmental Law No. 5/98; 2014 Presidential Decree No. 116/14 approving the Statute of the Ministry of Energy and Water (MINEA); **Mozambique**: 1991 Act No. 16/91 regulating water resources belonging to the public domain; 1997 Act No. 20/97 approving the Environment Act.

2.8.2 Indicators of water availability and quality in relation to governance

Legal principles as indicators

The key principles relating to governance of freshwater, as identified in Milestones 4 and 57 (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2017; 2018) are used as indicators for the assessment of the level of legal expectation which is placed upon a member state regarding a particular action. While a full breakdown of this process will be demonstrated in the forthcoming Deliverable 4.4⁷² (Models and Principles of Water Governance in the OTB and ZRB), an example of this process is demonstrated in Figure 83.

Figure 83 - Key principles as indicators of the level of legal expectation.

As stated within the diagram above, the level of legal expectation is derived from the strength of legal language and the presence of the principle within the instrument of law or policy. The two tables below provide a summary of the scores from the most relevant international, regional, and basin rules applicable to the ZRB and OTB States, which represent the basic legal framework for the basins.

These legal principles are divided into substantive and procedural obligations:

1. *Substantive obligations* are broad standards which should be met or upheld
2. *Procedural obligations* set out the specific processes and procedures which must be followed for attaining those substantive ends.

However, it should be noted that these are loose categorisations, as they both necessarily contain elements of each other. That is to say, substantive obligations are umbrella norms for managing and protecting shared water resources, which inherently requires taking due diligence measures⁷³, while procedural law is inherently process-oriented in what it sets out to achieve⁷⁴.

Therefore, Table 41 demonstrates that some legal principles score higher than others. For instances, the principles on the preservation and protection of ecosystems scores and the principle of sustainable utilisation score highest in the ZRB. This means that an action which could have an impact on the realisation of either of these two principles would likely have a high level of legal expectation or obligation regarding the process and procedures which must be followed.

WEF Nexus

Water⁷⁵. Despite huge quantities of water in the ZRB, water availability continues to be an issue, with many in the region still lacking adequate access to clean water and sanitation. In addition, a number of planned water transfer schemes put further water security at risk. There is also significant interest in developing the navigable stretches of the ZRB.

⁷² DAFNE-Deliverable 4.4. Models and principles of water governance in the Omo and Zambezi river basins.

⁷³ Owen McIntyre, 'Analysis: The Proceduralisation and Growing Maturity of International Water Law' (2010) 22 *Journal of Environmental Law*.

⁷⁴ Thomas O Main, 'The Procedural Foundation of Substantive Law' (2010) 87 *Washington University Law Review*.

⁷⁵ See Yihdego and Hawkins, Identification of Water Governance Structures in the Zambezi River Basin: A Water-Energy-Food Nexus Perspective, Milestone 4, September 2017 pg. 32-34, Yihdego and Hawkins, Identification of Water Governance Structures in the Omo-Turkana Basin: A Water-Energy-Food Nexus Perspective, Milestone 57, September 2018, pg. 5-9

Energy⁷⁶. The Zambezi river system has enormous hydropower potential, with a number of large scale projects both in operation and in planning stages.

Food⁷⁷. The ZRB has a vital role in ensuring food security in the region due to its role in sustaining agriculture and fisheries. The river system is vital in maintaining the ecosystem which ensures the seasonal fluctuations sustaining agriculture.

Table 41 - Scores of legal principles in the ZRB.

Instrument:	Principle:	Substantive obligations								Procedural obligations						
		Equitable and reasonable use	Intergenerational equity	Prevention of pollution	No significant harm to states	Protection and preservation of ecosystems	Sustainable development	Sustainable utilization	Cooperation: harmonization and agreements	Precautionary principle	Environmental / social / cultural impact assessment	Transboundary impact assessment	Joint body or COP encouraged or established	Information/ data exchange	Planned measures: notification / consultation	Dispute resolution mechanism
	UNWC	3	1	3	3	3	1	2	3	0	1	0	2	3	3	2
Global	ACCNNR	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
	Revised ACCNNR	2	3	3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	0	3	3	2	3
Regional	SADC-PC	3	1	3	3	3	2	1	3	0	1	0	3	3	3	3
Basin	ZACPLAN	0	0	3	0	3	2	0	3	0	3	0	1	3	0	0
	ZAMCOM	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3
	Score	11	8	16	9	17	10	6	17	6	11	2	13	16	11	14

Legend:

3 = Strong reference (key/ priority provision with elaboration); 2 = Medium reference (key provision but no elaboration); 1 = Weak reference (only mentioned or in part mentioned); 0 = No reference

Implications of key principles and procedures on WEF-Nexus

Greater analysis of the relationship between key principles and procedures will be provided in the forthcoming Deliverable 4.4⁷⁸ (Models and Principles of Water Governance in the OTB and ZRB, however an example of how a WEF action could relate to the associated legal principles and therefore create a legal expectation, or in some cases (dependant on the status of ratification and/or status of the document from which the principle is derived) a legal obligation, is given below with respect to the ZRB.

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ DAFNE-Deliverable 4.4. Models and principles of water governance in the Omo and Zambezi river basins.

Table 42 - Implications of key principles and procedures on WEF-Nexus in the ZRB.

WEF Related Action	Possible Impact	Applicable Principles	Legal Expectation Created
Water Transfer Scheme (such as Zimbabwe's Matabeleland Zambezi Water Project)	Water quantity, water quality, water level, energy and food and other societal implications	Substantive Principles: Equitable and Reasonable Use, No Significant Harm Procedural Principles: Obligation to notify and Consult	All factors and circumstances to equitable and reasonable use must be considered (UNWC, Articles 5-6) Notification and process of consultation triggered (UNWC, Articles 12-16)

2.9 SYNTHESIS

2.9.1 Overview of geo- and time series data

This report is intended to describe the baseline scenario that will form the basis for the reference simulation of the WEF nexus, against which simulation of development pathways will be analysed and compared. An important component of the baseline scenario is represented by the data that form both the drivers of the WEF nexus and the boundary conditions for the simulation. These data – time series, digital thematic data and statistics of demand and use – were described and analysed in the previous section and are synthesised in section 2.9.2. In this section we summarise them in Table 43, where we also provide (only for publicly available data, for which disclosure is not limited by the data owner or provider) a link to their location on the internal project data repository.

Table 43 - Geo- and time series data and link to Dropbox per chapter for the ZRB.

General description	
Shapefile containing the basin boundaries of the ZRB	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/33vd27gfnevevxb/AAArIvv6JS2TIkFTUM-DBBCRa?dl=0
DEM (USGS-SRTM-90meters)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/8zm3o44brbr3vgc/AAADAGz7Bydo6KEd43-Og7hFa?dl=0
Dominant soil units of the ZRB following the 2nd edition of WRB (IUSS WRB Working Group 2007) (based on the Harmonised Soil Map of Africa (Dewitte et al., 2013) combined with the SOTER maps of Southern Africa (Dijkshoorn, 2003) and Malawi (Dijkshoorn et al., 2016)).	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/m0x2k9e1u2mpfd5/AAAbcm9H_71swbqkwc2p_rqe1a?dl=0
Land cover (ESA CCI – 300meters resolution, 2015)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/s78wddyeyi5id0s9/AACyyp1dgodYvJrvts6E2aGUa?dl=0
Climatic zones of the ZRB (adapted from Global Yield Gap Atlas - http://www.yield-gap.org/cz-ted)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/qvo1p3c6ps6314p/AAA6nvSUE5OBJWEa1kTK-6Jna?dl=0
Water availability	
Station flow data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/lv93mzng1vthhcb/AAD9kTgX5wEU9E590ID3wBeva?dl=0

(Table 43 continued)

Station precipitation data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/mq5acmib9em568k/AABydJtZNpv267cyRgltU9-ra?dl=0
Station temperature data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/bks-bkl3pngth6ak/AAAM5tYDgk1aU1t_ggyKZlyGa?dl=0
Gridded precipitation dataset CMORPH (Xie et al., 2017) [1998-present, 30 min, 8km]	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/p6v3yxtin7w00xp/AA-BeMSUXFIVs9JbgJdMWP3n7a?dl=0
Gridded precipitation dataset CHIRPS (Funk et al., 2014) [1981-present, daily, 5km]	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/4xnr64qvqxu50qu/AADf_RSctioMNFzZyNCbpeYa?dl=0
Gridded precipitation dataset TAMSAT (Maidment et al., 2017) [1983-present, daily, 4km]	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/7x22q6ebw4s8jy2/AADAmDg1FzjV1uoEjpmDFyWva?dl=0
Station water quality data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/hpkqgbvkt8ql0wc3/AABIWzqTrdD6UAMlp0YZTF8da?dl=0
Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries	
HydroSHEDS (Pfaffstetter Level5, standard (Without lakes) subbasin boundaries)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/p3qxjhima3ldvz4/AADyIp-JOcqaiahEOa37QeDTa?dl=0
Surface area of land used for livestock production	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/x7y99sin-nhipy1p/AACH5jnnKB1g3CjtLN9SQ2UAa?dl=0
Surface area of land used for rainfed crop production	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/vemu18maksa5jta/AAB0f1QJdX8Qsu4N5WJnsSZka?dl=0
Georeferenced irrigation schemes and their characteristics (area under irrigation, water source, produced crops), as points and polygons (irrigation perimeters)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/ouy-vxw652xu0isb/AABc_l1ut4px449zPZdrRB2ja?dl=0
Crop production (in tonnes per year), livestock headcounts, and fish catch and aquaculture (in tonnes per year) per subbasin derived from D3.3	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/jtxsojxhtj3bk01/AAAulphjhs6jmKg8nH5b8_Aha?dl=0
Annual food production (from harvested crops, livestock products, fish catch and aquaculture, and total agricultural output) in terms of calories and proteins per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/ukqmspk02rvj pdu/AACuOcDZ3-Ig3aMlul-vLEL8La?dl=0
Water requirement for crop and livestock production per subbasin (in cubic hectometres per year)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/mc191r0v8ttbmvr/AABe41L7806JHho9BOv1FDqCa?dl=0
Environment	
Database of surface water extent (global level, between 1984 and 2015, 30m resolution) (Pekel et al., 2016)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/f0ivasb0wy85vqs/AADI320JBcXXUYRBK1vtEFkia?dl=0
Continuous time series of lake levels (for Lakes Turkana, Malawi, Kariba and Cahora Bassa, high temporal resolution since the 1990's) (Crétau et al., 2011; Schwatke et al., 2015)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/q45j1ynidr qv6w6/AACk4-Jd-Zcl_eU-63ViZEKaa?dl=0
Accumulated data on fish species richness and fish habitat requirements developed for deliverable D3.4	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/k707bbmo6j51g78/AABox33-e-MlhuEHGsbJcY1Xa?dl=0
Data on floating vegetation cover based on LANDSAT satellite and drone imagery for the pilot study on the Kafue river	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/3u0xxovw59wv1og/AADx9Ydzb-sppFFsvdWluOMK9a?dl=0

(Table 43 continued)

The data on land cover changes (based on global land cover time series is available from 1992 to 2015 by the ESA CCI project (Li et al., 2017)) presented in deliverable D 3.4	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/q4waqz8q5dznezb/AADf6WGdUo7RHRJVsfXDnTfwa?dl=0
Demography	
ZRB Night Light map	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/7xnenhqbkp4dns/AACEZKwuwoeiBTyJGnqasDUua?dl=0
Daily calorie and protein requirements per country (between 2000 and 2013)	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Daily calorie and protein requirements per capita per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/gvg96cwwbyg9gld/AABOw7qu6KgGtXW-FXRBHhL_a?dl=0
Global Food Security Index per country (for 2017)	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Global Hunger Index Scores per country (for 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005 and 2015)	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Percentage of population with access to electricity	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Percentage of population with at least basic sanitation	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Total household water use per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Total household energy use per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Urban centres	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of tonnes proteins per year per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/gvg96cwwbyg9gld/AABOw7qu6KgGtXW-FXRBHhL_a?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/gvg96cwwbyg9gld/AABOw7qu6KgGtXW-FXRBHhL_a?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of g proteins per capita per day per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/gvg96cwwbyg9gld/AABOw7qu6KgGtXW-FXRBHhL_a?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of kcal per capita per day per subbasin	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/gvg96cwwbyg9gld/AABOw7qu6KgGtXW-FXRBHhL_a?dl=0
Economy, Industry, Mining	
Water use by Mining and quarrying per country	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0

(Table 43 continued)

Water use by total industry per country	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Institutional Framework of Water Governance	
Relevant legal material	https://www.drop-box.com/sh/vggtu31rzz2bgnw/AABnOVdBT2SWpl3O3xW-SC1lea?dl=0

2.9.2 Narrative synthesis

The ZRB is characterized by a relatively dense network of perennial rivers, the streamflow regime of which is strongly influenced by the latitude at which the river basin is located. Whereas the source areas of the Zambezi river are located in the humid tropical climate zones and hence provide water on a continuous basis, the pronounced seasonality of rainfall at more southern latitudes results in higher variability of the seasonal discharge regimes (see §2.2). The quantification of water availability as computed from streamflow regimes reflects such climatic variability and shows different potential across the year and in space, as well as variable influence of the already existing infrastructures. Information on groundwater resources in the ZRB is relatively scarce so that water availability from groundwater bodies could not be properly quantified, not even at coarse temporal and spatial scales (see §2.2.4). The basin is home to a large number of wetlands, which provide a broad range of ecosystem services (see §2.2.3). The perennial character of the rivers and local topography conditions favoured the development of large and medium hydropower schemes, which, together with irrigated agriculture, alter the natural regime of many streams.

The installed hydropower capacity in the ZRB is considerable, but, together with other modes of electricity production, is not yet capable of meeting the demands for electricity. During the 2000-2013 period a positive trend of hydropower production contributed to reduce the deficit, but the latter, aggregated for seven out of eight riparian states (excluding Botswana) still amounts to 4045 GWh y⁻¹. For Zambia alone the deficit amounts to 2501 GWh y⁻¹, being the deficit of the five major hydropower plants within Zambia combined equal to 2356 GWh y⁻¹. Because the operation of water reservoirs associated to the hydropower plants remarkably alters the natural discharge regime in ZRB's river system, one can expect that development pathways, which aim to fill the gap between demand and production, can induce higher deviations from the natural river regime on several of the main ZRB streams, thus increasing the negative implications of the water-energy nexus.

The climate of some of the ZRB regions, which is unfavourable to rainfed agriculture, determines in those regions a high irrigation demand. The major schemes for irrigated agriculture are located in Malawi, central Zambia and north Zimbabwe while they are almost absent in the other parts of the ZRB. The annual water consumption, on top of direct consumption of rainfall, by all the inventoried schemes, summing to 178,910 hectares is estimated at 1652 hm³. Rainfed agriculture is ubiquitous, but concentration zones coincide with areas where irrigated agriculture is also characterised by high density. Direct water consumption by animals kept in livestock production systems spread out over the full ZRB-territory is estimated at 168 hm³. No data could be found about aquaculture, its productivity and related water demand and use. Fish catch is associated mainly with the major natural and artificial lakes (Kariba, Cahora Bassa and Malawi). The available data suggest that there is no generalised food deficit. The significant differences among the regions depend essentially on the lack, relative to population density, of agricultural developments in some areas. This is not due to water scarcity, but rather to the dominance of natural landscapes and the remoteness of the region with respect to the major centres of development in the riparian countries. In the regions characterised by a surplus of production the available data do not allow to establish whether the considerable extent of irrigated regions induce also conditions of water stress. A more precise quantification of such condition will be possible only by simulations with the WEF integrated model.

In the upstream reaches of the ZRB, a number of major water supplying ecosystems are present while major water-dependent ecosystems (seasonal flooding) are located in the middle and lower reaches. The need of preserving and even extending these ecosystems and their provisioning (agriculture, fisheries) and cultural (tourism) services interferes with the hydropower and agriculture sectors, as pointed out by some of the analysis regarding the streamflow alteration due to hydropower induced flow regulation. The quantification of their contribution to the social and economic welfare, while not quantified by this report due to the limited data availability, will be possible only by modelling the WEF nexus and accounting for the socio-economic boundary conditions.

About 7.4 million of the roughly 40 million people in the ZRB live in cities with more than 100.000 inhabitants. The remaining 32.6 million people live in smaller settlements and rural communities spread out over the basin, with the highest densities in the subbasins around lake Malawi, in central Zambia and in the copper belt region of north-central Zambia. The total annual consumption of water by private households is estimated at 200 hm³, while the energy use is estimated at 316 PJ. In 2016, only 36% of the population had access to electricity, indicating that electricity from other sources than hydropower is important in the ZRB. About half of the 67 subbasins (corresponding to the Pfaffstetter level 5) of the ZRB do not produce enough food calories from crops, livestock or fish products to feed the local population. A subset of the subbasins, which show deficit for calories (hence not all) also exhibit insufficient protein production. This points to regional imbalances, which, to some extent, are countered by intra-basin trade of food products, however suggesting also that agricultural intensification through e.g. irrigation is an option in regions where water is sufficient to reach the production that can lead towards food security.

Based on the available data, the use of water for industrial purposes appears to be confined to few major industry sectors, namely brewing, cement producing and sugar refining plants. These are mainly located in central Zambia. Another important stakeholder accessing water for industrial use is the mining sector. Copper mines are concentrated in Zambia's north central region known as "Copperbelt". Coal mining is present in the Tete province of Mozambique, close to the Zambezi delta. Despite the modest industrialisation level of the country, in Zambia as a whole (i.e. within and outside the ZRB), the recent increasing employment trend in the industrial sector indicates that the magnitude of industry and mining is growing, despite the water use remained more or less constant in the 2006-2014 period at 2400 hm³y⁻¹. This is 12 times higher than the annual water consumption by private households and 50% higher than the water used in irrigated agriculture. While the available data do not allow to be conclusive on the reasons behind this inconsistency, possible explanations are the increase of services and, for the mining sector, an improved efficiency in the use of water as well as a reduction of the extraction and refinement activities due to price and demand stagnation, which may be compensated by employment growth in other and less water demanding sectors.

The transboundary nature of the ZRB has triggered various legal initiatives, some of which consolidated, at global, regional, ZRB-, national and sub-national level to ensure that water resources are managed and used in sustainable ways by and for all stakeholders in all riparian states. The analysis of the legal instruments at national, international and basin scale allowed to identify the framework within which water resources are presently shared and managed. However, the translation of the regulatory and legal framework established at various scales into quantitative constraints and/or objectives to be used in simulating the WEF nexus does not seem straightforward. On the one hand, the absence of regulatory limits (e.g. water rights, environmental flows, etc.) represents an element of uncertainty in understanding the WEF nexus, it allows, on the other hand, the exploration of various legal instruments and combination thereof to achieve a sustainable water resources management strategy.

It is finally worth to point at some underlying elements that emerged from the collection, analysis and interpretation of the data forming the baseline scenario and that did not allow a proper quantification of the reference management strategy, which follows from the combination of drivers (e.g. climate forcing, water demand, etc.) and basin configuration (e.g. existing infrastructure and their operation). This is due mainly to a substantial lack of data, in turn due to their non-existence (e.g.

missing instrumentation and/or observations), their unavailability (data could not be obtained from the relevant agencies) or their poor quality (e.g. coarse temporal and spatial scales as compared to the characteristic scales of the process, missing observations, etc.). However, from the analysis of the data and, especially, from the interaction with stakeholders occurred in the context of the Negotiation Simulation Lab (NSL), it seems evident that the known nexus among water, electricity production and agriculture cannot be quantified on the basis of the existing and available data. This would require the analysis of joint observations of water availability and water use and demand by each sector at appropriate temporal and spatial scales, which can highlight the effects of space-time variability, thus allowing the identification, on the one hand, of the positive and negative interactions, as well as, on the other hand, of the *widespread disconnection of management strategies* that lead to unsustainable water management practices. This suggests that an exploration of the WEF from data in the ZRB is a difficult if not impossible task, which can be overcome only by a *connected representation* of the river basin functioning in the form of a WEF integrated model, as proposed by the DAFNE project and reported in the forthcoming deliverable D3.5.

3. OMO-TURKANA BASIN

3.1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The OTB is located in the eastern part of Africa between the equator and approximately 8°N (Figure 84). The basin outlets into the endorheic Lake Turkana. It is shared among four countries – Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda and South Sudan – although 95% of the drainage area is located in Ethiopia and Kenya, covering the basin fraction in South Sudan and Uganda only about 5% of the total area of the basin. Because of predominantly dry climate of the latter region and of the limited anthropic presence and infrastructure development, the focus of the DAFNE case study is on the OTB basin area shared between Ethiopia and Kenya.

The Omo river originates in the northern highlands at an elevation of 2,200 m.a.s.l. Its most important tributary is the Gibe River, smaller tributaries are the Wabi, Denchya, Gojeb, Mui and Usno rivers. After a journey of 760 km through deep gorges and lowlands the river – named just Omo in its lower course – flows into Lake Turkana at an elevation of 360 m.a.s.l. Due to the difference in elevations and the topography the hydropower potential is very high (Figure 84 and Figure 85). The climate (Figure 86) of the Omo subbasin varies with the altitude: tropical humid in the north and hot arid in the south. Both the temperature and the precipitation follow a seasonal pattern associated with the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (Degefu and Bewket, 2017). The rainfall regime is highly variable with mean annual rainfall up to 2000 mm in the highlands and around 400 mm in the south. The interannual rainfall variability is also quite pronounced, this being a factor that can enhance impacts due to water management. The Omo subbasin contributes 14% of Ethiopia's total annual runoff (Woodroffe, 1996). About 90% of the lake's freshwater inflow and nutrients are also provided by the Omo river. It is estimated that the average flow at the Lake Turkana is around 650 m³/s. Thus, the average annual outflow⁷⁹ from the basin into Lake Turkana is around 20·10⁹ m³. The main tributaries flowing northward in Kenya and draining into Lake Turkana are the Turkwel River and the Kerio River. These tributaries account for about only 10% of the inflow into Lake Turkana, thus suggesting that the Omo river is key for understanding Lake Turkana's hydrology (Avery, 2012). Because of its large significant hydropower and irrigation potential, the Omo subbasin has been a target for large infrastructural developments. This can have significant impacts on the dynamics of both the lower Omo river in Ethiopia and the Lake Turkana.

In contrast to the soils of the plateaus of the Zambezi Rivers Basin, the tectonic uplifting and the rift formation in and along the OTB, has led to a rejuvenation of the soils of both the Ethiopian and the Kenyan Highlands (Figure 87). In Ethiopia, the highest parts are dominated by volcanic ejecta in

⁷⁹ Agriconsulting S.p.A. & Mid Day International Consulting Engineers, "Gibe III: Environmental and Social Impact Assessment. Additional Study on Downstream Impact." EEPSCO. 2009.

which *Andosols* are formed; in Kenya, on the highest parts of Mount Elgon, *Histosols* and *Andosols* occur. *Nitisols* are typically formed from basaltic or volcanic rocks at mid-range altitudes, while *Alisols* tend to dominate on acidic parent materials. At lower altitudes, where climate is warmer and where there is a pronounced dry season *Vertisols* developed from basic rocks, such as basalts and similar rocks. At even lower altitudes, in areas which have been subjected to soil erosion, weakly developed soils occur (*Cambisols* and *Regosols*). In the driest parts, soils occur where soluble minerals have accumulated (*Calcisols*, *Solonetz*, and *Solonchaks*). These different soil units not only have their specific hydraulic properties, which has an implication for soil water availability throughout the basin, but also influence the type of land cover on top of the soils. Concerning the natural vegetation, as shown in Figure 88, forests and woodland are predominantly found in the southern parts of the Ethiopian Highlands and along the middle parts of the Omo valley. Montane rainforest also occurs on the escarpment and highest parts of the Kenya Highlands. In the dry, hills and plains around Lake Turkana grasslands and shrublands prevail. The largest extent of cropland is found in the highest parts of the Ethiopian Highlands particularly around the cities of Jimma, Hossa'ina and Soddo.

Despite the fact that Ethiopia is one of the countries with the highest hydropower potential in Africa with 45,000 MW, only about 5% has been exploited⁸⁰. In the context of modern development of the country, the Government of Ethiopia is developing the Gibe Hydroelectric Cascade scheme (4,600 MW installed capacity) and the Kuraz Sugar Development Project of about 175,000 hectares⁸¹ in the Omo subbasin with the aim of satisfying energy and water demands and enhancing the national economy. A decrease in the flow of the river, a change in the natural flow pattern and silt trapping, due to the above mentioned projects, has the potential to considerably affect the biodiversity of the Lower Omo Valley and also the natural dynamics of Lake Turkana, in Kenya, since about 80 to 90% of its inflow depends on the Omo river.

The Gibe Hydroelectric Cascade scheme, particularly the Gibe III dam, which is operational since late 2015, is controversial because of the potential environmental and societal problems downstream in the Lower Omo Valley and Lake Turkana that could be caused by the disruption of the natural regime of the Omo River. In addition, the water withdrawal for the large-scale irrigation schemes in the Lower Omo Valley might cause a permanent drastic drop in the Lake Turkana water level, accelerating the delta retreat and exacerbating the ethnic conflicts over natural resources. To develop these projects, resettlements and land conversion are taking place, and territories from the Omo and Mago National Parks are being excised, thus endangering the rich wildlife and decreasing the potential to foster tourism in this region. About 400,000 indigenous people of Lower Omo Valley and Lake Turkana base their poor rural economy on flood-recession agriculture, cattle and fishery, practices tied to the natural flow regime.

3.2 WATER AVAILABILITY

The water availability in the OTB is dictated by the strong climatic variability characterising the catchment. The climate is cool to sub humid in the Ethiopian highlands, which occupy the northern part of the basin, while it is very hot and arid in the Lake Turkana region and the Kenyan part of the basin. The same pattern reflects in the water resource distribution in the basin. The Ethiopian highlands represent the main source of water for Lake Turkana, through the Omo river perennial flow, while the Kenyan region is very arid and water reaches the lake only by intermittent rivers.

The present section reports about water as a natural resource, on the basis of data compiled and analysed from three main sources: (a) ground observations available from previous studies, (b) remote sensing and/or re-analysis data set, which were collected by the DAFNE from publicly available sources, and (c) data derived from literature reports. Due to the delayed inclusion of an Ethio-

⁸⁰ Ethiopian Electric Power Company. "Gibe III: Hydroelectric Project. Environmental and Social Issues related to Gibe III Hydroelectric Project". 2010.

⁸¹ Ethiopian Sugar Development Corporation: "Kuraz Sugar Development Project" 2015. <http://www.etsugar.gov.et>

pian partner, the acquisition of hydrometeorological data from the relevant agencies is still ongoing. For this reason, the hydrometeorological data available for the assessment of water availability in the OTB is largely incomplete, especially in respect of historical data available from local, regional and national agencies. For the baseline scenario represented in the following sections the current climate and water resources will be therefore largely based on global datasets and a limited number of ground stations. As in the case of the ZRB, the space and time (S-T) resolution of global datasets, however, is coarser than that which would be ideal for calibrating and validating the model at resolutions that would allow to investigate some of the critical nexus interactions (e.g. intradaily deficit irrigation policies to minimize the agricultural water consumption, or flooding in small catchments).

Figure 84 - Topography of the OTB based on the DEM derived from SRTM data.

Figure 85 - Slope map of the OTB at 400 m resolution (based on SRTM 90 m resolution data - <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>).

Figure 86 - Climatic zones of the OTB (each colour in the map symbolises one of 39 climate zones in the ZRB defined in terms of growing degree days, temperature seasonality and an annual aridity index) (adapted from Global Yield Gap Atlas - <http://www.yieldgap.org/cz-ted>).

The data acquired and collected so far are stored on the internal project data repository and organised as described in section 2.2 for the ZRB. The available data were first investigated to analyse their consistency, quality and suitability for further use in the project. Moreover, some elaborations were carried out both on historical data and time series simulated by a preliminary setup of the hydrological model, in order to explore key statistical indicators (e.g. seasonal hydrographs, mean annual streamflow, probability distribution curves, and flow duration curves), which could provide proxy information about the nexus between water availability and its use in the different sectors. Accordingly, the following subsections illustrate some of the analyses that were carried out on the available data to characterise water availability and space-time variability. A level of detail providing a more complete and meaningful description of the water availability than that reported here will come from the final model simulations that will be presented in the deliverable D3.6⁸², where the WEF integrated model will be extensively described and its outputs will define the list of the hydrological output variables (indicators) that will be used to compare the baseline scenario and the alternative zero with the pathways and scenarios defined for the OTB.

⁸² DAFNE-Deliverable 3.6. Water quality response in the Omo River to reservoir management scenarios.

Figure 87 - Dominant soil units of the OTB following the 2nd edition of WRB (IUSS WRB Working Group 2006) (based on the Harmonised Soil Map of Africa (Dewitte et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2015)).

Figure 88 - Land cover of the OTB (adapted from ESA, 2018).

3.2.1 Climate

Ethiopia is divided into five climatic zones, shown in Figure 89, characterized by strong differences in the mean annual rainfall (Figure 90) and average temperatures. The high climatic variability of Ethiopia is mainly determined by its topographic heterogeneity. All these 5 climatic zones are present in the OTB, but the predominant ones are:

1. The “Weynadega” or “temperate zone”, characterising parts of Ethiopia’s central plateau between 1500 and 2400 m of altitude, where the climate is cool and sub humid with a mean annual rainfall between 800 and 1200 mm;

2. The “Kola” or “hot zone”, typical of areas between 500 and 1500 m of altitude with mean annual rainfall between 200 and 800 mm, characterises the Lower Omo valley;
3. The “Berha” region is the hot and arid region with elevation below 500 m and a mean annual precipitation below 200 mm, characterises the areas surrounding Lake Turkana.

Climatic variability in the Omo-Turkana region is therefore very strong, ranging from a tropical sub-humid climate in the northern part of the Ethiopian highland, to a desert climate towards Lake Turkana (Avery, 2012; Berhanu et al., 2014).

The Lake Turkana area lies within the “very arid” agro-climatic zone of Kenya, where precipitation is very low and evaporation rates very high. The average annual rainfall of the area ranges between 150 and 350 mm and the mean annual temperature between 24 to 30°C. Overall, this, without any irrigation, results in a very low potential for plant growth (Avery, 2012).

Lake Turkana is characterised by strong prevailing SE winds; the mean daily wind speed at Lodwar is 2.35 m/s. Winds are stronger in the morning and slower in the afternoon. This, together with the high temperatures, leads to high lake evaporation rates.

Figure 89 - Traditional climatic zones of Ethiopia (Berhanu et al., 2014).

Figure 90 - Mean annual rainfall distribution in Ethiopia (Berhanu et al., 2014).

Rainfall data

Data from 14 rain gauges in the Omo river basin and surrounding areas where available from previous studies which acquired them from the National Meteorological Agency (NMA) of Ethiopia. The data cover the period 1998-2008. It has not been possible so far, to obtain more recent data as the website of the NMA has not been accessible in the 6 months before the writing of this report. We are pursuing this in collaboration with project partner WLRC.

An additional station in the Omo region at Jimma is available from the GHCN dataset. The time series at this station have many missing data, therefore, some years had to be excluded from the analysis.

From the GHCN dataset one station is available also in the Kenyan region of the Turkana basin, at Lodwar. However, also in this case, the precipitation time series for this station have many missing data, therefore only limited analysis was possible for this station. See Figure 91 for the location of the stations. Figure 92 shows the rainfall distribution in Kenya and the measurement stations of the Kenyan Meteorological Department⁸³. There are only a few stations within the OTB and, at the moment of the writing of this report, data from these stations were not available.

The available rainfall data in the Omo basin have been analysed to observe average yearly precipitations, see Figure 93, and the annual rainfall fluctuations over time, see Figure 94 and Figure 95.

All the considered stations have an average annual precipitation above 1100 mm, suggesting that they all belong to the “Weynadega” or “temperate zone”. This is a realistic assumption, given that all the stations are located in the northern and central part of the Omo basin.

Looking at Figure 94, no significant change in the mean annual rainfall can be observed in the period 1998-2008. This is coherent with the finding of Cheung et al. (2008), whose analysis of long-term rainfall data in Ethiopia (1960 to 2008) showed no significant change or trend both at the national and watershed level.

However, it must be observed that the data from 2009 to today, not available at the moment of this report, may be the most significant in terms of variation in rainfall trends due to climate change.

For the Lodwar station the yearly precipitation has been computed for the 4 years with the maximum number of available data (Figure 96). The missing data for these 4 years are, however, still a considerable number, as they range from 83 to 94 days for each year. Therefore, the annual rainfall reported in the figure might be affected by a significant error. The station in Lodwar indicates a considerably drier climate, compared to the Omo region, with an average yearly precipitation of 258.6 mm (computed from the 4 available years). This value is typical of the “Berha” region, which indeed characterized the areas surrounding Lake Turkana.

Avery (2012) showed, by using the data from the Kenyan Meteorological Department, that at this location the annual rainfall had an increasing trend during the period 1921 to 2011.

⁸³ ILRI (2018)

Figure 91 - Rainfall stations of the NMA (in red) and GHCN (in green) datasets.

Figure 92 - Rainfall stations of the Kenyan Meteorological Department and annual rainfall distribution in Kenya, from ILRI database (ILRI, 2018).

Figure 93 - Average annual rainfall at the Omo basin stations (X-axis). The blue line is the NMA dataset, the red star is the GHCN station at Jimma.

Figure 94 - Annual rainfall data from 1998 to 2008 in 14 stations in the Omo river basin and surrounding area.

Figure 95 - Annual rainfall at Jimma from 1956 to 1988.

Figure 96 - Annual rainfall at Lodwar from 1988 to 1995.

Rainfall distribution throughout the year defines the three seasons of Ethiopia’s climate:

1. The “Keremt Season” is the main rainy season, from June to September and covers the entire Ethiopia except for the southern and south-eastern parts;
2. The “Belg season” is the light rain season, from March to May, and is the main source of rain for the south and south-eastern parts of the country;
3. The “Bega” season is the dry season, spanning from October to February.

Avery (2012) observed that, at the level of the Omo-Gibe river basin, the yearly trends of monthly rainfall patterns are unimodal in the north and become increasingly bi-modal towards the equator. This has also emerged from the data available in the present study, as shown in Figure 97.

The precipitation peaks in July in the upper part of the basin, between April and September in the central part of the basin, while precipitation in the lower basin shows a first peak between April and May and a second one in October.

The monthly precipitation at Jimma shows a unimodal trend with a smooth peak, coherent with the mid-basin yearly patterns. Given the availability of data over a longer time span, it was possible for this station to look at changes of the yearly rainfall distribution over time. The available information is not enough to draw any definitive conclusion, however, Figure 98 shows an emergent tendency of the rainfall monthly distribution to become wider and smoother over the years.

Figure 97 - Yearly patterns of monthly rainfall for the upper, central and lower Omo basin, using NMA stations.

Figure 98 - Monthly precipitation at Jimma, average over 3 time periods.

Temperature data

Temperature data were available at the Jimma and Lodwar stations. The average annual minimum (T_{min}), maximum (T_{max}) and average (T_{avg}) temperatures have been computed and plotted for the available years, see Figure 99. The average T_{min} and T_{max} at Jimma for the period 1955-1988 are, respectively, 11.0 °C and 26.8 °C. The mean T_{avg} at Lodwar for the period 1957-2014 is 30.0 °C.

No clear trend can be observed in the temperature for the available time span. However, Avery (2012) has reported an increase in temperature of 2 to 3°C at Lodwar station, for which he had a more complete time series. In the same study, a long-term trend of increasing temperature in Lake Turkana waters is also reported.

Figure 99 - Average yearly minimum, maximum and mean temperatures at Jimma and Lodwar stations.

The yearly patterns of monthly temperatures during the year has been computed for the minimum and maximum temperature at Jimma and for the average temperature at Lodwar (see Figure 100 and Figure 101). The minimum temperature at Jimma shows a peak during the main rainy season, probably due to the increased cloud cover in that period, and a minimum during the dry season. The maximum temperature shows an opposite trend, with a minimum during the wet season and maximum during the dry season. The patterns at Jimma seem to suggest an increase in the minimum temperature in the past 60 years and a decrease in the maximum temperature. It will be necessary to account for this during the model fitting procedures for the climate generator, however the change appears to be a step change in the late 1950s and may be due to a reporting bias/error rather than a valid climate trend.

The average temperature at Lodwar shows a trend similar to the maximum temperature at Jimma, with a minimum during the wet season. Data from 2006-2008 show a different behaviour that might be due to the higher number of missing data for these years.

Figure 100 - Yearly pattern of minimum and maximum temperature at Jimma.

Figure 101 - Yearly pattern of average temperature at Lodwar.

3.2.2 Hydrography and river flow regime

There are three main rivers contributing to the Lake Turkana water balance: the Omo River, draining from the Ethiopian side of the basin, and the Turkwel and Kerio rivers, in the Kenyan part of the basin. Only the Omo River has a perennial flow and contributes to more than 90% of the freshwater input of Lake Turkana (Tebbs et al., 2015; Kälin, 2018). The Turkwel and Kerio rivers are intermittent rivers and, together with a number of other small tributaries, contribute only seasonally to the inflow of Lake Turkana (Yuretich, 1979; Frostick and Reid, 1986).

Lake Turkana is the world's largest desert lake and the largest water body of the basin, with a volume of approximately 200 km³. The other two big water bodies of the OTB are the reservoirs of Gibe I and Gibe III, with a total capacity of 0.917 km³ and 14.7 km³ respectively.

Streamflow data were available for the stations of Abelti, Shebe and Wolkite, belonging to the Ethiopian Ministry of Water, Irrigation and Electricity network of stations (see Figure 102 for location). The available data and mean annual flow for the 3 stations are summarized in Table 44. Additional data are available for other 11 minor stations, but these data are not analysed in the present report and will not be useful for further analysis because of poor data quality.

The Moving Average over Shifting Horizon (MASH) method has been applied to analyze the runoff data. The code computes the average runoff over user-defined moving windows of days and years, in order to smooth out interannual variability and highlight trends in the time series (see Anghileri et al., 2014, for more details). In the present analysis a window of 30 days and a window of 3 years have been used for averaging the daily discharge. Results are reported in Figure 103.

Figures 104 and 105 compare the flow distribution of the Abelti, Shebe and Wolkite gauges. As expected both the flow volume and range of flows are highest for the Abelti gauge, which has the greatest upstream catchment area. Of note is the "flashy" nature of the flows at the Wolkite gauge, evidenced by the wide range of high percentile flows shown in Figure 104.

In the upper basin, where precipitation peaks in July, we observe a runoff peak in August (Abelti and Wolkite stations, Figure 103). Shebe discharge measurements instead, show the signal of the transition between uni- and bi-modal precipitation that characterises the central part of the basin (Figure 103).

Figure 102 - Location of runoff gauges in the Omo basin

Table 44 - Period of measurements and mean annual flow at the 3 flow stations.

Station	Period	Mean annual flow
Abelti	1998-2006	190 m ³ /s
Shebe	1998-2005	64 m ³ /s
Wolkite	1998-2006	27 m ³ /s

At Abelti and Shebe stations, a decrease in the daily discharge can be observed from year 1998 to 2004. After this year, the discharge follows an increasing trend. No similar trend is instead visible in Wolkite data.

Data for the lower part of the basin are very scarce in general and they were not available at the moment of writing this report. Only one station has been operational for 4 years at Omorate, just upstream of the Omo delta. In absence of adequate data, other studies have simulated the discharge at Omorate obtaining annual averages between 500 and 800 m³/s (e.g. Woodroffe, 1996; Avery, 2012).

It is also known that the Omo River periodically floods and inundates the plains of the Lower Omo valley. This phenomenon is expected to be affected by the operation of the Gibe III reservoir, the management policy of which may alter significantly the seasonality of the flows in the lower Omo valley. However, quantitative data about floodplain inundation are not available. The only semi-quantitative information that could be retrieved to understand the inundation behaviour was derived for Lake Turkana by processing remote sensing retrievals. Figure 106 shows an example of the seasonal variation of inundation extent for the years 2013-2018.

Figure 103 - Yearly pattern of average daily discharge at Wolkite, Abelti and Shebe.

Figure 104 – Box plots comparing the distributions of daily average flow rates of runoff gauges in the Omo basin. As expected the range of flows at the Abelti station is much greater due to the larger upstream catchment area. The Wolkite station has the smallest inter-quartile range but quite large variation among the peak flows observed in the upper percentiles of the distribution.

Figure 105 – Empirical flow distribution curves of average daily discharge volume at Wolkite, Abelti and Shebe.

Figure 106 – Map of the variations in Lake Turkana's extent derived from remote sensing analysis during the period 2013-2018. Details of the processing algorithm are presented in the deliverable 3.4 report.

3.2.3 Lakes and wetlands

Lake Turkana is an endorheic lake with semi-saline waters. The lake measures over 250 km from north to south and has a width of about 30 km. It has a mean depth of 30 m, but its maximum depth is about 110 m. The total volume of water is estimated to be over 200 km³, however, the lake levels, and therefore its volume, are subject to natural strong seasonal and inter-annual fluctuations. The latter can be observed in satellite-derived lake levels, computed for the period 1992 to today, and available from the Theia Land Data centre (<http://hydroweb.theia-land.fr/>, see Figure 107). Seasonal fluctuations are driven by the peak flow of the Omo river with the lake level peaking in November, following the peak flow of the Omo river in August. The lake levels shown in Figure 107 show the combined effects of inter-annual variations in seasonal flows, and the impact of infrastructure interventions (Gibe I and Gibe III). Notably the effect of the reservoirs filling results in smaller deviations than those from the natural variability – the question will be how reservoir operating policy affects the seasonal behaviour of the natural flow regime.

Following the influx of nutrients carried by the river Omo, a peak in Chlorophyll-a concentration is observed in the lake between August and September (Tebbs et al., 2015).

Figure 107 - Level of Lake Turkana for the last 25 years.

3.2.4 Groundwater

The information provided in this and the following paragraphs have been mostly taken from the Hydrogeology Atlas of Africa by Kebede et al. (2018), where information is given for individual African countries.

Ethiopia. The estimates of total groundwater storage of Ethiopia vary from 1'000 to 10'000 billion m³, of which 36'000 million m³ are estimated to be renewable resources. The most important aquifers in Ethiopia consist of unconsolidated Quaternary sediments, Tertiary-Quaternary volcanic rock and Mesozoic consolidated sedimentary rocks. Locally, basement aquifers are also important.

Figure 108 presents the hydrogeology map of Ethiopia, where we can observe that the Omo river basin is mostly dominated by unconsolidated aquifers with a low to moderate productivity, igneous volcanic aquifers with moderate to high productivity and sedimentary aquifers with fracture and intergranular flow of moderate productivity. Some localized basement aquifers of low productivity are also found in the central part of the basin.

Among the most important unconsolidated aquifers found in the Omo basin are the “wadi bed” aquifers of the Lower Omo valley. Those aquifers, although localized, have a significant groundwater

potential in water scarce arid and desert settings. Those aquifers can suffer from water quality issues as their water has variable salinity. The most productive wadi bed aquifers are those dominated by sandy and gravelly sediments with a low proportion of clay (Kebede et al., 2018). No quantitative estimates are unfortunately available to determine the volume of potentially available resource from renewable aquifers, which may represent a valuable complement to surface water resources.

Igneous volcanic aquifers generally have a good water quality of bicarbonate type, low salinity and low fluoride. Recharge takes place through direct rainfall, indirect recharge and fractures in highland areas. Sedimentary aquifers with fracture and intergranular flow offer a good to very good water quality, although some issues related to excessive concentration of dissolved salts can occur. Kebede et al. (2018) cite recharge rates in highland areas with high rainfall reaching 200 mm/yr, while in arid regions they suggest it varies between 10 and 50 mm/yr.

Kenya. The total potential groundwater resource of Kenya is estimated to be 619 million m³, with a total annually recharged rate of 193 million m³/year. By looking at the Kenyan hydrogeological map in Figure 108, the predominant aquifers of the Turkana basin can be identified as unconsolidated and semi-consolidated aquifers with intergranular flow of moderate to high productivity, volcanic aquifers of moderate productivity and low to moderately productive basement aquifers.

The unconsolidated and semi-consolidated aquifer of the Lodwar region consists of alluvial sand and sediments, up to 80 m deep. It has high groundwater potential where dominated by coarse grained sediments (sand and gravel), but limited elsewhere. Recharge occurs by direct rainfall and leakage from the river Turkwel.

The volcanic aquifers of Kenya typically have a thickness from a few meters to several hundreds of meters. Groundwater flow and storage occur in fractures and weathered zones, along the sub-horizontal boundaries between successive lava flows. Groundwater typically has low total dissolved solids and high bicarbonate. The volcanic deposits of the East African Rift System are rich in fluoride which leads to high groundwater fluoride concentrations.

Groundwater use

In Ethiopia, groundwater provides more than 90% of the water used for domestic and industrial supply, while only a very small portion is used for irrigation, for which surface water is mostly used (Kebede et al., 2018). The most important groundwater sources in Ethiopia consist of boreholes, hand dug wells, improved cold springs, river bed excavations/pits, haffirs⁸⁴, traditional Ella wells (very large diameter wells) and bircados⁸⁵ (Kebede, 2013).

Kenya also relies strongly on groundwater, which is extracted from private or communal boreholes, or supplied from groundwater wellfields. It is used for domestic use by the rural population and, locally, also for mining. A small proportion of groundwater is also dedicated to irrigation scopes. However, many problems like poor water quality, overexploitation and saline intrusion, affect the groundwater resource of Kenya.

No quantitative estimates of the groundwater use are, however, available at the time of writing this report.

⁸⁴ Low earth dams (Natea et al. 2010)

⁸⁵ Ground-runoff supplied to underground tanks (Natea et al., 2010)

http://earthwise.bgs.ac.uk/images/0/02/Ethiopia_Hydrogeology2.png

http://earthwise.bgs.ac.uk/images/2/26/Kenya_Hydrogeology2.png

Aquifer type and productivity

- Unconsolidated - Moderate to High
- Unconsolidated - Low to Moderate
- Igneous Volcanic - Moderate to High
- Sedimentary Fracture - High
- Sedimentary Fracture - Moderate
- Sedimentary Fracture - Low to Moderate
- Sedimentary Fracture - Very Low
- Sedimentary Intergranular/Fracture - High
- Sedimentary Intergranular/Fracture - Moderate
- Sedimentary Intergranular/Fracture - Low to Moderate
- Basement - Low
- Basement - Very Low

Aquifer type and productivity

- Unconsolidated & Semiconsolidated; Intergranular - Moderate to High
- Volcanic; Moderate
- Sedimentary; Intergranular - Moderate
- Basement - Low to Moderate

Figure 108 - Hydrogeology maps of Ethiopia (left) and Kenya (right) (Kebede et al., 2018).

3.2.5 Surface water quality

Water quality data of surface water bodies in the OTB are not available for the project so far. Interactions with the local partners and stake-holders revealed that no stable monitoring programme of the water quality of the Omo River or Lake Turkana is in place and a consultation of the relevant literature confirmed the absence of a long-term surface water quality monitoring programme. Concerning Ethiopia, Awoke et al. (2016) address a review of the existing water policy, legal and institutional regulations for optimum water resources management and the sustainability of aquatic ecosystems. Different policies or strategies aiming at raising awareness have been introduced in Ethiopia in the last two decades: the National Conservation Strategy (1994), the Environmental Policy of Ethiopia (1997), the Ethiopian Water Policy (2001) and the Ethiopian Water Sector Strategy (2005). The issue of water quality is addressed, since growing economic activities are impacting the surface water bodies, however, no clear goals to achieve are outlined. According to Awoke et al. (2016), the main weakness of the Ethiopian water policies is the lack of coherent objectives, monitoring, evaluation and continuity in activities. Focusing specifically on monitoring, the Ethiopian Water Sector Policy gives direction for the establishment of basin institutions for just two of the basins of the country (Blue Nile and Awash), which do not include the Omo. Although the proposed establishment of basin management authorities is a promising direction, the possibility of having more than the two planned authorities is very low, due to a shortage of man power and resources and the absence of institutional arrangements. Therefore, continuous monitoring will not

be feasible, at least in the next few years, and the policy does not even provide direction for standards or monitoring methods for water quality.

Awoke et al. (2016) also offer a snapshot of the water quality of some Ethiopian rivers, including the Omo-Gibe system. They conducted two measurement campaigns, one after the main rainy season (September to November) and one during the dry season (February to April) to show the average level of pollution. Results are repeated here in Table 45, taken from the paper.

The results in Table 45 show several cases clearly exceeding desired levels of nutrients (i.e., nitrogen and phosphorus) and also very depleted oxygen conditions, associated with high concentrations of BOD, which points to an unfavourable environment for the key ecosystems.

Table 45 – Water quality measurements summarized in mean, median, and interquartile range for the impacted sites of Blue Nile, Omo-Gibe, Awash, and Tezeke river basins compared to the reference sites and the concern level (CL), from Awoke et al., 2016.

Parameters, mean (median, IQR)	CL	Reference forest	Impact type		
			Agriculture	Urban	Coffee waste
Blue Nile					
TN(mg/L)	<0.3	0.9 (0.2, 0.1–1.2)	7.3 (8.0,1.5–10.5)	11.1 (5.9,4.4–18.0)	9.3 (8.2, 5.4–10.5)
TP(mg/L)	<0.015	0.02 (0.08,0.06–0.15)	0.4 (0.2, 0.1–0.4)	1.0 (0.2,0.1–2.0)	1.3 (0.4, 0.1–1.4)
DO(mg/L)	>7	6.9 (7.0,6.5–7.2)	6.2 (6.6, 5.8–6.8)	4.9 (5.2, 2.9–6.8)	5.9 (6.2, 5.7–6.6)
BOD5(mg/L)	<3	1.8 (0.7, 0.3–1.0)	12.2 (1.2, 0.7–21.4)	18.4 (15.3,8.1–28.6)	17.6 (3.3,1–22.7)
pH	6.5–9	7.0 (7.0,6.9–7.2)	7.4 (7.4, 7.0–7.6)	7.2 (7.4,6.7–7.7)	7.1 (7.2, 7–7.3)
EC (µS/cm)	–	76 (66, 65–95)	122 (76, 66–156)	92 (86,79–105)	95 (76,64–96)
Omo-Gibe					
TN(mg/L)	<0.3	1.5 (2.7, 1.9–3.4)	20.3 (21.1, 16.7–23.4)	17 (16.4, 14.8–19)	22 (23, 18–26)
TP(mg/L)	<0.015	0.08 (0.08, 0.08–0.1)	0.3 (0.1,0.1–0.4)	0.2 (0.2, 0.1–0.3)	0.3 (0.1, 0.1–0.3)
DO(mg/L)	>7	7.0 (6.9, 6.5–7.3)	6.1 (6.2,5.6–6.5)	5.7 (6.3, 5.7–6.5)	4.7 (4.8,4.3–5.6)
BOD5(mg/L)	<3	2.3 (2.4, 2.2–2.6)	2.7 (2.1,1.5–2.5)	108 (130, 90–150)	64 (57, 24–102)
pH	6.5–9	7.3 (7.3, 6.8–7.8)	7.2 (7.3, 6.7–7.6)	7.3 (7.3, 7.2–7.3)	6.8 (6.8,6.4–7.2)
EC (µS/cm)	–	95 (99, 94–103)	117 (102, 95–130)	140 (140, 120–160)	101 (99, 89–110)
Awash					
		Minimal impact	Agriculture	Urban	
TN(mg/L)	<0.3	0.2 (0.1, 0.1–0.2)	2.6 (2.2, 1.6–2.7)	30.8 (26, 18–46)	
TP(mg/L)	<0.015	0.08 (0.08, 0.05–0.12)	0.9 (0.3, 0.1–1.1)	12.5 (11.2, 6–15)	
DO(mg/L)	>7	7.1 (7.1, 7–7.2)	6.8 (7.0, 6.2–7.5)	2.6 (1.9, 0.9–3.8)	
BOD5(mg/L)	<3	3.2 (2.5, 2–4)	6.9 (5.9, 4.3–7.9)	508 (413, 98–864)	
pH	6.5–9	7.3 (7.3, 7.2–7.4)	7.8 (8.0, 7.2–8.3)	7.2 (7.4, 7.0–7.8)	
EC (µS/cm)	–	93 (92, 81–102)	192 (195, 105–250)	580 (608, 220–800)	
Tekeze					
TN(mg/L)	<0.3	0.7 (0.4, 0.2–0.8)	1.5 (1.0, 0.9–1.6)	3.1 (3.1, 2.2–3.9)	
TP(mg/L)	<0.015	0.13 (0.06, 0.04–0.09)	0.2 (0.1, 0.1–0.2)	2.0 (2.0, 1.3–2.6)	
DO(mg/L)	>7	7.6 (7.5, 7.3–8.1)	6.8 (6.2, 6.1–7.8)	4.9 (5.2, 3.9–6)	
BOD5(mg/L)	<3	6.5 (5.5, 5.2–6.2)	11.3 (10, 7.8–14.5)	29 (30, 21–37)	
pH	6.5–9	7.5 (7.4, 7.2–8.1)	7.6 (7.6, 7.4–7.7)	6.3 (6.6, 6–6.7)	
EC (µS/cm)	–	381 (350, 325–430)	560 (551, 403–573)	514 (456, 403–624)	

The concern level (CL) to protect aquatic life in rivers were compiled from recommended values by European WFD (Chave, 2001) and US-EPA (1986)

Mean values in bold fonts are those significantly different from the reference sites at $p < 0.05$

Sediments in the Omo River Basin

Soil erosion rates are typically high in the Ethiopian highlands, because of natural factors like erosive rainfall and an erosion-prone topography, but also because of the agricultural practices of the

rural population. High soil erosion rates determine high sediment concentration in the waters of the Omo River, and thus a reduced water quality and problems of reservoir siltation for the Gibe I and III dams. (Guzman, 2013).

Devi et al. (2008) measured very high values of total suspended sediment in three locations of the Gibe I reservoir. The measured values are between 280 and 460 mg/l, which exceed the WHO guideline limit of 100 mg/l quoted in Devi et al. (2008). Based on an empirical formula for sheet erosion, they also estimated an input of sediment of 37.5 Mm³/year into the reservoir.

The ESIA for Gibe III Hydropower Project estimates that an average of 18 Mm³/year of sediments will be trapped in the reservoir (approximately half of the estimate given by Devi et al. (2008) for Gibe I), thus defining a maximum lifespan of the reservoir of 130 years (Sogreah, 2010).

The operation of the recently built and planned dams is expected to show an effect on the Omo delta in Lake Turkana, as the new reservoirs will reduce the sediment availability at the river outlet.

3.3 HYDROPOWER

3.3.1 Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP)

The Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP) was established in 2005 as a specialized institution to foster power system interconnectivity between seven signatory Eastern Africa countries, namely: Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Egypt, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda and Sudan. The founder countries were in the following years joined by Tanzania, Libya, Uganda, Djibouti, and South Sudan. The members of EAPP are reported in Table 46 (Wright, 2014).

EAPP objectives include pursuing an optimal development of energy resources in the Eastern Africa Region, and extending the electricity power access to all the countries inhabitants, thereby promoting regional integration, reducing electricity production cost, and creating a suitable environment for investments (EAPP, 2005).

EAPP produced a Master Plan in 2011, successively updated in 2014, containing evaluations on optimal dispatch and least-cost investments for energy generation and transmission for the entire system under different future scenarios. These evaluations serve as recommendations to guide the development of national power systems towards an integrated, reliable, and cost-effective network of energy pooling in the East African region (ibid.).

Table 46 - Members of Eastern Africa Power Pool (Wright, 2014).

ENTITY	ABBREVIATION	COUNTRY
Régie de Production des Eaux et de l'Electricité	REGIDESO	Burundi
Société Nationale d'Electricité	SNEL	DR Congo
Egyptian Electricity Holding Company	EEHC	Egypt
Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation	EEPCo	Ethiopia
Kenya Electricity Generation Company	KenGen	Kenya
The Kenya Electricity Transmission Company	Ketraco	Kenya
Kenya Power and Lighting Company	KPLC	Kenya
General Electricity Company of Libya	GECOL	Libya
Electricity Water and Sanitation Agency	EWSA	Rwanda
National Electricity Corporation	NEC	Sudan
Tanzania Electric Supply Company Ltd.	TANESCO	Tanzania
Société International d'Electricité del Pays del Grands Lacs	SINELAC	DR Congo-Rwanda-Burundi
Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited	UETCL	Uganda

EAPP members are developing countries that are witnessing a fast increase in their population and economic activities, leading to a projected 3.5-fold increase in energy demand in 20 years from 2010 to 2030. Current and projected energy demand of EAPP member states are reported in Figure 109 (IRENA, 2015), where a disparity in demand between member states is evident. Egypt accounts for the largest share of energy demand (75% of the total), while Burundi, Djibouti, Eritrea, Rwanda, and Somalia together total less than 2% of the total.

The regional growth in energy demand is mostly driven by the rising industrial sector, which will consume 44% of the energy by 2030, with urban and rural demand at 39% and 17% respectively.

Figure 109 - Current and projected energy demand of EAPP member states from 2010 to 2030 (IRENA, 2015).

In 2010, the total installed capacity of the entire region was more than 38 GW, of which more than 70% is Egyptian, more than 6 times larger than the closest producer, Ethiopia. Electricity generation largely comes from gas-fired power plants, except for Ethiopia, Burundi, Uganda and Sudan where hydropower is the main source.

Despite the current circumstances of poor diversification among energy sources, the region is characterized by a rich mix of renewable and non-renewable resources to be exploited. Among the non-renewables, other than natural gas reserves, the region can rely on oil and coal. Considering renewables, Kenya is the largest producer of geothermal energy, an expanding sector in the whole region, while hydropower is a relevant source of renewable energy for Egypt, Tanzania, Uganda, Sudan, and, especially, Ethiopia, which has identified additional hydropower projects bound to increase the internal production of nearly 15 GW. Among these projects, the most ambitious is the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD, 6 GW), currently under construction. Moreover, the whole region is highly suitable for wind and solar energy production (IRENA, 2015).

The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA, 2015) projects an increase in exploitation of renewable resources with a significant supply diversification. In the renewable-promotion scenario, represented in Figure 110, wind power shows the biggest growth in installed capacity (60 GW), followed by hydro (30 GW), solar PV (8 GW), and geothermal (5 GW). However, regional trends are strongly dependent on the choices of its biggest player, Egypt, which will continue to account for about 66% of the energy production in 2030. Increased integration will encourage trade from countries with cost-effective renewable resource to those more reliant on fossil fuels.

Figure 110 - Current and projected capacity by source (IRENA, 2015).

The identification of existing and planned energy generation potential is pivotal for EAPP to develop a strategic plan for the cross-boundary power lines and grid that aim at effectively interconnect the region and enable energy trades.

The analysis of the existing transboundary power lines at the year 2013 (highlighted in Figure 111 with a solid line) indicates a situation of poor regional energy exchange with only few countries interconnected. In response, the EAPP produced a development plan to substantially reinforce the power transmission lines network at regional level for the short-to-medium term (reported for the year 2028 in Figure 111) based on the location and capacity of energy generation hubs.

The extended network shows a substantial increase in the number of cross-boundary, high-voltage power lines to sustain regional energy exchange towards a strong integration of the countries' energy sectors (Gebrehiwot, 2013).

Ethiopian Electric Power and Energy Security in Ethiopia

Among the EAPP members, the state-owned Ethiopian Electric Power (EEP) is the fully government-owned public enterprise representative (and sole) electric power producer in Ethiopia. The company was founded in 1948 and is based in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. EEP aims at significantly increasing the Ethiopian energy production potential mainly exploiting clean energy and natural resources, including hydropower generation, wind, geothermal, and waste-to-energy projects, and, contextually, to maximize the access to electricity through the construction of transmission lines (Wright, 2014).

EEP is recognized as a key player to sustain the Ethiopian unprecedented economic growth, as energy security was, and continues to be, a primary issue for the country. In 2009, less than 10% of Ethiopians had access to electricity, and the population mostly relied on traditional solid biomass energy use, particularly fuelwood for cooking purposes, with drastic deforestation and public health impacts (IEA, 2013). At the same time, Ethiopian economy is one of the fastest growing in the world, with an average growth of 10,9% in GDP between 2004 and 2014.

As a result, in the past decades the country has suffered chronic electricity shortages due to a steadily growing imbalance between rapid energy demand growth and underdevelopment of the energy sector. Moreover, the energy demand is projected to rise by a rate of 10-14% per year until 2037 (EEPCo, 2013).

Figure 111 - Regional plan of power line interconnections for 2028 based on national generation plans (Gebrehiwot, 2013).

Hydropower in Ethiopia

Ethiopia aims at becoming a regional power hub by exploiting its exceptional renewable energy resource potential, estimated around 60 GW of electric power producible from hydroelectric, wind, solar and geothermal sources. Of the total, the biggest share is represented by the feasible hydropower potential of 45 GW, of which only 1% was being harnessed before 2009.

As a consequence, EEP has embarked on an ambitious dam building program in order to overcome the energy security emergency and to become not only energy self-sufficient, but also a regional power exporter. Table 47 lists the details of the main Ethiopian dams primarily operated for hydropower production. Three hydropower plants with a combined capacity of 1.18 GW were commissioned in 2009 and 2010 alone (Tekezè, Beles, and Gilgel Gibe II), more than doubling the previous installed capacity of the country. Gibe III began to generate electricity in October 2015, and was finalized in 2016 with the completion of the remaining generators, contributing an additional electrical output of 1.87 GW to the Ethiopian grid and further doubling the country installed capacity.

Table 47 - List of main hydropower dams in Ethiopia (existing and under construction U/C)

* power stations with no associated reservoir. The relative reservoir capacity must be intended as the capacity of the upstream reservoir (Lake Tana for Beles, and Gibe I reservoir for Gibe II) and the dam height must be intended as the hydraulic head between reservoir and the power station.

Dam	Coordinates	First use	Second use	Date of Commission	River	Drainage basin	Reservoir capacity [km ³]	Dam height [m]	Installed capacity [MW]
<u>Aba Samuel</u>	8.788°N 38.706°E	hydropower	flood control	1932	<u>Akaki</u>	<u>Afar Triangle</u>	0.035	22	
<u>Koka</u>	8.468°N 39.156°E	hydropower	flood control	1960	<u>Awash</u>	Afar Triangle	1.9	47	42
<u>Genale Dawa III</u>	5.51°N 39.718°E	hydropower	flood control	2017	<u>Ganale</u>	<u>Jubba</u>	2.6	110	256
<u>Genale Dawa VI</u>	5.68°N 40.93°E	hydropower	irrigation	U/C	Ganale	Jubba	0.18	39	257
Beles*	8.4683°N 39.15°E	hydropower	irrigation	2010	Beles	Nile	9.120*	350*	460
<u>Fincha</u>	9.561°N 37.413°E	hydropower	drinking water	1973	<u>Fincha</u>	Nile	0.65	20	100
<u>GERD</u>	11.214°N 35.08°E	hydropower	flood control	U/C	Blue Nile	Nile	74	155	6450
<u>Tekeze</u>	13.34°N 38.742°E	hydropower	flood control	2010	<u>Tekeze</u>	Nile	9.3	188	300
<u>Melka Wakena</u>	7.225°N 39.462°E	hydropower	drinking water	1989	<u>Shebelle</u>	<u>Shebelle</u>	0.75	42	153
<u>Gibe I</u>	7.831°N 37.322°E	hydropower	flood control	2004	<u>Gilgel Gibe</u>	<u>Turkana Basin</u>	0.92	40	180
Gibe II*	7.762°N 37.56°E	hydropower		2010	Omo	Turkana Basin	0.92*	505*	420
<u>Gibe III</u>	6.844°N 37.301°E	hydropower	flood control	2015	Omo	Turkana Basin	14.7	243	1870
<u>Koyscha</u>	6.460°N 36.340°E	hydropower	irrigation	U/C	Omo	Turkana Basin	6	179	2200

Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam

The most ambitious dam construction project undertaken, yet to be completed, is the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD), on the Blue Nile. With 6.450 GW, the dam will be the largest hydroelectric power plant in Africa when completed, as well as the 7th largest in the world (Elsanabary, 2015). The dam construction began on April 2nd 2011, with a USD4.8 billion project awarded without competitive bidding to *Salini Costruttori*⁸⁶. As of August 2017, the dam was at 60% completion, and it will need additional 5 to 15 years for the reservoir filling phase before being able to operate at full regime (Kumagai, 2016).

The potential impacts of the dam have sparked a severe regional controversy, with Egypt expressing open concern that the dam will reduce the water flowing in the Nile downstream the dam, and into the Egyptian border, and openly demanding that Ethiopia interrupts the dam construction.

It is reported that, upon completion, GERD will act as a stabilizing backbone of the Ethiopian national grid, providing support to the development of the whole country, both in rural and urban areas. All the energy generated by GERD will be going into the national grid, and eventual energy surplus will be exported to Sudan and Djibouti, upon completion of massive transmission lines to the nearer consumption centers (e.g., Khartoum, located 400 km away from the dam) (CapitalEthiopia, 2017).

Energy Sector in Kenya

Kenya is the strongest economy of East and Central Africa, and its capital, Nairobi, is a commercial and services hub for the entire region. With the 2007 governmental program named “Vision 2030”, the country strives at achieving the status of newly-industrialized, middle income country. However, the country economic growth is hampered by a still inadequate energy sector, capable of generating a total of 2150 MW in 2015 (Power Africa, 2015). In 2013, 20% of the population was able to access electricity, a percentage that lowers to 5% when considering rural areas (The Kenya Power and Lighting Company, 2014).

The main company responsible for energy production is the Kenyan Electricity Generating Company (KenGen), state-owned for approximately 71% and responsible for 90% of the installed capacity in the country, while the remaining 10% is managed by independent power producers (Power Africa, 2016).

As part of the Vision 2030, Kenya aims at attracting private investment to reinforce the energy sector by enlarging the transmission network, the production capacity, and shifting the energy generation mix towards a less fossil-intense energy production.

The current energy generation mix is dominated by hydropower and fossil fuel sectors, each accounting for above 35% of generation capacity, while the remaining capacity is almost completely covered by geothermal resources (see Table 48)

Table 48 - Kenyan energy generation mix in 2015 (Energy Regulatory Commission, 2015).

SOURCE	CAPACITY [MW]	CAPACITY [%]
Hydropower	820.6	36.1%
Fossil Fuels (incl. gas, diesel and emergency power)	810	35.7%
Geothermal	588	25.9%
Biogas	26	1.1%
Wind	25.5	1.1%

⁸⁶ <https://www.salini-impregilo.com/en/projects/in-progress/dams-hydroelectric-plants-hydraulic-works/grand-ethiopian-renaissance-dam-project.html>

In the future, Kenya is expected to greatly increase its energy generation capacity, exceeding by 2030 a 10-fold increase with respect to 2013 potential. The future energy mix is expected to drastically change with respect to the current, with most of the investments directed towards the generation of energy from alternative domestic renewable resources to limit the dependence on imported fossil fuels.

The geothermal sector is envisioned to greatly increase its production share in the next years, as Kenya is estimated to possess more than 7,000 MW of undeveloped geothermal energy resources, extremely abundant in the Rift Valley region (Power Africa, 2015). By 2020, geothermal energy is expected to constitute the baseload of Kenya's power system reaching 40% of total installed capacity (Power Africa, 2016).

Large investments are also foreseen for wind power generation. In particular, the ambitious project of the Lake Turkana Wind Farm will result, at its completion, the largest wind farm in Africa, and the largest private investment (USD 800 million) in Kenya's history. Lake Turkana Wind Power Project, with its 301 MW generation capacity is expected to, among other benefits, create 150 permanent jobs, increase national electricity supply by 15-20%, and save US USD180 million per year on imported fuel (Cookson et al., 2017).

Solar energy, absent from 2013 energy mix, will reach a capacity of 430 MW by 2020, moreover, many of the 19 off-grid diesel stations currently installed in remote areas will likely be converted to solar-diesel hybrids (Power Africa, 2016).

Hydropower energy, on the other hand, will experience the opposite tendency. Despite it is currently associated with the highest installed capacity, its share is estimated to drop to only 5% by 2030, given the lack of new large hydroelectric projects (Kianji, 2012).

Moreover, in 2012, the British company of Tullow Oil PLC discovered major oil reserves in the Turkana region, estimated at 750 million barrels. Few years were necessary to assess the commercial viability of oil extraction in the region, and in the beginning of 2018 the oil extraction started. A crude oil pipeline will be developed to connect the Turkana region to the Lamu harbor on the coast, allowing large scale commercial oil exports (Paraskova, 2018).

Oil discovery in Turkana has sparked unprecedented attention to this remote region of Kenya, mainly inhabited by semi-nomad pastoralist tribes with a poverty rate equal to 94.3% in 2006 (Johannes et al., 2014). While oil could constitute an opportunity to lift the region out of poverty, some studies point out the risk that local inhabitants can be penalized by the oil discovery with the reduction and fragmentation of grazing lands, degradation of environment, and growing dependence on temporary oil related jobs, finally leading to the spark of conflicts. This condition, namely the "oil curse", has affected several African countries in the past. To avoid the oil curse, several organizations, including oil companies, are starting to recognize the importance of compensating the population with the construction of social-services infrastructure in Turkana, including schools, roads, and hospitals with the expected results to avoid conflicts, adequately compensate the population, and create a safe environment for business (Johannes et al., 2014).

3.3.2 Hydropower infrastructures: dams and hydropower plants

Among the Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP) members, the state-owned Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation (EEP) is the representative (and sole) electric power producer in Ethiopia. The company was founded in 1948 and is based in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. EEP aims at significantly increasing the Ethiopian energy production potential mainly exploiting clean energy and natural resources, including hydropower generation, wind, geothermal, and waste-to-energy projects, and, contextually, to maximize the access to electricity through the construction of transmission lines (Wright, 2014). The main company responsible for energy production in Kenya is the Kenyan Electricity Generating Company (KenGen), state-owned for approximately 71% and responsible for 90% of the installed capacity in the country, while the remaining 10% is managed by independent power producers (Power Africa, 2016).

With a total fall of about 1800 m (from an elevation of 2300 m at its source to 500 m at lake Turkana level) (Figure 112), the Omo-river is particularly suitable for hydroelectric generation. To exploit its river hydropower potential, EEP has interrupted the natural course of the river and its affluent with a series of dam, namely the Gibe cascade.

The Gibe cascade includes the existing Gibe I dam (184 MW, on the Gilgel Gibe river) and Gibe II power station (420 MW) as well as the newly concluded Gibe III (1870 MW). In addition, in 2016 the construction of Koyssha dam started (Figure 113). While Gibe I and II are conjunctively operated for hydropower production only, Gibe III (and Koyssha) are expected to also provide water to irrigate the extensive sugar plantations in the lower Omo valley (Avery, 2013).

Additionally, EEP envisioned a large number of hydroelectric projects in its 2008 and 2013 Master Plans in many parts of the Ethiopian territory, including several projects on the Omo river and its main tributaries. Among them, the construction of two smaller dam alternatives to Koyssha, namely Gibe IV and Gibe V dams was considered, but soon dismissed as Koyssha project was preferred; the power plants of Halale-Werabesa and Gojeb were proposed on the homonymous rivers, Omo tributaries, in various stages and sizes with the aim of attracting foreign and local investments. Halale-Werabesa HP project managed to obtain founding from a Chinese bank, but the project was suspended after the completion of feasibility and geological studies (International Rivers, 2015).

Lastly, the Turkwel dam (112 MW) in the Kenyan territory regulates the waters of the ephemeral Turkwel river, southern tributary of lake Turkana, for hydropower production and irrigation. Despite being the highest dam in Kenya, the Turkwel dam is much less relevant in terms of flow control capacity and hydropower production potential compared to the Gibe cascade and, given the limited contribution of the Turkwel river to Lake Turkana, less impacting than the dams on the Omo river on the alteration of the natural regime dynamics of the lake itself.

Figure 112 - Elevation profile of the Gibe cascade along Gilgel Gibe and Omo rivers.

Technical sheets for the existing hydropower plants

The technical sheets that have been collected from public literature⁸⁷ for the existing hydropower plants in the OTB are available on the internal project data repository and in Annex II of this report. Alike for ZRB, variables highlighted in red refer to either missing data or data that still needs to be validated by the utility managing the power plants. The covered stations are Gibe I, the Gibe II, the Gibe III in Ethiopia and the Turkwel dam in Kenya.

⁸⁷ At the moment of writing no contact could be established with EEP

Figure 113 - Dams in OTB. Marker area is proportional to the dam installed capacity.

3.3.3 Hydropower production

Ethiopia aims at becoming a regional power hub by exploiting its exceptional renewable energy resource potential, estimated around 60 GW of electric power producible from hydroelectric, wind, solar and geothermal sources. Of the total, the biggest share is represented by the feasible hydropower potential of 45 GW, of which only 1% was being harnessed before 2009. As a consequence, EEP has embarked on an ambitious dam building program in order to overcome the energy security emergency and to become not only energy self-sufficient, but also a regional power exporter. In the Omo basin, the Gibe I and Gibe II hydropower plants with a capacity of 180 MW respectively 420 MW were commissioned in 2004 respectively 2010 alone. Gibe III began to generate electricity in October 2015, and was finalized in 2016 with the completion of the remaining generators, contributing an additional electrical output of 1.87 GW to the Ethiopian grid and further doubling the country's installed capacity. The Koysha dam (2.2 GW) is still under construction. In the Kenyan portion of the OTB, the Turkwel dam (106 MW) is the only one.

3.3.4 Electricity surplus/deficit

The same methodological approach described for the ZRB has been applied to the OTB case study for estimating electricity surplus/deficit data.

Electricity surplus/deficit in OTB

In this section we report the results of the electricity surplus/deficit historical analysis in the OTB, first aggregated at the national scale and then at the power plant scale. In each table, the last row reports the average data and is coloured in green and red in case of electricity surplus and deficit, respectively.

Ethiopia hydropower sector is characterized by a remarkable growth in the electricity demand, which records an almost four-fold increase from 2000 to 2013. The electricity production, however, expands five-fold, significantly incrementing the electricity surplus of the country. The largest increase in production is recorded from 2010 to 2013, after the years 2008-2009 in which the country recorded nearly even values of demand and production (Table 49).

Kenya presents a similar situation with both demand and production growing between 2000 and 2013, although at much smaller rates compared to Ethiopia. Most years record electricity surplus, except for an initial deficit in 2000, and in the years 2008-2009, similarly to Ethiopia (Table 50).

At the power plant level, the hydropower plants Gibe I and II go against the national trend, both recording deficit in production with respect to the allotted demand (Table 51).

Table 49 - Hydropower demand (Howells et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Ethiopia. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	1,474	1,646	-172
2001	1,497	1,992	-495
2002	1,769	2,023	-254
2003	1,913	2,280	-367
2004	2,147	2,521	-374
2005	2,453	2,833	-380
2006	2,705	3,259	-554
2007	2,928	3,385	-457
2008	3,309	3,296	13
2009	3,447	3,524	-77
2010	4,078	4,931	-853
2011	4,654	6,262	-1,608
2012	5,276	7,388	-2,112
2013	5,276	8,338	-3,062
<i>Average</i>	3,066	3,834	-768

Table 50 - Hydropower demand (Howells et al., 2011), production (IEA, 2018) and surplus/deficit at the country level: Kenya. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand.

Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
2000	2,046	1,325	721
2001	2,161	2,403	-242
2002	2,436	3,119	-683
2003	2,923	3,260	-337
2004	2,046	2,869	-823
2005	2,541	3,026	-485
2006	2,776	3,278	-502
2007	3,102	3,488	-386
2008	3,102	2,849	253
2009	3,102	2,170	932
2010	3,102	3,427	-325
2011	3,102	3,451	-349
2012	3,102	4,299	-1,197
2013	3,102	3,945	-843
Average	2,760	3,065	-305

Table 51 - Average hydropower demand, production and surplus/deficit at the hydropower plant level in the OTB. The last column identifies the difference between hydropower demand and production: a positive difference corresponds to a deficit, whereas a negative difference to a surplus in the production with respect to the demand. Demand data for the single plants are from Howells et al. (2011), whereas production data are from EEPCo (1997) and Balbo (2012).

Average Year	Demand [GWh/yr]	Production [GWh/yr]	Demand – Production [GWh/yr]
Gibe I	824	770	54
Gibe II	1,882	1,556	326

3.4 AGRICULTURE, LIVESTOCK AND FISHERIES

3.4.1 Land used for rainfed and irrigated crop production and livestock production and water bodies used for fisheries

The various agro-ecological zones in the OTB make that agricultural practices are very diverse throughout the basin. We tried to delineate the areas currently used for food production in the OTB. This was done for crop and livestock production and fish catch and aquaculture.

Crops

For crop production, we make a distinction between rainfed and irrigated agriculture. The latter was done by identifying and –if possible– georeferencing individual irrigation schemes within the OTB by using literature and open source satellite imagery provided by Google Earth. Further, information on areas under irrigation and the crop type cultivated was collected. The irrigation schemes that could be georeferenced are illustrated in Figure 114. They are mainly concentrated in the more humid Omo-subbasin on the Ethiopian side, and alongside the Turkwel subbasin on the Kenyan side. In the absence of more detailed data available from the involved countries and relevant authorities, the perimeters of the irrigation schemes were identified on the basis of Google Earth

imagery. By subtracting the area equipped by these schemes from the total area under crops as identified in D3.3, the land under rainfed agriculture was delineated (Figure 115). Rainfed agriculture is concentrated in the cooler and wetter part of the OTB, i.e. in the Ethiopian highlands, while almost no rainfed agriculture was identified in the Kenyan part of the OTB, which is characterised by an arid climate.

From Figure 115, it can be seen that the area under irrigation is relatively small compared to the area under rainfed agriculture. However, there are some large irrigation schemes in the basin, which are expected to have a high water demand. The most apparent irrigation scheme is the Kura sugar estate along the Omo river. This scheme currently has a size of ca. 7300 ha, and there are plans to even increase its size in the near future (Avery, 2012). There is still uncertainty about the planned extent, with reported areas ranging from 150000 ha up to 245000 ha (Avery, 2012). Because of its year-round It is expected that these large-scale growing season and high water requirement (between 1500 and 2500 mm/year, depending on factors such as soil, climate and irrigation efficiency) sugar developments will have a significant impact on the water availability locally, and in the rest of the basin (Brouwer and Heibloem, 1986).

Figure 114 - Operational irrigation schemes in the OTB. Size of the dots reflects the size of the scheme.

Figure 115 - Land under rainfed agriculture in the OTB.

Livestock

In D3.3, statistics on livestock were collected from national reports. These statistics were available on various administrative levels, depending on the country. They were assigned to LUs throughout the OTB based on land use type (Figure 116). The ensemble of these LUs is considered to be land

that is –at least partially– used for livestock production. It spreads relatively uniformly over the entire OTB with the exception of the western part of the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region in Ethiopia and southern part of the Turkana county in Kenya. A large part of the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region in Ethiopia is covered by forest of which the Belete Gera Forest and Bonga Forest are examples (ESA, 2018). The southern part of the Turkana county is characterized by an arid climate and the main land cover type is bare soil (ESA, 2018). Both land cover types were assumed to be very marginally suitable for livestock production and therefore, livestock statistics were not assigned to LUs with this land cover type in D3.3. Further, it can be seen that these LUs are especially concentrated in the most northern part of the OTB, where the climate is wet (FAO, 2000), and in the North of Lake Turkana where water is available from the Omo river and the Lake itself. This water availability is not only essential as drinking water, but in the areas where more water is available, the availability of natural vegetation and crops that can be used as fodder for the livestock is expected to be higher.

Figure 116 - Land used for livestock production in the OTB.

Fisheries

D3.3 reported also statistics on fish catch and aquaculture production for 2013 in the OTB. Where no data were available about the location and characteristics of individual aquaculture production units, fish catch was assigned to the major surface water bodies in the OTB (Figure 117).

3.4.2 Food production from crops, livestock and fisheries

Food production from harvested crops, livestock products, and fish catch and production are discussed for subbasins corresponding to the HydroSHEDS⁸⁸ subbasins of Pfaffstetter level 5 (Figure 118). Their number in the OTB is equal to nine. Each one is identified by a unique code, based on the Pfaffstetter coding system. For each of the nine subbasins, agricultural output in terms of produced food energy and proteins was calculated encompassing harvested crops, livestock products, and fish catch and aquaculture. By comparing the sum of these values per subbasin with the human food requirements within that subbasin, we estimated food surplus or deficit.

Figure 117 - River network and major waterbodies associated with fish catch the OTB.

Figure 118 - HydroSHEDS Pfaffstetter level 5 subbasins of the OTB. The HydroSHEDS subbasin numbers are displayed for each of the nine subbasins.

Crops

In D3.3, statistics on production of the 38 major crops were disaggregated and assigned to LUs throughout the OTB based on land use type and slope class. Crop production was expressed in tonnes per year. In the case of multiple cropping cycles during one year, per cycle the production values were summed up. Of these 38 major crops, 36 were retained here because chat and coffee were not considered to be food crops. Next, the production values of these 36 crops were summed up per subbasin and converted into amount of calories (Figure 119) and proteins (Figure 120) based on energy and nutrient coefficients for the considered crops as derived from FAO (2001)

⁸⁸ <https://www.hydrosheds.org>

and USDA (2018). These conversion values can be found in Table 52. In line with the spatial distribution of land used for rainfed agricultural (Figure 115) and -to a lesser extent- for irrigated agriculture (Figure 116), energy and protein production through crops is the highest in the northern, more humid part of the OTB, the Omo-subbasin.

Figure 119 - Energy content of harvested crops in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 120 - Protein content of harvested crops in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Livestock

Head numbers for five categories of livestock (cattle, sheep, pigs, goats and poultry) reported for a given administrative unit in a given year were assigned to LUs in the OTB as reported in D3.3 (Figure 116). In order to convert these livestock head numbers into livestock product offtake per year, we estimated meat, milk and egg offtake cattle, sheep, pigs, goats and poultry per livestock class and per year. The offtake values are dependent on the region (Otte and Chilonda, 2001). Therefore for each subbasin, the main livestock production system was determined based on the map about ruminant production systems in sub-Saharan Africa created by Otte and Chilonda (2001) (Figure 121). Finally, we computed an estimation of the annual offtake of animal products per animal for each of these livestock production systems (

Table 53). For cattle, goats and sheep, these numbers are based on Otte and Chilonda (2001). For pig and poultry products, they are based on Jahnke (1982) and no distinction could be made between the different livestock production systems.

Per subbasin, the total offtake of livestock products (in kg/year) was calculated and this was converted into amount of calories (Figure 122) and proteins (Figure 123) based on nutrient contents of the animal products according to FAO (2001). These conversion values are assumed to be the same as for the ZRB and can be found in Table 23.

While crop energy and protein production were rather low in the southern part of the OTB, energy and protein supply from livestock products is high in this area, as well as in the Lower Omo valley. Whereas the land devoted to livestock production is rather uniformly spread throughout OTB (Figure 116), the livestock densities are much more variable being co-determined by the carrying capacity of the land. In more arid conditions rainfed agriculture is difficult while extensive livestock production systems are more competitive.

Fisheries

The quantities of fish catch and aquaculture production calculated in D3.3 were summed per subbasin and converted into amounts of calories (Figure 124) and proteins (Figure 125) based on energy and protein contents of fresh fish according to FAO (2001). It was assumed that all fish caught and produced were pelagic fish. The energy and protein content was assumed to be the same as for the ZRB and can be found in Table 24. Fish energy and protein production is mainly concentrated in the Lower Omo valley in Ethiopia and in the Kenyan part of the OTB, containing the major share of Lake Turkana.

Crops, livestock and fisheries combined

For each of the nine subbasins in the OTB, the sum of the total annual agricultural output in terms of amount of calories (Figure 126) and proteins (Figure 127) was calculated by adding the amounts of calories (respectively proteins) coming from harvested crops, livestock products and fish catch and production.

Table 52 - Energy content (kcal) and protein content (grams) per 100g retail weight of 36 crops considered (from FAO (2001) and USDA (2018)).

Crop	Energy content [kcal/100g]	Protein content [g/100g]	Crop	Energy content [kcal/100g]	Protein content [g/100g]
Avocado	119	1.5	Mango	45	0.4
Banana	60	0.7	Millet	340	9.7
Barley	332	11	Neug	483	17.35
Beans	341	22.1	Oats	385	13
Cabbage	19	1	Onion	31	1.1
Cassava	109	0.9	Orange	34	0.7
Chickpeas	358	20.1	Papaya	26	0.4
Eth. cabbage	19	1	Potato	67	1.6
Fababeans	88	7.92	Red haricots	337	22.53
Fieldpeas	31	1.1	Red pepper	26	0.99
Garlic	332	11	Sorghum	343	10.1
Grasspeas	31	1.1	Sugarcane	30	0.2
Green pepper	20	0.86	Sweet potato	92	0.7
Groundnuts	567	25.7	Taro	86	1.5
Kale	35	2.92	Teff	367	13.3
Lentils	346	24.2	Tomato	17	0.8
Linseed	498	18	Wheat	334	12.2
Maize	356	9.5	Yam	101	1.3

Table 53 - Annual livestock product offtake in kg per animal for the main agricultural zones in the OTB (from Otte and Chilonda (2001) and Jahnke (1982)).

Annual offtake [kg/animal]	Livestock production system		
	Agropastoral/ semi-arid mixed	Highland mixed	Pastoral/agropastoral
<i>Cattle</i>			
Meat	10.9	6.8	11.8
Milk	40	24.8	41.4
<i>Sheep</i>			
Meat	2.9	2.7	1.8
Milk	3.3	1.5	3.3
<i>Goats</i>			
Meat	3	3.1	2.3
Milk	1.8	1	2
<i>Pigs</i>			
Meat	33	33	33
<i>Poultry</i>			
Meat	1	1	1
Eggs	1	1	1

Figure 121 - Main livestock production systems in the OTB.

Figure 122 - Energy content of livestock products in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 123 - Protein content of livestock products in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 124 - Energy content of fish catch and production in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 125 - Protein content of fish catch and production in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 126 - Total energy content of agricultural products in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 127 - Total protein content of agricultural products in terms of tonnes protein per year per subbasin in the OTB.

3.4.3 Water use associated with irrigated crop production and livestock production

Crops

Although a proper assessment of crop water consumption will be provided through modelling results to be reported in D3.5, we carried out in this section a first attempt to estimate water requirements for irrigated agriculture by considering only areas that were identified as irrigated (Figure 114). We aggregate them by subbasin (Figure 128) and computed their corresponding gross irrigation water requirement.

In D3.3 maize was identified as the most produced crop in the OTB. To calculate the gross irrigation water requirement, we made the assumption that all irrigation schemes produced maize, and this all year round. Gross irrigation water requirement was calculated following the same methodology as in the ZRB and was summed per subbasin (Figure 129). The results show that water required for irrigation is highest in the subbasins around Lake Turkana, the Turkwel and Kerio river and in the Lower Omo valley.

Livestock

Total annual water requirement for livestock (Figure 130) was calculated by multiplying the average daily water requirement per animal with the total livestock head count per subbasin. The average daily water requirement for livestock was assumed to be the same as for the ZRB and can be found in **Error! Reference source not found.** Water consumption for livestock production is highest in the most southern part of the OTB, around the Turkwel and Kerio River and in the Lower Omo valley, where livestock counts and area of land devoted to livestock production are highest. Water requirements for livestock production are higher than those estimated for irrigated agriculture (Figure 129).

Figure 128 - Total area under irrigation per subbasin in the OTB based on identified irrigation schemes.

Figure 129 - Annual gross irrigation water requirement in hm^3/yr per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 130 - Annual livestock water requirement in hm^3/yr per subbasin in the OTB.

3.5 ENVIRONMENT

3.5.1 Major water capturing and water dependent ecosystems

The OTB encompasses 20 key biodiversity areas (BirdLife International, 2018). Nine of these 20 are natural areas that we identified as most relevant for the interaction with the hydrological cycle. They include water dependent ecosystems such as lakes, rivers, wetlands (floodplain grasslands, deltas) and riparian forests. These water dependent ecosystems are mostly located in the dry low-lying areas that are located in the centre of the endorheic basin (Figure 131). Lake Turkana is particularly dependent on inflows, as it does not have an outflow but high levels of evaporation. The only water dependent area that is legally protected is Omo national park (Table 54). However, major parts near the Omo river are currently degazetted from the national park to the benefit of the Kura sugar project. Areas that have an important role in supplying water are mountain forests and wet grasslands that store water and release it gradually. These are mostly located in the upper regions of the catchments, where most rainfalls of the region are recorded (Figure 131). Some of these areas are legally protected, for example as part of a new Biosphere reserve that includes parts of the Gojeb wetlands, the Belete-Gera forest and the Bonga forest (Table 54).

Figure 131 - Location of the key natural areas with the biggest importance for the hydrological cycle of the OTB. Areas are classified according to whether they are more water dependent or have a more water supplying function. The areas are listed in Table 54.

3.5.2 Water-related services provided by water dependent ecosystems and indicators

The most important services provided by water dependent ecosystems in the OTB are flood recession agriculture and fisheries. The cultural service tourism has some potential but is not yet very developed.

Flood-recession agriculture

About 613 km² in the OTB overlap with wetlands (based on our own analysis in deliverable D3.4⁸⁹). As described for the ZRB, also many people in the OTB benefit from the “free” soil improvements (compared to the use of irrigation and fertilization) provided by wetlands and seasonally inundated areas (Avery, 2013). Especially along the Lower Omo (ID #7 in Figure 131) and inside the Omo delta (ID #8), local communities depend heavily on small-scale flood-recession agriculture. The narrow bands of flood recession agriculture along the banks of the Lower Omo are estimated to account for approximately 11,000 ha (EEPSCO, 2009). The estimated number of population engaged in flood recession agriculture along the Lower Omo varies between 66,000 -100,000 people (SOGREAH, 2010; Woodroffe, 1996). Wet grasslands that typically occur in the upper catchment of the Omo (IDs #1, 2) but also in the Omo (ID #5) and Mago (ID #6) national parks are also commonly used by people to grow crops and to graze their animals (Gil-Romera et al., 2010).

Table 54 - Name and characterization of the key natural areas with importance for the hydrological cycle.

Map ID	Name	Country	Protected	Area (km ²)	Type	Water
1	Gibe headwaters	Ethiopia	Little/ none	222	wetland	supplying
2	Gojeb wetlands	Ethiopia	Some	189	wetland	supplying
3	Belete-Gera Forest	Ethiopia	Whole	1,545	forest	supplying
4	Bonga forest	Ethiopia	Whole	1,673	forest	supplying
5	Omo National Park	Ethiopia	Whole	4,346	openland	dependent
6	Mago National Park	Ethiopia	Whole	1,227	wetland	supplying
7	Lower Omo	Ethiopia	Little/ none	1,255	wetland	dependent
8	Lake Turkana and Omo delta	Ethiopia	Little/ none	659	wetland	dependent
9	Lake Turkana	Kenya	Little/ none	7,350	lake	dependent

Fisheries

The most important places in the OTB, where people rely on fisheries are Lake Turkana and parts of the Omo delta (ID #8, 9). The Omo river itself (ID #7) is occasionally used for fishing activities, especially to bridge times of low yields from agriculture (Turton, 1977).

For lake Turkana, five types of fish behaviour are known (Hopson, 1982):

1. Spawning only in the river Omo;
2. Spawning within the mouths of both the major rivers and ephemeral rivers during periods of spate;
3. Spawning in the littoral region of the lake; and
4. Spawning away from the shore in the open lake.

Out of the 11 economically most valuable species, four belong to group (a), four to group (b), one to group (c) and two to group (d). According to records from 2013, group a) generated a value of 843 260 US\$, group b) 826 610, group c) 1 902 960 and group d) 692 930 (Table 55). Historical stream flows (1964-2001) at the Gibe III location ranged from average values of 71 m³/s in February to 1530 in August. Long-term minimum flows were recorded with 25 m³/s in 1973 and the maximum with 2360 in 1988 (EEPSCO, 2009). This illustrates the strong seasonal and decadal variations that lead to pronounced dynamics in the levels of Lake Turkana and the inundated areas along the shore (see section 3.2.2). Apart from the species in group (d) that are potentially only affected by reduced water volumes due to lower lake levels, all other species depend on seasonal variation of

⁸⁹ DAFNE-Deliverable 3.4. Key ecosystems and ecosystem services in the Omo and Zambezi river basins.

inflows from the Omo river. If surface water variations are reduced due to damming and flow equalization, this will affect most of the fish species in a negative way with implications for nutrition and the economy around Lake Turkana (Gownaris et al., 2017).

Table 55 – Overview of the spawning behaviour of the economically most important fish species in Lake Turkana (Hopson, 1982) and the quantity and value of fisheries for each species on the Kenyan side of Lake Turkana in 2013 (Kenyan Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, 2013)

Scientific name	Spawning group	Spawning site	Spawning season	Distribution	Quantity [tonnes]	Value [US \$]
Citharinus citharus	a	R. Omo only	Flood season	Inshore and R. Omo	120	141,180
Alestes dentex	a	R Omo only	Flood season	Lake and river	329	273,590
Distichodus niloticus	a	R. Omo only	Flood season	Littoral zone, R. Omo	330	345,620
Barbus bynni	a	R. Omo only	Flood season	Flood season	91	82,870
<i>Sum group a</i>					870	843,260
Clarias sp.	b	River mouth	Flood season	Inshore	61	4,860
Synodontis schall	b	Inshore and R.Omo	Flood season	Lake and river	141	118,840
Labeo horie	b	Lake and R. Omo	Flood season	Lake and river	657	604,650
Hydrocynus forskalii	b	Lake and R. Omo	Flood season	Lake and river	109	98,260
<i>Sum group b</i>					968	826,610
Oreochromis niloticus	c	Lake shore, pools	Continuous	Inshore, river	1,812	1,902,960
<i>Sum group c</i>					1,812	1,902,960
Lates niloticus	d	Open lake and R. Omo	Continuous	Pelagic, and R. Omo	583	684,380
Bagrus bayad	d	Open lake and R. Omo	April - July (rainy season)	Lake and river	105	8,550
<i>Sum group d</i>					688	692,930
<i>Total sum</i>					4,338	4,265,760

Tourism

In the OTB, the tourism economy is still marginal but it grows fast. In the SNNPRS region of Ethiopia, annual incomes from the tourism industry increased from 50 000 US\$ in 1997 to 440 000 US\$ in 2006 (SOGREAH, 2010). The natural potential for further development is high. The landscape diversity ranges from mountain forests in the Kafa biosphere reserve (IDs #2, 3, 4, Schormann, 2011), through grasslands and savannas in the Omo (ID #5) and Mago (ID #6) national parks down to the landscapes of the Omo valley (ID #7) and lake Turkana (ID #9) with their unique culture and landscapes and often referred to as the “cradle of mankind”.

Water supply

The most important areas that have water-supplying functions are the mountainous areas in the northern part of the OTB. Forests (IDs #3, 4) and wetlands (IDs #1, 2) in the upper river catchment as well as in Omo (ID #5) and Mago (ID #6) national parks store and filter water resources and only gradually release them to the river system. A complete lack of data makes an estimation of

the impact of forests and wetlands impossible on the basis of observations. This will be possible only by means of model based simulations, as expected to occur in D3.5.

3.6 DEMOGRAPHY

3.6.1 Major urban centres

In Ethiopia and Kenya, there are seventeen urban centres with more than 100,000 inhabitants. In comparison to the ZRB, the OTB has a significantly lower concentration of major urban centres, with only one city (> 100,000 in.), Jimma (Ethiopia), located within the geographical area of the OTB. In addition to being a major urban center, Jimma is of particular importance as the Gilgel-Gibe hydropower dam is located in the Jimma region. However, both countries have several major urban centres which fall outside the boundaries of the OTB, which inevitably rely on outputs of activities dependent on OTB resources such as agriculture and energy production. Table 56 outlines the main urban centres in Ethiopia and Kenya with Jimma highlighted in grey.

Table 56 - List of major urban centres in OTB countries: OTB urban centres in gray (Source: World Population Review, 2018).

Country	City Name	2018 Population	Location (Google Map link)	Coordinates	
Ethiopia	Addis Ababa	2,757,729	Link	9.02497	38.74689
	Dire Dawa	252,279	Link	9.59306	41.86611
	Mek'ele	215,546	Link	13.49667	39.47528
	Nazret	213,995	Link	8.55000	39.26667
	Bahir Dar	168,899	Link	11.59364	37.39077
	Gondar	153,914	Link	12.60000	37.46667
	Dese	136,056	Link	11.13333	39.63333
	Hawassa	133,097	Link	7.06205	38.47635
	Jimma	128,306	Link	7.67344	36.83441
	Bishoftu	104,215	Link	8.75225	38.97846
Kenya	Nairobi	2,750,547	Link	-1.28333	36.81667
	Mombasa	799,668	Link	-4.05466	39.66359
	Nakuru	259,903	Link	-0.28333	36.06667
	Eldoret	218,446	Link	0.52036	35.26993
	Kisumu	216,479	Link	-0.10221	34.76171
	Thika	200,000	Link	-1.03326	37.06933
	Malindi	118,265	Link	-3.21799	40.11692

3.6.2 Population number by subbasin

The population within the OTB was calculated using the same methodology as for the ZRB (see section 2.6.2). The population density and the total population of OTB are calculated as 103.12 people/km² and a total 10,081,880 inhabitants respectively. Existing literature would suggest these figures are slightly higher than expected, with other estimates putting the total population of the Omo river basin at approximately 6.5 million and that of Turkana at 780,000 people (PHE-Ethiopia Consortium; African Great Lakes Information Platform, 2018; Michigan State University, 2018). The results of this exercise can be found in Figure 132, Figure 133 and Figure 134, and in Table 57.

Figure 132 - Population density per subbasin within the OTB (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Figure 133 - Night light occurrence per subbasin within the OTB (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Figure 134 - Night Light Intensity across the OTB (Source: Linard et al., 2012; Worldpop, 2015).

Table 57 - Total Population in OTB- Breakdown by subbasin (Source: Linard et al., 2012; worldpop, 2015)

Subbasin ID	Normalised night light index [-]	Mean population density [1/km ²]	Area [km ²]	Total population [-]
1	1.00	3.46	53	183
2	9.12	25.03	48,649	1,217,892
3	1.00	8.80	15,813	139,165
4	1.00	5.60	12,292	68,811
5	17.81	89.41	42,948	3,839,890
6	1.00	130.68	7,110	92,912
7	25.63	291.47	7,954	2,318,325
8	21.40	147.71	10,619	15,68,494
9	100.00	225.96	5,217	1,178,836
<i>Mean Population Density</i>		87.77		
<i>Total Area (km²)</i>			150,655.00	
<i>Total Population</i>				10,424,508

3.6.3 Water consumption by private households

Withdrawals for domestic uses include drinking water, municipal use or supply, and use for public services, commercial establishments and homes. Taking into account the water consumption in the domestic sector for each country of the OTB (computed as a percentage of the annual total water withdrawals per country) it is possible to estimate the annual water consumption per capita for the sector. For the purpose of estimation, we assume that this percentage remains stable from 2005. Additionally, using the OTB share (%) of each riparian country and assuming that the domestic consumption per capita is homogeneous across each country, it is possible to estimate the total water consumption of the portion of each river basin country that lies within the OTB. The results of this calculations are summarized in the following Table 58.

Table 58 - Private households annual water consumption per capita in m³ of OTB countries (Source: World Bank, 2018).

Country	OTB Share (%)	Water Use per Capita	Water Use In OTB [m ³]
Ethiopia	7.16	10.55	57,973,303
Kenya	12	13.04	56,403,840

Based on the estimates of the total annual water consumption per capita of private households in the OTB countries (Table 58) and the population density for each of the OTB subbasins (Table 57), it is possible to calculate the total water consumption of the private households disaggregated by subbasin in each country. In the case of transboundary subbasins, an average consumption value per capita of the subbasin countries is used. In this specific case, Uganda and South Sudan, which are included in the basin as parts of sub-basins 2 and 4, were not taken into account due to lack of available data on the water use per capita. The resulting values are reported in Table 59.

Access rates to safe drinking water supplies and sanitation services in Ethiopia have historically been amongst the lowest in Sub-Saharan Africa. According to the World Bank (2018), in 2015 the percentages of the total population which had access to at least basic drinking water services was

39% and percentage of the total population using at least basic sanitation services was only 7.1%. As a result of considerable efforts to improve the water accessibility (especially in the more arid parts of the country), Ethiopia was able to meet the MDG target of 57% access to water. This figure translates to more than 52 million people with access to drinking water within a 1.5km radius (UNICEF-Ethiopia, 2016).

In Ethiopia, the water use in Private households has a decreasing trend of -0.03% from 1990 to 1994, with only a slight increase of 0.004% in 1991 (Figure 135). Then it remains practically stable until 2013 when an increasing trend of 0.08% is observed to 2015. One can note that, except for the periods 1990-1994 and 2014-2015 (the above decreasing and increasing trends respectively), there are no extreme variations from the average water use in this sector.

Table 59 - Water use by private households in the OTB: Breakdown by subbasin.

Subbasin ID	Water Use [m³]
1	2,389
2	15881306
3	1,814,705
4	811,629
5	40,510,843
6	9,802,212
7	24,458,330
8	16,547,612
9	12,436,730
Total Water Use	122,265,757

Figure 135 - Trend graph of annual water use for private households in Ethiopia (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

In Kenya, the water use in Private households has a slight increasing trend of 0.016% from 1990 to 2015 (Figure 136). One can note that, except for the time period of 2014-2015, there are not extreme variations from the average water use in this sector. In Kenya, as at 2015 the percentages of the total population which had access to at least basic drinking water services was 58%. While

both access to clean water and the percentage of the total population using at least basic sanitation services stood at 30%; considerably higher than the figures recorded in Ethiopia for the same period. Additionally, the annual increase in the total population of the country translates to an increase in water demand (World Bank, 2018).

Figure 136 - Trend graph of annual water use for private households in Kenya (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

3.6.4 Energy consumption and access to electricity by private households

As in the preceding subsection, the energy consumption in the domestic sector for each country of the OTB is used to estimate the annual energy consumption per capita for the domestic sector. Energy consumption refers to energy usage from petroleum and biomass and waste electricity. Additionally, using the OTB share (%) of each riparian country (Sundin, 2017) and assuming that the domestic consumption per capita is homogeneous across each country, it is possible to estimate the total energy consumption per portion of each river basin country within the ZRB. The results of this exercise are summarized in the following Table 60.

Table 60 - Private households energy consumption per capita per year in KWh in the OTB countries (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017 and World Bank, 2018).

Country	OTB Share (%)	Energy Use per Capita	Energy Use In OTB [TJ]
Ethiopia	7.16	3,483.90	896,87
Kenya	12	2,444.12	49,875

Based on the estimates of the total annual private households energy consumption per capita of the OTB countries (Table 60) and the population density for each of the ZRB subbasin (Table 57), it is possible to compute the total energy consumption of the private households disaggregated by subbasin in each country. In this specific case, Uganda and South Sudan, which are included to the basin through sub-basins 2 and 4, were not taken into account due to lack of available data on the water use per capita. Our results are summarized in Table 61.

Table 61 - Energy Use in the OTB – Breakdown by subbasin.

Subbasin ID	Energy Use [TJ]
1	1.61
2	10,716.02
3	1,224.48
4	734.25
5	48,160.02
6	11,653.05
7	29,076.50
8	19,672.10
9	14,785.01
<i>Total Energy Use [TJ]</i>	<i>136,023.04</i>

In Ethiopia it is estimated that biomass fuels account for 88 % of the total energy consumed in the country. In urban areas access to petroleum fuels and electricity has enabled a significant proportion of the population there to employ these for cooking and other domestic energy requirements, (Kebede, 2014). Access to electricity within the country has increased significantly over the last seven years; between 2007 and 2011 the number of towns connected to the grid grew more than three-fold from 1,620 to 5,866, increasing connectivity to electricity services to 53%. Households are connected to the grid by either having a direct electricity meter from the utility company or through sharing meters from their connected neighbours. By mid-2011 approximately 22.5% of households were connected to the grid either through private meters (9.3%) or shared connections (13.2%). In 2013, the electricity connectivity rate of households in urban areas was 87.4% while in rural areas this figure dropped to a mere 4.9%. A reported 2.03 million consumers were connected to the grid, of which approximately 1.65 million were households (Ministry of Water, Irrigation and Energy, 2013).

In Kenya, the energy use in by private households experienced a major increase of 281.11% from 2007 to 2008 (Figure 137). Afterwards there is a slight upward convergence of 8.4% to 2011, and then the energy consumption remains stable till 2015. One can also note that there are extreme variations from the average energy use in this sector.

Figure 137 - Trend graph of annual energy use for private households in Kenya (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

3.6.5 Food surplus/deficit at subbasin scale

Food production versus food requirements

By comparing at subbasin scale the amount of calories and proteins available from the combination of harvested crops, livestock and fish products, as derived in section 3.4.2, with the amount of calories and proteins required by private households, we calculated the food deficit or surplus.

Daily food energy and protein requirement numbers (in kcal/capita and g proteins/capita) were available per country for the year 2000-2013. From these data we computed the average daily food energy and protein requirement for each country. In the case of a subbasin being shared among multiple countries, we calculated the weighted average of daily food energy and protein requirement per capita and subbasin by assuming a weight proportional to the fraction of the area of the country within the subbasin. By multiplying the average daily food energy requirement per capita for each subbasin with the population number within that subbasin (see section 3.6.2), we calculated the total food energy and protein requirement per day. These numbers were converted to annual requirements by simply multiplying by 365 days.

We calculated the absolute annual food production deficit or surplus (Figure 138) and (Figure 139) and relative food production daily deficit or surplus (Figure 140) and (Figure 141) per subbasin in the OTB by using the same methodology as for the ZRB.

A food production surplus in terms of calories is calculated for a large part of the OTB (Figure 138) and (Figure 140), while the Turkwel and Kerio River Basins are characterized with a food production deficit in terms of calories. A deficit in food protein production is calculated for the Lower Omo valley (Figure 139) and (Figure 141), while a surplus in proteins is produced in the Turkwel and Kerio River basin. This can be explained by the type of agricultural system producing the food. In the lower part of the OTB, in the Turkwel River Basin, a relatively large part of the food is coming from livestock products due to the dry character of the area which is not suitable for crop production. Livestock products are relatively high in proteins compared to crops (Table 23 and Table 52). While, e.g., 1.8 litres of cow milk could fulfil the daily protein requirements, almost twice as much milk would be needed to fulfil the daily calorie demand. The contrary is true for food protein production.

Achieving a balance locally and across subbasins between production and demand of calories and proteins, has implications on water demand. If trading among regions is not considered as option, achieving a balance in the subbasins characterized by an overproduction of both calories and proteins implies a reduction of food production and thus a decrease of the water demand. The opposite is obviously true for regions with a deficit in both calorie and protein production.

In areas with an overproduction in calories, but with an underproduction of proteins (or vice versa), the steps to be taken are less straightforward. For example, let us assume we want to create a balance in food production in terms of calories and proteins within HydroSHED subbasin 11542 (Figure 118) by only adapting the amount of chicken meat and maize produced. Maize contains 365kcal/100g and 9.5g proteins/100g (Table 52). Chicken meat contains 185kcal/100g and 17.1g proteins/100g. In subbasin 11542, there is an underproduction of 302.69kcal per capita per day and an overproduction of 11.09g proteins per capita per day. Solving the resulting set of equations suggests that producing an additional 167g of maize per capita per day and producing 158g of chicken meat less per capita per day results in a balance in calorie and protein production. According to the current average estimate of water consumption –higher for 1 kg of meat than for 1 kg of crops (e.g., Waterfootprint.org, 2018)– and given that the additional weight of maize to be produced is almost the same as the reduction in weight of chicken meat to be produced, one can assume that the water demand in this part of the OTB could go down. The opposite is true for the upper part of the OTB, where an overproduction of proteins and an underproduction of calories can be seen. In subbasin 11545 for example, there is an overproduction of 58kcal per capita per day and an underproduction of 1.81g proteins per capita per day. Decreasing the maize production by 308g per capita per day and increasing the chicken meat production by 277g per day would solve this imbalance. Achieving this would imply an increase of water demand. In reality, the implications

on water demand also depend on social and economic policies, which may introduce further nex-uses aiming at food security and growth of agricultural export.

Figure 138 - Food production deficit/surplus (in Tcal per year) per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 139 - Food production deficit/surplus (in tonnes proteins per year) per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 140 - Food production deficit/surplus (in kcal per capita per day) per subbasin in the OTB.

Figure 141 - Food production deficit/surplus (in g protein per capita per day) per subbasin in the OTB.

3.7 ECONOMY, INDUSTRY, MINING

The industry and mining sector plays an important role in the economy of each country since supply consumer goods, creates employment opportunities and through exports earn foreign exchange.

3.7.1 Major industrial mining sites

Major industrial and mining sites

There are approximately 2,527 industrial sites in Kenya, 1,206 (47.8%) of which are located in the capital city of Nairobi. In descending order, the following districts are listed as most industrialized: Mombasa (with 258 industrial sites), Nakuru (with 164 industrial sites), Kiambu (with 126 industrial sites) and Kisumu (with 96 industrial sites). Three major industrial subsectors account for 60% of the national production. These are; food, beverage, and tobacco (accounting for 26.8% of industrial production), wood, wooden products and paper related goods (17.5%) and Textiles (15.7%)⁹⁰. Due to lack of regional data on specific major industrial or mining sites for the OTB at the time of producing this deliverable, analysis has been undertaken with data available at national level.

Employment in industry

As cited in Deliverable 4.6⁹¹, both the industrial and services sectors in Ethiopia contributed significantly to GDP growth, expanding at a rapid rate of 18.7% and 10.3% respectively. Construction, manufacturing, and electricity sub-sectors were the most important contributors to the faster growth of the industrial sector, and grew respectively by 20.7%, 17.4%, and 11.4% in the period between 2016 and 2017 (compared to 25%, 18.4%, and 15% respectively between 2015 and 2016) (Senoga and Zerihun, 2018).

In Ethiopia, an increasing trend of 204.53% for the employment in industry (including mining) is observed from 1991 to 2005 (Figure 142). Then a decreasing trend of -4.79% follows from 2005 to 2010. Finally, the employment exhibits an increasing trend of 32.04% to 2017. One can note that, except for the time periods of 1991-1996 and 2015-2017, there are no extreme variations from the average employment of 5.28% in this sector.

Manufacturing is a major source of employment in urban areas of Kenya and is tied to other sectors within the economy such as agriculture and services. In Kenya, a decrease of -10.25% for the employment in the industrial sector (mining included) has been observed from 1991 to 1993 (Figure 143). This is followed by an increasing trend of 30.88% from 1993 to 2007, with a slight decrease of -5.47% between 1997 and 1999. Finally, a decreasing trend of -10.74% has been noticed from 2007 to 2017. These figures indicate that there have been no extreme variations from the average water use of 14.25% in this sector.

3.7.2 Water use by industry and mining

Water is vital for industrial development as it is a major input in industrial production. Thus, an increase in production activity translates into an increase in water use within this sector. Figure 144 shows that in Ethiopia, the water used by the industrial sector (mining included) exhibits a decreasing trend of -3.25% from 1990 to 1993 is observed, followed by an increase of 6.96% to 1994. The water use fluctuates around its average until 2013, before increasing by 6.47% in 2015. This period of increased water use within the sector coincides with a period of rapid economic development in the country largely due to inward investment particularly in infrastructure and transport development. This has led to the establishment of Ethiopia as one of the fastest growing economies globally, with further economic expansion forecasted at an annual growth rate of 6.2% until 2022 (Kopf, 2017). The wider industrial sector in Ethiopia, particularly manufacturing as a subset of this, grew at a faster rate after 2005. Thus, the annual rate of growth of industrial output doubled to nearly

⁹⁰ Kenya National Water Report. Available at: <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0014/001488/148866E.pdf>.

⁹¹ DAFNE-Deliverable 4.6. Models of the economic development in the Omo river basin.

20% by 2015 while the manufacturing output grew by 10% per annum from 2005 to 2010 and by 17.9% in 2015 (Oqubay, 2018).

Figure 142 - Trend graph for employment in industry (including mining) in Ethiopia (Source: World Bank, 2018).

Figure 143 - Trend graph for employment in industry (including mining) in Kenya (Source: World Bank, 2018).

Except for the period of 2014-2015, one can note that there are no extreme variations from the average annual water use in the Kenyan industrial and mining sectors. In Kenya, manufacturing alone accounts for 14% of GDP (The Kenya Economic Outlook, 2017). According to the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS), the manufacturing sector registered a declined growth of 1.9% in Q3 2016 compared to a growth of 3.3% in the similar quarter in 2015. The Kenyan Ministry of Industry is working to implement an investment and trade program, which has formulated a policy to promote local industry through procurement of locally made products. In Ethiopia, the large-scale irrigation development by the state-owned Ethiopian Sugar Corporation is in the process of implementing a plan to create 100,000 hectares of irrigated plantations in the Lower Omo. As such, greater demand for water is to be expected within the mining, industrial and agricultural sectors.

However, as in the case of the ZRB, the importance of conserving water (both from an environmental and economic perspective) must be recognised by major companies, and measures implemented to improve the water efficiency of their production.

Figure 144 - Trend Graph for water use by industry (including mining) in Ethiopia (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

Figure 145 - Trend Graph for water use by industry (including mining) in Kenya (Source: EORA Global MRIO, 2017).

3.8 INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF WATER GOVERNANCE

3.8.1 Overview of applicable legal texts

Global legal instruments and applicability to OTB

The Global legal instruments applicable to OTB are the same that are applicable to the ZRB. For the description of these instruments we refer therefore to section 2.8.1.

Neither Kenya nor Ethiopia have signed or ratified the UNWC, with the implication that the Convention does not yet bind these states. However, Kenya did vote in favour of the adoption of the Convention during its inception. Ethiopia was recorded as abstaining and had previously made a number of reservations to some of the provisions during the drafting stage of the UNWC. Ethiopia has however been noticeably supportive of the process of the UNWC, voting in favour of the text when it was adopted by the Working Group of the Convention. Therefore, while neither Kenya nor Ethiopia are party to the UNWC, both Kenya and Ethiopia can be said to be supportive of the UNWC in principle regarding its spirit, objectives and aspirations.

Regional legal instruments

In comparison to the ZRB, which has progressively developed a specialised regional framework through the formation of a number of SADC level instruments, the OTB lacks the same comprehensive regional level governance. However, a number of broader instruments, which still have some relevance to the environmental goals and aims found in international water law, can be used to demonstrate commitment to such goals in the OTB region, as demonstrated in Table 62)

Basin legal instruments

Aside from the 1970 Border Agreement, Kenya and Ethiopia relations have mainly revolved around trade agreements,⁹² and to date there is no treaty between Kenya and Ethiopia directly addressing the governance of the OTB at the basin level. However, there have been two recent agreements between the countries relevant to the OTB: an agreement signed in December 2016 regarding hydro-power sharing in relation to the Kenya-Ethiopia Electric Highway project,⁹³ and the Cross-Border Programme for Sustainable Peace and Socio-Economic Development (SUPSED Agreement) signed in June 2017.⁹⁴

The 2016 power sharing agreement provides a mandate for the Kenya-Ethiopia Electricity Highway Project (or the Eastern Electricity Highway Project), which will see the construction of a 1,000km power line to run from Ethiopia to Kenya to be completed by 2018.⁹⁵ The agreement is built upon an MoU signed in 2006 between the Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation and the Kenya Electricity Transmission Company for the joint development of the project.⁹⁶ The environmental and social impact assessment report was approved in 2012, although it has been criticised as it was conducted after any objection could be made.⁹⁷ Following a World Bank loan of US\$684 million,⁹⁸ construction began in June 2016.⁹⁹ While the 2016 agreement is not yet publicly available, it is reported that the agreement will allow Ethiopia to supply Kenya with 400 megawatts of hydro-power at less than 1 US cent/kwh.¹⁰⁰ The hydro-power source or sources that will supply this transmission line is not officially stated, although the World Bank modified an official project report specifying that power would be sourced “from Ethiopia’s Gilgel Gibe hydropower scheme”,¹⁰¹ changing the reference to the dam in its next report instead to “Ethiopia’s power grid”.¹⁰²

⁹² (“Kenya and Ethiopia sign cross-border agreement,” n.d.); (“Ethiopia, Kenya ink cross-border trade agreement,” n.d.); (“Ethiopia, Kenya Sign Agreement to Build Major Road Linking the Two Countries,” n.d.)

⁹³ (“Ethiopia, Kenya to enhance cooperation on energy sector.,” n.d.)

⁹⁴ (“Ethiopia and Kenya join hands on cross-border initiative to boost sub-regional peace and development,” 2015)

⁹⁵ (“Ethiopia, Kenya to enhance cooperation on energy sector.,” n.d.)

⁹⁶ (“Kenya-Ethiopia Electricity Highway, Kenya,” n.d.)

⁹⁷ (Abbink, 2012)

⁹⁸ (“AFCC2/RI-The Eastern Electricity Highway Project under the First Phase of the Eastern Africa Power Integration Program,” n.d.)

⁹⁹ (“Kenya-Ethiopia Electricity Highway, Kenya,” n.d.)

¹⁰⁰ (“Ethiopia, Kenya to enhance cooperation on energy sector.,” n.d.)

¹⁰¹ (Resettlement Action Plan (RAP) Final Report 2012, n.d.)

¹⁰² (Resettlement Policy Framework Draft Report 2012, n.d.)

Table 62 - Overview of regional legal instruments in the OTB.

Instrument	Status	Key Principles/Aims
1968 African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources, which was revised in 2003. ¹⁰³	Kenya and Ethiopia have signed both the ACCNNR and the Revised ACCNNR. Kenya is the only State to ratify the original ACCNNR, while neither State has ratified the Revised Version. Although the 2003 Convention takes precedence over the original Convention, where there is a relationship between Parties bound by the 2003 Convention and Parties bound by the original 1968 Convention, the original Convention shall apply. ¹⁰⁴	<p>“to adopt the measures to ensure conservation, utilization and development of soil, water, flora and faunal resources in accordance with scientific principles and with due regard to the best interests of the people”.¹⁰⁵ “to adopt the measures to ensure conservation, utilization and development of soil, water, flora and faunal resources in accordance with scientific principles and with due regard to the best interests of the people”.¹⁰⁶</p> <p>The 2003 Convention incorporates the principle of equitable utilization.¹⁰⁷ It also reinforces the need for cooperation in the management of water resources across a varied to sectors relevant to the WEF nexus, including irrigated agriculture and sustainable agro-based industrialization.¹⁰⁸</p>
COMESA 1993 Treaty Establishing a Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa. ¹⁰⁹	Both Kenya and Ethiopia are party to the agreement	<p>“[e]nvironmental protection requirements shall be a component of the Common Market’s policy <i>in all the fields</i> of Common Market activity”.¹¹⁰</p> <p>Also calls on States to foster co-operation in the joint and efficient management and sustainable utilisation of natural resources within the Common Market for the mutual benefit of the member states”, with specific reference to fresh water and forests.¹¹¹</p>
Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD)	Both Kenya and Ethiopia are party to the agreement	<p>Regional integration organization, including various aspects of regional cooperation.</p> <p>Relevant to transboundary water governance, Article 6A establishes States’ commitment to “[m]utual and equitable sharing of benefits accruing from cooperation under this Agreement”, and Article 7 sets out an aim of IGAD to “[i]nitiate and promote programmes and projects for sustainable development of natural resources and environment protection”.</p>

The 2017 SUPSED Agreement is built upon a programme initiated by the World Bank, UNDP, and the IGAD Council of Ministers, which launched in December 2015 through an MoU between Kenya and Ethiopia.¹¹² Its scope covers the northern Marsabit county of Kenya and the southern Borana Zone in Ethiopia, where the OTB is situated, and aims to foster “environmental protection, trade,

¹⁰³ (1968 ACCNNR, n.d.); (2003 ACCNNR (Revised Version), n.d.)

¹⁰⁴ (1968 ACCNNR, n.d.), Article 35.

¹⁰⁵ (1968 ACCNNR, n.d.), Article 2.

¹⁰⁶ (1968 ACCNNR, n.d.), Article 2.

¹⁰⁷ (2003 ACCNNR (Revised Version), n.d.), Article 7(3).

¹⁰⁸ (2003 ACCNNR (Revised Version), n.d.), Article 7(4).

¹⁰⁹ (COMESA Agreement, n.d.)

¹¹⁰ (COMESA Agreement, n.d.), Article 122(6).

¹¹¹ (COMESA Agreement, n.d.), Article 123.

¹¹² (“The European Union Emergency Trust Fund For the Stability and Addressing the Root Causes of Irregular Migration and Displaced Persons in Africa,” n.d.)

development and peaceful coexistence in their border regions.”¹¹³ The SUPSED agreement is not yet available to the public (or the authors), meaning its content cannot be examined. However, it has been said to call for the joint management of the OTB’s natural resources; a significant step toward a cooperative arrangement for the basin.

National legal instruments

A full analysis of relevant national and policy documents relating to water, environmental and other relevant laws and policies in Ethiopia and Kenya is contained in Milestone 57 (Yihdego and Hawkins, 2018). A summary of the main findings is listed below.

Key Points from National Legislation

- The Constitution of both Kenya and Ethiopia recognise the importance of protecting the environment.¹¹⁴
- Kenya implements the principle to prevent pollution to watercourses¹¹⁵, while Ethiopia provides regulation on the control of pollution and standards for discharging pollutants.¹¹⁶
- Ethiopia requires an EIA to be conducted for developments which are likely to cause harm to the environment.¹¹⁷ Kenya also requires an EIA to be conducted and goes further to require that water permits are subject to an EIA.¹¹⁸
- Protection of ecosystems is in place within Kenyan national legislation¹¹⁹, but is only in place in a policy document of Ethiopia.¹²⁰
- The obligation to conduct an EIA can be inferred from legislation in Ethiopia¹²¹, and is explicitly required in Kenyan legislation.¹²²
- Neither the principles of equitable and reasonable utilisation nor the principle of no significant harm are explicitly present in the national legislation of Kenya and Ethiopia. However, legislation in Kenya does provide some broader provisions for equitable sharing of natural resources and of water.¹²³ Equitable and reasonable use is also present within Ethiopia’s 1999 Water policy on ‘Transboundary Waters’.¹²⁴

3.8.2 Indicators of water availability and quality in relation to governance

The indicators for the assessment of the level of legal expectation which is placed upon a country regarding a particular action are those also used for ZRB (section 2.8.2). The level of legal expectation is derived from the strength of legal language and the presence of the principle within the instrument of law or policy. Table 63 provides a summary of the scores from the most relevant international, regional, and basin rules applicable to the OTB States, which represents the basic legal framework for the basin.

¹¹³ (“Ethiopia and Kenya join hands on cross-border initiative to boost sub-regional peace and development,” 2015)

¹¹⁴ 2010 Constitution of Kenya, Article 69. And 1995 Constitution of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (adopted 8 December 1994; In force 21 August 1995), Articles 44 and 92

¹¹⁵ **Kenya:** 2016 Water Act (No. 43 of 2016), Article 58-59, 108, 110, 143

¹¹⁶ **Ethiopia:** 2002 Environmental Pollution Control Proclamation (No. 300 of 2002), Article 6(1)(a) and 16.

¹¹⁷ **Ethiopia:** 2005 Ethiopian Water Resources Management Regulations (No. 115 of 2005), Article 6(3)(e).

¹¹⁸ **Kenya:** 1999 Environmental Management and Co-ordination Act [Cap. 387].

¹¹⁹ **Kenya:** 2006 Environmental Management and Co-ordination (Water Quality) Regulations [Cap. 387], Articles 50-52

¹²⁰ 1997 Environmental Policy of Ethiopia (Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia 1997).

¹²¹ **Ethiopia:** 2002 Environmental Impact Assessment Proclamation (No. 300 of 2002), Article 2(10).

¹²² **Kenya:** 2003 Environmental (Impact Assessment and Audit) Regulations [Cap. 387], Article 44

¹²³ The Constitution of Kenya in Article 174(g) provides for the “equitable sharing of national and local resources throughout Kenya”, while Article 27(j) of the 2016 Water Act sets out the power and function of the basin water resources committee to advise the government on “the equitable water sharing within the basin area through water allocation plans”.

¹²⁴ 1999 Ethiopian Water Resources Management Policy (Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, Ministry of Water Resources 1999).

Table 63 - Scores of legal principles in the OTB.

Instrument:	Principle:	Substantive obligations								Procedural obligations						
		Equitable and reasonable use	Intergenerational equity	Prevention of pollution	No significant harm to states	Protection and preservation of ecosystems	Sustainable development	Sustainable utilization	Cooperation: harmonization and agreements	Precautionary principle	Environmental / social / cultural impact assessment	Transboundary impact assessment	Joint body or COP encouraged or established	Information/ data exchange	Planned measures: notification / consultation	Dispute resolution mechanism
Global	UNWC	3	1	3	3	3	1	2	3	0	1	0	2	3	3	2
	ACCNNR	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
	Revised ACCNNR	2	3	3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	0	3	3	2	3
Regional	COMESA	1	0	2	3	3	1	2	3	0	1	0	3	3	0	3
Basin	IGAD	1	0	0	0	2	1	2	3	0	0	0	3	1	0	2
	Score	7	4	10	9	14	6	7	14	3	5	0	12	11	5	13

Legend:

3 = Strong reference (key/ priority provision with elaboration); 2 = Medium reference (key provision but no elaboration); 1 = Weak reference (only mentioned or in part mentioned); 0 = No reference

WEF Nexus

Water¹²⁵. In the OTB, water supply is a key feature of the basins use. Flooding patterns are also extremely important within the OTB, with indigenous groups placing heavy reliance on seasonal flooding.

Energy¹²⁶. In the OTB, energy has become a source of controversy in recent years, with the production of many hydropower plants.

Food¹²⁷. In the OTB, flood managed agriculture and fisheries are key sources of food security.

Implications of key principles and procedures on WEF-Nexus

As stated with regard to the ZRB, greater analysis of the relationship between key principles and procedures will be provided in the forthcoming Deliverable 4.4¹²⁸ (Models and Principles of Water Governance in the OTB and ZRB, however an example of how a WEF action could relate to the associated legal principles and therefore create a legal expectation, or in some cases (dependant on the status of ratification and/or status of the document from which the principle is derived) a legal obligation, is given below with respect to the OTB.

¹²⁵ See Yihdego and Hawkins, Identification of Water Governance Structures in the Zambezi River Basin: A Water-Energy-Food Nexus Perspective, Milestone 4, September 2017 pg. 32-34, Yihdego and Hawkins, Identification of Water Governance Structures in the Omo-Turkana Basin: A Water-Energy-Food Nexus Perspective, Milestone 57, September 2018, pg. 5-9

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ Ibid.

¹²⁸ DAFNE-Deliverable 4.4. Models and principles of water governance in the Omo and Zambezi river basins.

Table 64 - Implications of key principles and procedures on WEF-Nexus in the OTB.

WEF Related Action	Possible Impact	Applicable Principles	Legal Expectation Created
Hydroelectric Dam (such as Koysha Hydroelectric Dam)	Water quantity, water quality, water level, water flow Impacts on energy, possible impacts on agriculture (food production) and other wider societal implications (displacement etc.)	Substantive Principles: Equitable and Reasonable Use, No Significant Harm Procedural Principles: Obligation to notify and Consult	All factors and circumstances to equitable and reasonable use must be considered (UNWC, Articles 5-6) Notification and process of consultation triggered (UNWC, Articles 12-16)

3.9 SYNTHESIS

3.9.1 Overview of Geo- and time series data

As in the case of the ZRB this report provides the baseline scenario that will form the basis for the reference simulation of the WEF nexus, against which simulation of development pathways will be analysed and compared. The data that form both the drivers of the WEF nexus and the boundary conditions for the simulation –time series, digital thematic data and statistics of demand and use – were described and analysed in the previous sections and are synthesised in section 3.9.2. Table 65 in this section summarises the location on the internal project data repository of the collected data. The data with unrestricted access to the reader are only publicly available data, for which disclosure is not limited by the data owner or provider.

Table 65 - Geo- and time series data and link to Dropbox per chapter for the OTB.

General description	
Shapefile containing the basin boundaries of the OTB	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/mlbpb7wpy2bffxz/AAC-xupWGwojz-E-m8vmwABta?dl=0
DEM (USGS-SRTM-90meters)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/xqnnljrqoenju6e/AACc9wkDEUKfdvh-WoQAqTj84a?dl=0
Dominant soil units of the OTB following the 2nd edition of WRB (IUSS WRB Working Group 2006) (based on the Harmonised Soil Map of Africa (Dewitte et al. 2013; Jones et al. 2015).	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/1ezyy1mk6mhodnl/AACi564hzgaEHehy-IYga7P4ca?dl=0
Land cover (ESA CCI – 300meters resolution, 2015)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/s78wddyei5id0s9/AACyrp1dgodYvJrvts6E2aGUa?dl=0
Climatic zones of the ZRB (adapted from Global Yield Gap Atlas - http://www.yield-gap.org/cz-ted)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/qvo1p3c6ps6314p/AAA6nvSUE5OBJWEa1kTK-6Jna?dl=0
Water Availability	
Station flow data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/3hvkmyzyxtq0qi/AAC6yptxUrfm45MWNLk3oRxBa?dl=0

(Table 65 continued)

Station precipitation data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/dxm07t82zvoena7/AAA9HW_IFhKoDppelTrw5mAMa?dl=0
Station temperature data	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/1jzk2c8lslaph8a/AABMQiMMgmQgpdRs-faFei_aOa?dl=0
Gridded precipitation dataset CMORPH (Xie et al., 2017) [1998-present, 30 min, 8km]	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/n7w6s1zq25nggcc/AABpFntdcO13jLIcTvgI-G0Ha?dl=0
Gridded precipitation dataset CHIRPS (Funk et al., 2014) [1981-present, daily, 5km]	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/bx8787dh8nz5evv/AAC_rtiGld1ZPJaanuLDX9G9a?dl=0
Gridded precipitation dataset TAMSAT (Maidment et al., 2017) [1983-present, daily, 4km]	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/1hjwuscrrng45usd/AAAUa-QoL-uayUEKjboizzY_pa?dl=0
Agriculture, Livestock and Fishery	
HydroSHEDS (Pfaffstetter Level5, standard (Without lakes) subbasin boundaries	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/ln7mn87drv2n7hf/AACiDi-VxS_knb4p7I1mcOvrla?dl=0
Surface area of land used for livestock production	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/ep4i1kvi699w37j/AABtE15j8JQ64onx7zVuyt2_a?dl=0
Surface area of land used for rainfed crop production	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/k9757r28eblsvzz/AABb1N7c8Raxd47RdFGunEALa?dl=0
Georeferenced irrigation schemes and their characteristics (area under irrigation, water source, produced crops), as points and polygons (irrigation perimeters)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/4436apqjbmuaqI/AACFRF-BLiWgX_sa3ITV7zAUba?dl=0
Crop production (in tonnes per year), livestock headcounts, and fish catch and aquaculture (in tonnes per year) per subbasin derived from D3.3	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wfqIm63fvbfey5/AACd-OSBeuVX-AzqehF_cl3Ha?dl=0
Annual food production (from harvested crops, livestock products, fish catch and aquaculture, and total agricultural output) in terms of calories and proteins per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/bv1r8zxivxz0pg9/AABQo3uKOVpZE0JLSp4N3f5za?dl=0
Water requirement for crop and livestock production per subbasin (in cubic hectometres per year)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/48eal1n39p18amo/AABnJvOAxJw27IiLHU94TCzSa?dl=0
Environment	
Database of surface water extent (global level, between 1984 and 2015, 30m resolution) (Pekel et al., 2016)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/c5lrlh7azs6r2t/AABwgP3rO50jpT-niTgWUX2qxa?dl=0
Shapefile of the bi-monthly extent of lake Turkana between 2015 and 2018 (see deliverable D 3.4)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/s1kps8s6rsythfc/AACI7kTb5gBawQCvF9XymodCa?dl=0
Lake level data for lake Turkana from (Butzer, 1971; Hopson, 1982; Källqvist, 1988; Schwatke et al., 2015)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/oh5bbl4gds8unmo/AABbz-lXRdjjrMssgrBiPzga?dl=0

(Table 65 continued)

Accumulated data on species richness and fish habitat requirements developed for deliverable D3.4	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/8enyr76m9w9h6vk/AACcC-FHE0Bp1_vUFN4Gv5nka?dl=0
The data on land cover changes (based on global land cover time series is available from 1992 to 2015 by the ESA CCI project (Li et al., 2017)) presented in deliverable D3.4	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/13qpwp7jt21mhwe/AA-DEYdcDa47hOGEkSz6YK1Fla?dl=0
Demography	
OTB Night Light map	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Daily calorie and protein requirements per country (between 2000 and 2013)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Daily calorie and protein requirements per capita per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/zzg-moyq74vgx63i/AAAivxXgAzx0VyM-QJxINj0Sa?dl=0
Global Food Security Index per country (for 2017)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Global Hunger Index Scores per country (for 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005 and 2015)	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Percentage of population with access to electricity	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Percentage of population with at least basic sanitation	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Total household water use per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Total household energy use per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Urban centres	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of tonnes proteins per year per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/zzg-moyq74vgx63i/AAAivxXgAzx0VyM-QJxINj0Sa?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of Teracalories per year per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/zzg-moyq74vgx63i/AAAivxXgAzx0VyM-QJxINj0Sa?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of g proteins per capita per day per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/zzg-moyq74vgx63i/AAAivxXgAzx0VyM-QJxINj0Sa?dl=0
Food production deficit/surplus in terms of kcal per capita per day per subbasin	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/zzg-moyq74vgx63i/AAAivxXgAzx0VyM-QJxINj0Sa?dl=0
Economy, Industry, Mining	
Water use by Mining and quarrying per country	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0
Water use by total industry per country	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/wbvur4jf0ucair6/AAACYbJrw66-JTAD2D7PPPuLa?dl=0

(Table 65 continued)

Institutional Framework of Water Governance	
Relevant legal material	https://www.dropbox.com/sh/vggtu31rzz2bgnw/AABnOVdBT2SWpl3O3xWSC1lea?dl=0

3.9.2 Narrative synthesis

The transboundary OTB is shared by two countries, Ethiopia and Kenya, and is characterised by a system of rivers all draining into the endorheic Lake Turkana. The major lake perennial inflow (about 80÷90%) comes, however, from the Omo river, entirely located in Ethiopia, while the largest part of Lake Turkana is located in Kenya. The remaining tributaries of Lake Turkana, located in Kenya, provide an intermittent inflow contribution of about 10÷20%.

The Omo river basin is in turn characterised by a dual climate: the northern half of the catchment extends almost completely in Ethiopian territory and is characterised by a humid tropical climate, modulated by elevation and relatively pronounced orography. The lower half is conversely characterised by lower elevations, gentle to flat topography and arid climate. The endorheic lake Turkana, extends for its largest part in Kenya and the basins of some of its southern tributaries extends into Uganda. The climatic contrast between the northern regions of the Omo river and the regions around Lake Turkana determines the strong imbalance of freshwater supply to the lake.

In terms of water availability, the analysis of the limited available data point at the pronounced seasonality of the streamflow, which is thus responsible for the lake level fluctuations as well as the periodic flooding of the lower reaches of the Omo river. In the recent years the construction of hydropower reservoirs contributed to altering the streamflow regime, especially in the lower Omo river. Annual rainfall records prior to 2009 do not show changing spatial or temporal patterns. Between 1998 and 2006 the data available at three discharge measurement stations in the upper reaches of the Omo river show, conversely, a light declining discharge pattern all over the year but most pronounced in the rainy season. Accordingly, the 1998-2006 period water levels in lake Turkana also show a decline, which was reverted to an increase for the year 2007-2016 period, despite this corresponds to the years of construction and commissioning of two major reservoirs. This counterintuitive behaviour and the few data that were available to the project to elaborate the baseline scenario, suggest that the OTB is characterised by a complex response, which depends on natural drivers (climate and hydrological processes) but also on anthropic interference (streamflow regulation) thus highlighting the strong water-energy nexus, in particular with respect to the influence it may have on the variability of the levels of Lake Turkana. Groundwater is also an important source of water at local scale for the communities in the riparian states of OTB but the quantification of its contribution is made impossible by the absence of data usable for the analysis.

OTB's major riparian states, Ethiopia and Kenya, are members of the Eastern Africa Power Pool whereby Ethiopia is intending to expand hydropower production both for domestic consumption (only 10.9% of its population is currently connected to a power grid) and for power export. As of 2016, three hydropower plants of the Gibe cascade were operational in the OTB with a combined installed capacity of 2474 MW. In the Kenyan portion of OTB, the Turkwel hydropower plant is the only one present with a modest installed capacity of 112 MW. For the 2000-2013 period Ethiopia the country-scale production of electricity shows increasing surpluses. The situation is similar in Kenya but absolute numbers are smaller. However, the average production from the existing hydropower systems in the OTB in 2011/2012 show a deficit of 330 GWh y⁻¹, thus suggesting that the local demand following the growth of the region requires an increase of the production to satisfy the observed and planned increase of the demand.

The water demand for irrigated agriculture is very low to non-existing in the Ethiopian highlands (upper OTB) where rainfed agriculture is mostly concentrated. Almost no rainfed agriculture is con-

versely observed in the arid Kenyan regions and in the lower Omo course. Some irrigated agriculture is practiced also in the Ethiopian highlands and along the Turkwel river in Kenya, but most of the relevant water demand comes from the lower Omo region, where extensive commercial irrigation schemes are planned. On both sides of the border between Ethiopia and Kenya almost no agriculture, neither rainfed nor irrigated, is practiced, being this region characterised mainly by the presence of pastoralist communities. The annual water consumption for irrigation purposes, as estimated by all the inventoried irrigation schemes amounts to 117 hm³ for 17,268 hectares. Land used for livestock production spreads relatively uniformly over the entire OTB with the exception of the western part of the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region in Ethiopia and southern part of the Turkana county in Kenya. Direct water consumption by animals kept in livestock production systems spread out over the full OTB-territory is estimated at 260 hm³. Fish catch is also significant and is associated mainly with lake Turkana and with the major rivers (Omo, Kerio, Turkwel) and their tributaries, thus suggesting the importance of considering a water demand associated with keeping the streamflow regime within a range that generate little to no impact to the fish population.

Five major water supplying ecosystems have been identified in addition to four major water-dependent ecosystems (seasonal flooding). The former are located in the upstream reaches of the Omo river system while the latter are located more downstream towards and in the Omo-delta. Because of its endorheic nature, Lake Turkana is obviously the major water dependent ecosystem. Cultural services, such as tourism are presently low because of the underdeveloped relevant infrastructure, but its potential is, conversely high. Provisioning services, particularly fisheries, are considerable and, together with other ecosystem services, are a non-negligible part of the WEF nexus, influencing the present socio-economic OTB systems as well as future development pathways.

The demographic structure in the OTB is characterised by a fragmented fabric with only one city populated by more than 100,000 people, namely the city of Jimma in Ethiopia with about 128.000 inhabitants. The very large majority of the more than 10 million inhabitants of the OTB live in smaller settlements and rural communities spread out over the basin. The highest densities occur in the subbasins in the northern highlands. Correspondingly the present water and electricity demands are relatively modest in absolute terms, being the total annual consumption of water by private households is estimated at 111 hm³ while the energy use is estimated at 136 PJ, but high if compared with similar estimates for the ZRB (see section 2.6). Three of the 9 subbasins (at Pfaffstetter level 5) of the OTB, two of which cover the entire Kenyan portion of the basin, do not produce enough food calories from crops, livestock or fish products to feed the local population. However, two of these three have a surplus in proteins due to the greater importance of livestock compared to crops. The situation is opposite in one of the Ethiopian subbasins: it faces a deficit in proteins while a surplus of calories are produced. The Omo-delta in north Kenya lacks both sufficient calories and proteins. All this points to regional imbalances, which, to some extent, are countered by intra-basin and more distant trade of food products but also shows that a change in the water demand structure has to be expected due to needed (and planned) irrigated agricultural intensification, especially in the lower Omo river regions.

Currently industrial and mining activities are almost absent in OTB so that the corresponding water and energy use is neglectable.

Finally, alike the ZRB case, the transboundary nature of the OTB is highly suitable for legal initiatives that can improve the benefit of sharing water resources and the related services across the entire OTB. In contrast with the ZRB case study the OTB is an emerging case of transboundary management for which little exists with respect to legal agreements between Kenya and Ethiopia directly addressing the governance of water resources of the OTB at the basin level. The highest level of formal cooperation seems to be in relation to supply and distribution of electricity. While this is, in this region, directly related to the water-energy nexus, the relevant implications for a sustainable governance of water resources are not included in the formal agreement signed by the two countries about hydro-power sharing in relation to the Kenya-Ethiopia Electric Highway project. Similarly, the only other formal agreement signed by the two countries aims to foster environmental

protection, trade, development and peaceful coexistence in the border regions between Kenya and Ethiopia, which extends around the Omo delta into Lake Turkana.

Finally, as in the case of the ZRB case study, the substantial lack of available data, in turn due to their non-existence (e.g. missing instrumentation and/or observations), their unavailability (data could not be obtained from the relevant agencies) or their poor quality (e.g. coarse temporal and spatial scales as compared to the characteristic scales of the process, missing observations, etc.), did not allow a proper quantification of the reference management strategy, which follows from the combination of drivers (e.g. climate forcing, water demand, etc.) and basin configuration (e.g. existing infrastructure and their operation). The evidence of the nature of the WEF nexus is, however, sufficiently clear to provide a basis for the analysis of its dynamics through the simulation of the complex interdependence of water availability and use. As in the case of the ZRB case study, a *widespread disconnection of management strategies* that leads to unsustainable water management practices seem to emerge prominently from the analysis of the baseline conditions. This is a call for a *connected representation* of the river basin functioning in the form of a WEF integrated model, as proposed by the DAFNE project and reported in the forthcoming deliverable D3.5.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This report was intended to provide a “snapshot” of the water resources use and management status quo in the two basins investigated by the DAFNE project. Such snapshot, in short, is the basis for understanding how much water is available and how it is used, by which actor, where and according to which strategy, thus defining the so-called “alternative zero”. This will be the reference against which the development pathways selected through the interaction with stakeholders will be compared in other deliverables.

Accordingly, we investigated the availability of water resources throughout the ZRB and OTB under historical climate, how they are used by the different productive sectors and in which socio-economic context, market and regulatory boundary conditions. The relevant analyses were conducted on the best data base we could acquire, given that data are often non-existing, missing or difficult to obtain from the relevant agencies, or provide observations at scale that are coarser than the characteristic scale of the system functioning. Indeed, data acquisition proved to be challenging and provided only part of the information necessary to disentangle the WEF nexus in both ZRB and OTB.

Besides specific sectoral findings, the main elements that emerged from the analysis are that:

- water resources are not necessarily scarce;
- evidence of availability imbalance is present in both case studies, due to both natural factors and sub-optimal management and planning;
- the productive sectors competing for the same resources do not necessarily coordinate their activities in order to maximise the benefit from using the resources while sharing among multiple users;
- the ZRB case study shows a more advanced planning and regulatory structure as compared to the OTB, which, however, does not translate always in efficient monitoring and use of the resource;
- both ZRB and OTB are at risk of over-exploitation of water resources in some regions and under-exploitation in others;
- the uncoordinated use of water resources can exacerbate the imbalance between demand and availability and among sectors;
- future climate and socio-economic drivers have the potential to challenge the present management structure and allocation options of water resources.

While the above list may sound intuitive and not represent an unexpected result, the quantification of how crucial is the resource water for the sustainable further socio-economic development of the nations and communities in the Zambezi River Basin emerged in a very clear way from outlining

the baseline scenario. The finite nature of water resources and their extremely variable in space and time availability have implications on the complex interactions between the natural hydrological cycle and the socio-economic systems, i.e. the WEF nexus. While the changing climate is expected to impose increasing modification of the hydrological cycle, evolving socio-economic development is altering the socio-economic systems thus increasing the competition across sectors and riparian countries for the use of the same resource. These circumstances and the limitations emerged from the effort to achieve an accurate delineation of the WEF nexus from the existing knowledge and available information showed that a proper quantification of the interdependencies between natural resources (in particular water) and productive socio-economic systems can be better (if not only) explored through long-term evidences, which capture the intrinsically variable nature of natural and anthropic systems. This can be conveniently achieved through an integrated (numerical) model representation of river basin functioning and its use to explore development pathways, which cannot be otherwise demonstrated if not running implementation experiments in the real systems on real (and long) temporal scales. The potential of the model-based approach will be further demonstrated in the forthcoming deliverables of WP3 and WP5.

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ANNEXES

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ANNEX I – TECHNICAL SHEETS FOR THE EXISTING HYDROPOWER PLANTS IN THE ZAMBEZI RIVER BASIN

This Annex reports the technical sheets that have been collected for the existing hydropower plants in the Zambezi River Basin. Variables highlighted in red refer to either missing data or data that still needs to be validated by the utility managing the power plants. It must be noticed that the list of hydropower stations here classified is not exhaustive but reflects the availability of information that could be collected from both scientific papers and grey literature (e.g., technical reports) via traditional information channels. Direct information from hydropower companies was, unfortunately, not shared by the time of compilation of this report.

1.1 Kafue Gorge Upper (Zambia)

The first dam on the Kafue River was completed at the Upper Kafue Gorge site in 1972 and is a gravity, earth-rockfill dam (Figure 1). The hydropower station (Kafue Gorge Upper – KGU) at the dam is equipped with six units each with 150 MW installed for a total nameplate capacity of 900 MW, which was upgraded to 990 MW in 2009. The dam is operated by ZESCO and operationally connected with the upstream Itezhi-Tezhi reservoir, even if this latter provides only partial regulation to the KGU (World Bank, 2010).

Figure 1 - Reservoir and gravity, earth-rock filled dam at the Kafue Gorge Upper site. Coordinates: 15°48'30''S 28°25'15''E. Taken by Federica Bertoni, 4th February 2017.

Figure 2 - Radial spillway gate (left) and concrete slide (right) at the Kafue Gorge Upper site. Taken by Federica Bertoni, 4th February 2017.

Table 1 - Plant data for the Kafue Gorge Upper, Zambia.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Zambia		
River	Kafue		
Operator	ZESCO		
Status	HC	Upgraded in 2009 (Energy Regulation Board, 2010)	Cervigni et al. (2015)
Closure	1972	Upgraded in 2009 (Energy Regulation Board, 2010)	Tilmant et al. (2012)
Type	Reservoir		
Operating Targets	Hydropower Production		
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	151,000		Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	7.64	Averaged from 1982 to 2010	Nyatsanza et al. (2015)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	1,000-1,200	Average altitude	African Development Bank Group (2013)
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	800 to 1,000		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Reservoir Length [km]	376		Mumba et al. (2005)
Crest Elevation [m asl]	981.5		Beilfuss (2012)
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	50		Mumba et al. (2005)
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm]	n.a.		
Live Storage [km ³]	0.78		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Dead Storage [km ³]	0.2		Beilfuss (2012)
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	975.4	972.3 m according to Cervigni et al. (2015)	Tilmant et al. (2012)
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	977		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	975.3	976.6 m from December to March	Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	0.1		Nyatsanza et al. (2015)
Level-Storage Curve	Available		World Bank (2010)
Level-Surface Curve	Available		World Bank (2010)

(Table 1 continued)

DAM DATA			
Dam Type	Gravity, earth-rock filled		Beilfuss (2012)
Number of Spillways	3		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Type of Spillways	Radial gates		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	4250		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
Installed Capacity [MW]	900	Upgraded to 990 MW in 2009 (Energy Regulation Board, 2010)	World Bank (2010)
Number of Turbines	6		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	152.5	Upgraded to 165 MW in 2009 (Energy Regulation Board, 2010)	Tilmant et al. (2012)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	42		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	290		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	397		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.		
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	89		World Bank (2010)
KEN	n.a.		

(Table 1 continued)

Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	n.a.		
Intake Rating Curve	Available		Tesini (2010)
Tailwater Rating Curve	Available		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Rule Curve	Available		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.		
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	0		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62		Cervigni et al. (2015)
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

Table 2 - Available time series for the Kafue Gorge Upper, Zambia.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	01/10/1973	30/09/2010	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	01/02/1972	30/09/2017	daily	ZESCO
Total Release [m ³ /s]	29/02/1972	30/09/2017	daily	ZESCO
Turbined Flow [m ³ /s]	29/02/1972	30/09/2017	daily	ZESCO
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	29/02/1972	30/09/2017	daily	ZESCO
Hydropower Production [MWh]	01/10/1987	30/09/2017	daily	ZESCO
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	January	December	Monthly (cyclostationary)	Gandolfi et al. (1997)
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 3 - Kafue Gorge Upper dam feature elevations (panel a) and hydropower plant curves (panel b,c,d,e,f). In particular, Panel a shows the existence of 3 radial gate spillways, whose dimensions are 14 x 12 m.

1.2 Victoria Falls (Zambia)

The Victoria Falls hydropower station is located in the third gorge below the UNESCO world heritage site of the Victoria Falls, on the Zambezi River. It consists of three run-of-the-river power plants with a total nameplate capacity of 108 MW: (i) Plant A, the oldest, was commissioned in 1937 and originally presented a 2 MW installed capacity, subsequently expanded up to 8 MW in 1956; (ii) Plant B was commissioned in 1968 with an installed capacity of 60 MW; (iii) Plant C was commissioned in 1972 and has an installed capacity of 40 MW. These three power stations are fed by a left-bank diversion at the level of the falls and do not run year round, since power generation is curtailed during low flows to maintain discharge at the falls (The World Bank, 2010). For instance, ZESCO, the operator of the Victoria Falls plant, is committed at low flow periods (below 400 m³/s) to reduce capacity from 108 MW to 35-45 MW. This did not happen in 2009-2010 because the Zambian power requirements have been such that ZESCO had to renege on this (Chapman, 2011).

Figure 4 - The Victoria Falls hydropower stations (Chapman, 2011).

Figure 5 - Close up of the Victoria Falls hydropower stations (Geopractica, 2015).

Table 3 - Plant data for the Victoria Falls, Zambia.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Zambia		
River	Zambezi		
Operator	ZESCO		
Status	HC		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Closure	1972	Commissioning year of the last plant, namely plant C	The World Bank (2010)
Type	Run-of-the-river		
Operating Targets	Hydropower production		Chapman (2011)

(Table 3 continued)

CATCHMENT DATA					
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	507,200				Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	33.74				Zambezi River Authority (2015)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	975			Average altitude going from 650 m asl in the north to 1300 m asl in the south	Balon et al. (2012)
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS					
	A	B	C		
Installed Capacity [MW]	8	60	40		The World Bank (2010)
Number of Turbines	2 + 3	6	4	All Francis turbines (Chapman, 2011)	The World Bank (2010)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	1 + 2	10	10		
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	1.2	12	12	It refers to the total max discharge [m ³ /s]	Jonker Klunne (2013)
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	100	100	100		Jonker Klunne (2013)
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
KEN	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	722.5			Averaged data between 2007-2010	Energy Regulation Board (2010)
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Rule Curve	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.		
COSTS					
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	0				Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35				Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62				Cervigni et al. (2015)
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS					
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.				
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.				
Other Constraints	n.a.				

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

Table 4 - Available time series for the Victoria Falls, Zambia.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	01/10/1958	05/02/2010	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

1.3 Itezhi-Tezhi (Zambia)

The Itezhi-Tezhi (ITT) dam was built 270 km upstream the Kafue Gorge Upper (KGU) dam and completed in 1978. The storage capacity of the KGU reservoir was insufficient and the geography of the Kafue Flats required the construction of a second gravity, earth-rockfill dam upstream, in order to ensure a steady supply of river water to maintain maximum power generation throughout the year at the KGU site (Godet et al., 2014).

In February 2016, a 120 MW power station was added to the existing Itezhi-Tezhi dam, due to an acute power deficit in the late 2000s. It consists of an underground powerhouse housing of two 60 MW Kaplan units (The World Bank, 2010). Both Tata Power (India's largest integrated power company) and ZESCO own the ITT hydropower plant on a 50:50 basis, even if the latter is the only off-taker of power (Lusaka Times, 2016b).

Figure 6 - Itezhi-Tezhi dam and hydropower plant. Source: Lusaka Times, 2016a.

Table 5 - Plant data for Itezhi-Tezhi, Zambia.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Zambia		
River	Kafue		
Operator	ZESCO		
Status	HC	Power plant added and commissioned in 2016 (Cervigni et al., 2015)	Cervigni et al. (2015)

(Table 5 continued)

Closure	1978	Power plant added and commissioned in 2016 (Cervigni et al., 2015)	Godet et al. (2014)
Type	Reservoir		
Operating Targets	Regulation of Kafue Gorge Upper		The World Bank (2010)
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	105,600		Milln (2015)
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	9.4	7.698 according to Nyatsanza et al. (2015) (averaged from 1982 to 2010)	Tilmant et al. (2012)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	1,000-1,200	Average altitude	African Development Bank Group (2013)
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	392		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Reservoir Length [km]	1.8		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Crest Elevation [m asl]	1,035		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	62		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/year]	780		Beilfuss (2012)
Live Storage [km ³]	4.9		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Dead Storage [km ³]	0.7		The World Bank (2010)
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	1,006		The World Bank (2010)
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	1,030.5		The World Bank (2010)
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	1,026.8		The World Bank (2010)
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	0.5		Nyatsanza et al. (2015)
Level-Storage Curve	Available		The World Bank (2010)
Level-Surface Curve	Available		The World Bank (2010)
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	Gravity, earth-rock filled		Beilfuss (2012)
Number of Spillways	1		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Type of Spillways	Radial gated chute		Tilmant et al. (2012)

(Table 5 continued)

Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	1,018.7		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	4200		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Number of Emergency Spillways	1		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Type of Emergency Spillways	Fuseplug		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	1,027.07		HARZA (1999)
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	23.65		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Spillway Rating Curve	Available		HARZA (1999)
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
Installed Capacity [MW]	120		The World Bank (2010)
Number of Turbines	2		The World Bank (2010)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	60		The World Bank (2010)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.		
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.		
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	89		The World Bank (2010)
KEN	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	n.a.		
Intake Rating Curve	Available	Estimated after the installation of the 2x60 MW turbines at the dam site	Tesini (2010)
Tailwater Rating Curve	Available	Estimated after the installation of the 2x60 MW turbines at the dam site	The World Bank (2010)
Rule Curve	Available	Prior to the installation of the 2x60 MW turbines at the dam site	Cervigni et al. (2015)

(Table 5 continued)

Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.		
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	2,232.6		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62		Cervigni et al. (2015)
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	40	All year round: 25 m ³ /s for environmental concerns and 15 m ³ /s for water abstractions downstream of the flats to provide drinking water for Lusaka and Mazabuka as well as other usages	The World Bank (2010)
	315	In March only	
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

Table 6 - Available time series for Itezhi-Tezhi, Zambia.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	01/10/1973	30/09/2010	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Level (or Storage) ^a [m] (or [km ³])	01/10/1977	30/09/2010	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Total Release [m ³ /s]	01/01/1986	30/09/2010	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Turbined Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [MWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	January	December	Monthly (cyclostationary)	Gandolfi et al. (1997)
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 7 - Itezhi-tezhi dam feature elevations (panel a) and hydropower plant curves (panel b,c,d,e,f,g,h). In particular, Panel a shows the existence of 1 radial gate spillway and 2 penstocks, whose dimensions are 6 m diameter and 70 m length each.

1.4 Kariba (Zambia/Zimbabwe)

The Kariba Dam was constructed across the Zambezi River between 1956 and 1959 and officially commissioned in 1960. Being the second largest man-made reservoir in Africa after the Lake Volta, it is a double curvature concrete arc dam that creates Lake Kariba. The Kariba Dam provides storage for two hydropower plants, namely the North Bank Station in Zambia operated by ZESCO and the South Bank Station in Zimbabwe operated by the Zimbabwe Power Corporation (ZPC) (Darbourn, 2015; The World Bank, 2010). The installed capacity of the former was upgraded from 720 MW up to 1,080 MW in 2013, whereas the latter is being enlarged from 750 MW up to 1,050 MW by 2018 (Darbourn, 2015; Cervigni et al., 2015).

Figure 8 - The Kariba dam as seen from Zimbabwe (Hanlon, 2016).

Table 7 - Plant data for Kariba, Zambia/Zimbabwe.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Zambia/Zimbabwe		
River	Zambezi		
Operator	ZESCO/ZPC/ZRA		
Status	HC	North Bank upgraded in 2013 – South Bank extension under construction (Darbourn, 2015)	Cervigni et al. (2015)
Closure	1960	North Bank upgraded in 2013 – South Bank extension under construction (Darbourn, 2015)	Darbourn (2015)
Type	Reservoir		
Operating Targets	Hydropower Production	Secondary flood control function according to Beilfuss (2012)	Nyatsanza et al. (2015)
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	663,000	687,535 km ² according to Beilfuss (2012)	Darbourn (2015)
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	40.24	Data from 1907-2000 Nyatsanza et al. (2015) report 32.14 km ³ /yr, averaging data from 1982-2010	Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	975	Average altitude going from 650 m asl in the north to 1300 m asl in the south	Balon et al. (2012)
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	5,577		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Reservoir Length [km]	280		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Crest Elevation [m asl]	489.50		ERM (2014a)
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	97		Tilmant et al. (2012)

(Table 7 continued)

Average Depth [m]	29		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/yr]	>2,000		Beilfuss (2012)
Live Storage [km ³]	64.7		Nyatsanza et al. (2015)
Dead Storage [km ³]	116		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	475.5		The World Bank (2010)
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	488.5		The World Bank (2010)
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	485		Balon et al. (2012)
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	1.4		Beilfuss (2012)
Mean Residence Time [yr]	3.3		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Level-Storage Curve	Available		The World Bank (2010)
Level-Surface Curve	Available		The World Bank (2010)
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	Double curvature concrete arc		Darbourn (2015)
Number of Spillways	6	No more than 3 spillway gates can be fully opened at the same time to avoid retrogressive erosion of the plunge pool (Tumbare, 2010)	Sanyanga (2012)
Type of Spillways	Sluices equipped with downstream gates		ERM (2014a)
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	9500		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	Available		The World Bank (2010)
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		

(Table 7 continued)

Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.				
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.				
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS					
	North^a	South^b	North^a	South^b	
Installed Capacity [MW]	1,080	750		To be enlarged up to 1,050 MW by 2018	Cervigni et al. (2015)
Number of Turbines	6	6	4 old and 2 newly commissioned in 2013	2 new turbines to be commissioned by 2018	Beilfuss (2012)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	180	125		150 MW for each of the new turbines	ERM (2014a)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	200	140	9,515 in total according to Beilfuss (2012)		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.			
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.			
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	108	110			Tilmant et al. (2012)
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.	n.a.			
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	360	360			Nyatsanza et al. (2015)
Turbine Efficiency [%]	89	89			The World Bank (2010)
KEN	n.a.	n.a.			
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	n.a.	n.a.			
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.				
Tailwater Rating Curve	Available				Cervigni et al. (2015)
Rule Curve	Available				Cervigni et al. (2015)
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.	n.a.			
COSTS					
	North^a	South^b	North^a	South^b	
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	1,339.6	1,333.3	It refers to the extension commissioned in 2013	It refers to the extension under construction	Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35	9.35			Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62	1.62			Cervigni et al. (2015)

(Table 7 continued)

OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

^a=Existing hydropower plant already upgraded (HC)

^b=Existing hydropower plant being upgraded and completed by 2018 (HC+CON)

Table 8 - Available time series for Kariba, Zambia/Zimbabwe.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	01/10/1958	05/02/2010	daily	<i>ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)</i>
Reservoir Level (or Storage) ^a [m] (or [km ³])	01/10/1960	30/09/2007	daily	<i>ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)</i>
Total Release [m ³ /s]	10/1961	09/2009	monthly	<i>ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)</i>
Turbined Flow [m ³ /s]	01/10/2007	30/09/2009	daily	<i>ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)</i>
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [MWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	January	December	Monthly (cyclostationary)	<i>Gandolfi et al. (1997)</i>
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 9 - Kariba dam feature elevations (panel a) and hydropower plant curves (panel b,c,d,e,f).

1.5 Cahora Bassa (Mozambique)

The construction of the Cahora Bassa Dam (CB) started in the Cahora-Bassa Gorge in the Middle Zambezi (i.e., Mozambique) in 1969 and ended in 1974. With its 63 km³ volume, it is the twelfth largest reservoir in the world (Tilmant, 2012). The Cahora Bassa is a concrete arch dam operated by HCB (Hidroelectrica de Cahora Bassa) for hydropower production, which dramatically altered the flow regime of the Zambezi River (Beilfuss et al., 2001). The power produced is mainly exported to South Africa. The Cahora Bassa North Bank project aims at upgrading the existing hydropower plant through the construction of a new underground powerhouse on the north bank of the Zambezi River, to be commissioned by 2017 (The World Bank, 2010).

Figure 10 - The Cahora Bassa Dam (Isaacman et al., 2013).

Table 9 - Plant data for Cahora Bassa, Mozambique.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Mozambique		
River	Zambezi		
Operator	HCB		
Status	HC	CB North Bank extension under construction (Ministry of Energy, 2012)	Cervigni et al. (2015)
Closure	1974	CB North Bank extension under construction (Ministry of Energy, 2012)	Tilmant et al. (2012)
Type	Reservoir		
Operating Targets	Hydropower Production	Secondary flood control function according to Beilfuss (2012)	Beilfuss et al. (2001)
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	1,050,000		Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	78.65	54.63 km ³ according to Nyatsanza et al. (2015)	Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	800	Average altitude	SADC (2007)
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	2,675		The World Bank (2010)
Reservoir Length [km]	250		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Crest Elevation [m asl]	331		Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	163	171 m according to Tilmant et al. (2012)	Beilfuss et al. (2001)
Average Depth [m]	26		Tilmant et al. (2012)
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/yr]	2,200		Beilfuss et al. (2001)

(Table 9 continued)

Live Storage [km ³]	51.7	63 km ³ according to Tilmant et al. (2012)		Beilfuss et al. (2001)		
Dead Storage [km ³]	12.5			Beilfuss et al. (2001)		
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	295			The World Bank (2010)		
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	326			The World Bank (2010)		
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	326			IIASA (1988)		
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	0.69			Beilfuss (2012)		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	0.7			Nyatsanza et al. (2015)		
Level-Storage Curve	Available			The World Bank (2010)		
Level-Surface Curve	Available			The World Bank (2010)		
DAM DATA						
Dam Type	Concrete arch			Beilfuss et al. (2001)		
Number of Spillways	8 + 1 crest gate			Beilfuss (2012)		
Type of Spillways	8 sluice gates + 1 single weir gate			IIASA (1988) Beilfuss et al. (2001)		
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	8 gates: 231 1 crest gate: 331			Beilfuss et al. (2001)		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	8 gates: 1700 1 crest gate: 349			IIASA (1988)		
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.					
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.					
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.					
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.					
Spillway Rating Curve	Available			The World Bank (2010)		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.					
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.					
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.					
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.					
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.					
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.					
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.					
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS						
	CB^a	CB Norte^b	CB^a	CB Norte^b	CB^a	CB Norte^b
Installed Capacity [MW]	2,075	1,250			Cervigni et al. (2015)	Nippon KOEI UK (2012)
Number of Turbines	5	3	4 operational + 1 standby (IIASA, 1988)		Tilmant et al. (2012)	Nippon KOEI UK (2012)

(Table 9 continued)

Max Power per Turbine [MW]	415	415			Tilmant et al. (2012)	Nippon KOEI UK (2012)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	452	452			Tilmant et al. (2012)	Nippon KOEI UK (2012)
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.				
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	2,260	n.a.			The World Bank (2010)	
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	128	n.a.			Tilmant et al. (2012)	
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.	n.a.				
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	200	n.a.			Nyatsanza et al. (2015)	
Turbine Efficiency [%]	89	89			The World Bank (2010)	
KEN	n.a.	n.a.				
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	n.a.	n.a.				
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.	n.a.				
Tailwater Rating Curve	Available	n.a.			The World Bank (2010)	
Rule Curve	Available	n.a.			The World Bank (2010)	
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.	n.a.				
COSTS						
	CB^a	CB Norte^b	CB^a	CB Norte^b		
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	0	972			Cervigni et al. (2015)	
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35	9.35			Cervigni et al. (2015)	
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62	1.62			Cervigni et al. (2015)	
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS						
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.					
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.					
Other Constraints	n.a.					

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

^a=Existing hydropower plant (HC) – Cahora Bassa

^b= Existing hydropower plant being upgraded and completed by 2017 (HC+CON) – Cahora Bassa North Bank Project

Table 10 - Available time series for Cahora Bassa, Mozambique.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	21/10/1948	17/08/2006	21/10/1948	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Level (or Storage) ^a [m] (or [km ³])	01/07/1975	11/12/2007	01/07/1975	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Total Release [m ³ /s]	01/10/1994	31/05/2008	01/10/1994	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)

(Table 10 continued)

Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	01/10/1994	31/05/2008	01/10/1994	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [MWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	January	December	January	Gandolfi et al. (1997)
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 11 - Cahora Bassa dam feature elevations (panel a) and hydropower plant curves (panel b,c,d,e,f). In particular, Panel a shows the existence of 8 spillways, whose dimensions are 7.8 x 6 m.

1.6 Tedzani (Malawi)

The Tedzani hydropower development is located on the Shire river, 7 km downstream of Nkula power stations. It comprises of three powerhouses: Tedzani I (2 x 10 MW machines), Tedzani II (2 x 10 MW machines) and Tedzani III (2 x 26.5 MW machines), for a total nameplate capacity of 93 MW. The latter power plant is the most recent one and was fully commissioned in 1995, whereas the former and the second one became operational in 1973 and 1977 respectively (ESCOM, 2015). In December 2001, intake structures at Tedzani I & II power stations were completely devastated due to the weeds that had accumulated at the intake screens, leading to the collapse of these latter (Kapute Mzuza et al., 2015). The complete refurbishment of Tedzani I & II was completed in 2008 (Kaunda et al., 2013). ESCOM operates the Tedzani hydropower station (The World Bank, 2010).

Figure 12 - Damaged coarse screens at the Tedzani Hydropower station (Kaunda et al., 2013).

Table 11 - Plant data for Tedzani, Malawi.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Malawi		
River	Shire		
Operator	ESCOM		
Status	HC		The World Bank (2010)
Closure	1995	Tedzani I & II have undergone refurbishment from 2001 to 2008 (Kaunda et al., 2013)	ESCOM (2015B)
Type	Pondage		
Operating Targets	Hydropower production		Beilfuss (2012)
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	n.a.		
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	13.65		Matos et al. (2015)

(Table 11 continued)

Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	n.a.		
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	0.8	km ²	The World Bank (2010)
Reservoir Length [km]	n.a.		
Crest Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	n.a.		
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/yr]	n.a.		
Live Storage [km ³]	n.a.		
Dead Storage [km ³]	n.a.		
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	n.a.		
Level-Storage Curve	n.a.		
Level-Surface Curve	n.a.		
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	n.a.		
Number of Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Spillways	n.a.		
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		

(Table 11 continued)

Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
	I+II	III	
Installed Capacity [MW]	40	53	ESCOM (2015B)
Number of Turbines	4	2	ESCOM (2015B)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	10	26.5	ESCOM (2015B)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	120	156	The World Bank (2010)
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.	
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.	
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.	n.a.	
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	39.5	38	The World Bank (2010)
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.	n.a.	
Turbine Efficiency [%]	86	86	The World Bank (2010)
KEN	n.a.	n.a.	
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	211	291	Tumbare (2010)
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.		
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.		
Rule Curve	n.a.		
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.	n.a.	
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	0		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35		Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62		Cervigni et al. (2015)
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

Table 12 - Available time series for Tedzani, Malawi.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	10/01/1976	21/01/2005	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	n.a.	n.a.		
Total Release [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		

(Table 12 continued)

Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 13 - Tedzani dam feature elevations.

1.7 Nkula Falls - Malawi

The Nkula Falls hydropower station commissioned in 1996 is located on the Shire River, about 70 km downstream of the Liwonde Barrage. It is a pondage hydropower plant and consists of two powerhouses, namely Nkula A and Nkula B, for a total nameplate capacity of 124 MW (The World Bank, 2010). The former presents a flared concrete intake in the west bank of the river through which water enters the penstock tunnel, whereas the latter has a separate penstock. The Nkula Falls hydroelectric station is operated by ESCOM and together with Kapichira and Tedzani, it generates 95% of the electrical energy used in Malawi (ICF International, 2010).

Figure 14 - Water intake dam at Nkula Falls (Kaputa Mzuza et al., 2015).

Figure 15 - Two water intake structures for Nkula A (ICF International, 2010).

Table 13 - Plant data for Nkula Falls, Malawi.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Malawi		
River	Shire		
Operator	ESCOM		
Status	HC		The World Bank (2010)
Closure	1996		The World Bank (2010)
Type	Pondage		
Operating Targets	Hydropower production		ICF International (2010)
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	n.a.		

(Table 13 continued)

Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	13.65		Matos et al. (2015)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	n.a.		
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	0.4	km ²	The World Bank (2010)
Reservoir Length [km]	n.a.		
Crest Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	n.a.		
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/yr]	n.a.		
Live Storage [km ³]	n.a.		
Dead Storage [km ³]	n.a.		
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	n.a.		
Level-Storage Curve	n.a.		
Level-Surface Curve	n.a.		
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	n.a.		
Number of Spillways	4	For Nkula B only	ICF International (2010)
Type of Spillways	n.a.		
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		

(Table 13 continued)

Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.			
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS				
	A	B		
Installed Capacity [MW]	24	100		The World Bank (2010)
Number of Turbines	3	5	Francis turbines	ICF International (2010)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	8	20		ICF International (2010)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	69	210	Total discharge from all the turbines	ICF International (2010)
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.	n.a.		
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	53.7	58.5		The World Bank (2010)
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	86	86		The World Bank (2010)
KEN	n.a.	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	n.a.	n.a.		
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.			
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.			
Rule Curve	n.a.			
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.	n.a.		
COSTS				
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	0			Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35			Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62			Cervigni et al. (2015)
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS				
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.			
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.			
Other Constraints	n.a.			

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

Table 14 - Available time series for Nkula Falls - Malawi.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	10/01/1976	21/01/2005	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	n.a.	n.a.		

(Table 14 continued)

Total Release [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 16 - Nkula Falls dam feature elevations.

1.8 Kapichira (Malawi)

The Kapichira hydroelectric power plant is located at the Kapichira falls, formerly known as the Livingstone Falls, on the left bank of the Shire river in the southern part of Malawi, 70 km south of Blantyre (Salini Impregilo, 2013). The power station, which is part of the “Malawi Power V” project, consists of an earth and rock embankment and an open powerhouse equipped with four 33 MW Francis turbines. The commissioning of these latter has been divided into two phases: Phase I saw the construction of the first two 64.8 MW units in 2000, whereas Phase II experienced the commissioning of the last two in 2013 (ESCOM, 2015). ESCOM operates the Kapichira hydroelectric plant (The World Bank, 2010).

Figure 17 - The Kapichira hydroelectric power plant (Salini Impregilo, 2013).

Table 15 - Plant data for Kapichara, Malawi.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Malawi		
River	Shire		
Operator	ESCOM		
Status	HC		The World Bank (2010)
Closure	2000	The first two units have been commissioned in 2000, the other two in 2013 (ESCOM, 2015)	Salini Impregilo (2013)
Type	Pondage		
Operating Targets	Hydropower production		Beilfuss (2012)
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	n.a.		
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	20		Matos et al. (2015)
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	n.a.		
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	2	km ²	The World Bank (2010)
Reservoir Length [km]	0.83		Salini Impregilo (2013)
Crest Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	30		Salini Impregilo (2013)
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/yr]	n.a.		
Live Storage [km ³]	n.a.		

(Table 15 continued)

Dead Storage [km ³]	n.a.		
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	n.a.		
Level-Storage Curve	n.a.		
Level-Surface Curve	n.a.		
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	Earth and rock embankment		Salini Impregilo (2013)
Number of Spillways	1		Salini Impregilo (2013)
Type of Spillways	Concrete spillway with five openings controlled by sluice gates		Salini Impregilo (2013)
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	8750		Salini Impregilo (2013)
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
	I	II	
Installed Capacity [MW]	64.8	64.8	ESCOM (2015A)
Number of Turbines	2	2	Francis turbines Salini Impregilo (2013)
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	64.8	64.8	ESCOM (2015A)
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	67	67	The World Bank (2010)

(Table 14 continued)

Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	58.04	58.04		The World Bank (2010)
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	55.33	55.33		The World Bank (2010)
Turbine Outlet Elevation [masl]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	88	88		The World Bank (2010)
KEN	n.a.	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	n.a.	n.a.		
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.			
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.			
Rule Curve	n.a.			
Turbines Efficiency – Releases Curve	n.a.	n.a.		
COSTS				
Capital Cost [USD/kW]	0			Cervigni et al. (2015)
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	9.35			Cervigni et al. (2015)
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	1.62			Cervigni et al. (2015)
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS				
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.			
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.			
Other Constraints	n.a.			

CON=Under Construction; HC=Historic Capacity (i.e. Existing); PLN=Planned Capacity

Table 16 – Available time series for Kapichara, Malawi.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	01/11/1985	31/10/1986	daily	ADAPT Database (Matos et al., 2015)
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	n.a.	n.a.		
Total Release [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		

(Table 16 continued)

Evaporation [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

Figure 18 – Kapichira dam feature elevations. In particular, it can be observed the existence of 5 spillways and 1 penstock, whose dimensions are 15.24 x 13.50 m and 7.80 m diameter/77m length respectively

ANNEX II TECHNICAL SHEETS FOR THE EXISTING HYDROPOWER PLANTS IN THE OMO-TURKANA BASIN

There are currently four hydropower plants in the Omo-Turkana Basin, i.e. the Gibe I dam, the Gibe II dam, the Gibe III dam, and the Turkwel dam. The technical sheets that have been collected for them are summarized. Variables highlighted in red refer to either missing data or data that still needs to be validated by the utility managing the power plants.

2.1 Gibe I dam

Gibe I dam is a rockfill dam and hydropower plant of 184 MW. Its construction started in 1986 and was completed in 2004 following an interruption in the early 90's, and has been carried out by several construction companies, including Salini-Necso for the dam, basing on the design by ENEL-ELC-SP (Pietrangeli and Pallavicini, 2007). The dam is located on the Gilgel Gibe river between the cities of Asendabo and Deneba, and creates an artificial reservoir regulating the river flow (Figure 20). Until 2007, Gibe I was the largest power plant in Ethiopia (Pietrangeli and Pallavicini, 2007).

Gibe I is the first of a two power plants-hydroelectric scheme named the Gilgel Gibe system, including Gibe I and Gibe II, the latter located on the Omo river. Continuous environmental flow of $1.3 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ is guaranteed on the Gilgel Gibe river downstream of Gibe I, together with the entire runoff of the residual catchment area between the two plants, which is about 79 km^2 , negligible if compared with catchment of Gibe I of 4225 km^2 (Pietrangeli and Pallavicini, 2007).

Figure 19 – Satellite view of Gibe I reservoir.

Figure 20 – Aerial photo of Gibe I reservoir.

Table 17 – Plant data for the Gibe I dam, Ethiopia.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Ethiopia		Pietrangeli, 2007
River	Gilgel Gibe		Pietrangeli, 2007
Operator	EEPCo		Pietrangeli, 2007
Status	in Operation		
Closure	-		
Type	Reservoir		Pietrangeli, 2007
Operating Targets	Hydropower		Pietrangeli, 2007
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	4225		Pietrangeli, 2007
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	50		Pietrangeli, 2007
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	n.a.		
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	60		Pietrangeli, 2007
Reservoir Length [km]	n.a.		
Crest Elevation [m asl]	1675		Pietrangeli, 2007
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	40		Pietrangeli, 2007
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/year]	0,87		EELPA, 1997
Live Storage [km ³]	657		Pietrangeli, 2007
Dead Storage [km ³]	182		Pietrangeli, 2007
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	1653		Pietrangeli, 2007
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	1671		Pietrangeli, 2007
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	1665		Pietrangeli, 2007
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	n.a.		
Level-Storage Curve	available		EELPA, 1997
Level-Surface Curve	available		EELPA, 1997
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	rockfill dam with impervious bituminous upstream facing		Pietrangeli, 2007
Number of Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Spillways	Gated Open Chute Spillway		Pietrangeli, 2007
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	1,665		
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	2,570		
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		

(Table 17 continued)

Spillway Rating Curve	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
Installed Capacity [MW]	184		Pietrangeli, 2007
Number of Turbines	3		Pietrangeli, 2007
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	~60		Pietrangeli, 2007
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	34		Pietrangeli, 2007
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	240/232.3		CESI, 2004
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	207,3		
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	n.a.		
KEN	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	722		Pietrangeli, 2007
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.		
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.		
Rule Curve	available		
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.		
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD]	n.a.		
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	n.a.		
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	n.a.		
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	1.3	Minimum Environmental flow	Pietrangeli, 2007
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

Table 18 - Available time series for the Gibe I dam, Ethiopia.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	2004	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	2004	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Total Release [m ³ /s]	2004	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations

(Table 18 continued)

Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	2004	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	2004	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

*Note: the listed time series were simulated via Topkapi-ETH model. No observed time series is available for the reservoir.

Figure 21 - Gibe I dam feature elevations (panel a) and hydropower plant curves (panel b,c,d,e).

2.2 Gibe II Power Plant

Figure 22 - Satellite view of Gibe II power plant and tunnel site.

Figure 23 - Gibe II power plant (ATB Riva Calzoni, 2018).

The Gibe II hydro-electric plant is part of a two power plants-hydroelectric scheme named the Gilgel Gibe system designed to exploit the water resources of the Gibe - Omo basin for energy production purposes. Gibe II has been conceived as a downstream completion of the Gibe I plant, and

it uses the same water accumulation basin and does not require the creation of another large size lake (Figure 22, **Error! Reference source not found.**). Gibe II exploits the large geodetical head of 505 m existing between the Gilgel Gibe river and the Omo river by making use of a 26 km long tunnel (7 m diameter) constructed to trespass the Fofa mountain, which makes use of the water regulated by the Gilgel Gibe I hydroelectric project (CESI, 2004). The tunnel bypasses the approximately 100 km of gorges that constitute the natural course of the confluence of the two rivers (Balbo et al., 2012).

In 2004, EEPCo awarded the 480 MW Gilgel Gibe II contract to an Italian company, Salini, commissioning the completion by 2007. No geological analysis has been performed prior the tunnel construction started, and problematic geological conditions were encountered resulting in unexpected costs and delay. Gibe II power station was inaugurated on January 14, 2010. Almost two weeks after inauguration, a portion of the head race tunnel collapsed causing the station to shut down until repairs were complete on December 26, 2010 (International Rivers Africa, 2015).

Table 19 - Plant characteristics of the Gibe II dam, Ethiopia.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Ethiopia		CESI, 2009
River	Gilgel Gibe		CESI, 2009
Operator	EEPCo		CESI, 2009
Status	in Operation		Moukala, 2015
Closure	-		
Type	Hydraulic Tunnel		CESI, 2009
Operating Targets	Hydropower		CESI, 2009
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	4,304		CESI, 2009
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	50		CESI, 2009
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	n.a.		
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
Installed Capacity [MW]	420		Pietrangeli, 2007
Number of Turbines	4		Pietrangeli, 2007
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	107		Reiner Mack, 2006
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	25,4		Pietrangeli, 2007
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	24,7		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	505		CESI,2004
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	470		CESI,2004
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	n.a.		
KEN	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	1,625		Pietrangeli, 2007
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.		
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.		
Rule Curve	available		Pietrangeli, 2007

(Table 19 continued)

Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.		
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD]	n.a.		
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	n.a.		
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	n.a.		
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]			
Level Constraints [m]			
Other Constraints			

Table 20 - Available time series for the Gibe II dam, Ethiopia.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Turbined Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		

2.3 Gibe III Dam

Gibe III dam is located on the Omo River around 150 km downstream of the Gibe II outlet and 600 km upstream from lake Turkana. Near the dam, the area is characterized by a large plateau with a long and relatively narrow canyon through which the Omo river flows. The 150-km long reservoir of Gibe III flooded the whole canyon from the dam upstream to the Omo River and retains about 14.7 billion m³ of water at maximum capacity (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Gibe III is a 243 m eters high roller compacted gravity dam and is the tallest dam in Africa with an electrical output of 1870 MW/year (Figure 25). The dam was commissioned by the Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation (EPCO), with the intent of significantly increasing Ethiopia’s energy production capacity, as it is projected to increase Ethiopia’s energy production by 85% at full capacity (Salini Impreglio, 2017). Additionally, Gibe III is the first dam on the Omo river basin which is not designed for hydro-power production only, but also for irrigation purposes.

Figure 24 - Aerial view of Gibe III dam and reservoir.

The USD1.8 billion project of Gibe III dam construction was awarded with no public bid to Salini Corp (UNEP, 2012). Construction works began in 2008 and the dam started to generate electricity at partial capacity in 2015, with an over two-years delay with respect to the initial prospects. The delay was mainly due to the African Development Bank ceasing to finance the project in 2009 due to the lack of sufficient environmental impact assessment. In July 2010 the Industrial and Commercial Bank of China came forward with a loan of USD450 million to cover the cost of the dam's turbines, and the construction works restarted. Dam construction and filling encountered discussion and opposition from local and international environmental groups, and the debate is still open regarding the socio-economic impacts of the project.

Figure 25 - Gibe III dam and power plant elements.

Table 21 - Plant data for Gibe III dam, Ethiopia.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Ethiopia		CESI, 2009
River	Omo		CESI, 2009
Operator	EEPCo		CESI, 2009
Status	Inundation phase		Moukala, 2015
Closure	-		
Type	Reservoir		CESI, 2009
Operating Targets	Hydropower Production		CESI, 2009
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	34,150		CESI, 2009
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	12		CESI, 2009
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	n.a.		
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	209		CESI, 2009
Reservoir Length [km]	150		CESI, 2009
Crest Elevation [m asl]	896		CESI, 2009
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	243		CESI, 2009
Average Depth [m]	70		CESI, 2009
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/year]	110,4		CESI, 2009
Live Storage [km ³]	11,750		CESI, 2009
Dead Storage [km ³]	2,950		CESI, 2009

Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	800		CESI, 2009
(Table 21 continued)			
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	892		CESI, 2009
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	889		CESI, 2009
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	1,06		CESI, 2009
Level-Storage Curve	Curve available		
Level-Surface Curve	Curve available		
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	RCC		CESI, 2009
Number of Spillways	9		CESI, 2009
Type of Spillways	Ungated Side Channel (4) + gated Overflow (5)		CESI, 2009
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	873		CESI, 2009
Spillway Capacity [m ³ /s]	10,600	18000 according to Revolv, 2011	Sogreah, 2010
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	Available		CESI, 2009
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	750		Sogreah, 2010
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	Formula Available		CESI, 2009
Number of Bottom Outlets	1		CESI, 2009
Type of Bottom Outlets	Conduit from the Power Waterways		CESI, 2009
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	800		CESI, 2009
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		CESI, 2009
Intake Elevation [m asl]	780		CESI, 2009
POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
Installed Capacity [MW]	1,870		CESI, 2009
Number of Turbines	10		CESI, 2009
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	187		CESI, 2009
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	102		Sogreah, 2010
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	~60		CESI, 2009
Turbine Penstock Capacity [km ³ /yr]			
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	211		CESI, 2009
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	186		CESI, 2009
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	670,3		CESI, 2009
Turbine Efficiency [%]	n.a.		
KEN	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	6,400		CESI, 2009
Intake Rating Curve	Curve Available		CESI, 2009
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.		
Rule Curve	n.a.		

(Table 21 continued)

Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.		
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD]	1.8 billion		CESI, 2009
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	n.a.		
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	n.a.		
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	70	Minimum Environmental flow	CESI, 2009
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

Table 22 - Available time series for the Gibe III dam, Ethiopia.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	1999	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	2015	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Total Release [m ³ /s]	2015	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Turbined Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	2015	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	2015	2017	daily	Topkapi ETH simulations
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

*Note: the listed time series were simulated via Topkapi-ETH model. No observed time series is available for the reservoir.

Figure 26 - Gibe III dam feature elevations (panel a) and hydropower plant curves (panel b,c,d,e).

2.4 Turkwel Dam (Kenya)

The Turkwel Hydroelectric dam is an arch dam situated on the Turkwel River, Kenya, one of the two southern tributaries of Lake Turkana (Figure 27, Figure 28). The station was completed in 1991 under the supervision of the Kerio Valley Development Authority (KVDA), and conceived as a multi-purpose project comprising hydro-power, agricultural, fisheries and tourism development (KenGen,

2018). The dam is also expected to provide protection against droughts due to its large storage (Mugo, 2012). With an installed capacity of 106 MW, the dam is the third largest hydroelectric power plant in the country and it generates approximately 10% of the national electricity supply.

Figure 27 - Turkwel dam (Mugo, 2012).

Figure 28 - Satellite view of Turkel and Kerio rivers, and the southern branch of Turkana.

Table 23 - Plant data for the Turkwel dam, Kenya.

GENERAL DATA		NOTES	SOURCE
Country	Kenya		Mugo, 2012
River	Turkwel		Mugo, 2012
Operator	Kerio Valley Development Authority		Mugo, 2012

(Table 23 continued)

Status	In operation		Mugo, 2012
Closure	-		
Type	Reservoir		Mugo, 2012
Operating Targets	Hydropower, Irrigation, Fisheries, Tourism		Mugo, 2012
CATCHMENT DATA			
Catchment Area (natural + diversions) [km ²]	5,900		
Average Inflow [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Maximum, Minimum, Average Altitude [m asl]	1,150 (max)		
RESERVOIR DATA			
Reservoir Area [km ²]	6,500		Mugo, 2012
Reservoir Length [km]	n.a.		
Crest Elevation [m asl]	153		Mugo, 2012
Max Depth (Dam Height [m])	1150		Mugo, 2012
Average Depth [m]	n.a.		
Average Net Reservoir Evaporation [mm/year]	n.a.		
Live Storage [km ³]	1,650		Mugo, 2012
Dead Storage [km ³]	n.a.		
Minimum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		Mugo, 2012
Maximum Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Normal Operating Level [m asl]	n.a.		
Storage to Flow Volume Ratio	n.a.		
Mean Residence Time [yr]	n.a.		
Level-Storage Curve	n.a.		
Level-Surface Curve	n.a.		
DAM DATA			
Dam Type	Double curvature arch dam		Mugo, 2012
Number of Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Spillways	n.a.		
Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Number of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Type of Emergency Spillways	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Sill Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Emergency Spillway Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Spillway Rating Curve	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Medium Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Number of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Type of Bottom Outlets	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Bottom Outlet Rating Curve	n.a.		
Intake Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		

(Table 23 continued)

POWER PLANT CHARACTERISTICS			
Installed Capacity [MW]	106		Mugo, 2012
Number of Turbines	2		Mugo, 2012
Max Power per Turbine [MW]	53		Mugo, 2012
Max Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	17		Mugo, 2012
Min Discharge per Turbine [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Turbine Penstock Capacity [km ³ /yr]	n.a.		
Max Hydraulic Head [m]	356		Mugo, 2012
Mean Hydraulic Head [m]	n.a.		
Turbine Outlet Elevation [m asl]	n.a.		
Turbine Efficiency [%]	n.a.		
KEN	n.a.		
Mean Annual Production [GWh/yr]	6,450		Mugo, 2012
Intake Rating Curve	n.a.		
Tailwater Rating Curve	n.a.		
Rule Curve	n.a.		
Turbines Efficiency - Releases Curve	n.a.		
COSTS			
Capital Cost [USD]	160		Mugo, 2012
Fixed Cost [USD/kW]	n.a.		
Variable Cost [USD/MWh]	n.a.		
OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINTS			
Release Constraints [m ³ /s]	n.a.		
Level Constraints [m]	n.a.		
Other Constraints	n.a.		

Table 24 - Available time series for the Turkwel dam, Kenya.

DATA	FROM	TO	FREQUENCY	SOURCE
Inflow to the Reservoir [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Level (or Storage) [m] (or [km ³])	n.a.	n.a.		
Total Release [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Turbinated Flow [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Reservoir Spill [m ³ /s]	n.a.	n.a.		
Hydropower Production [GWh]	n.a.	n.a.		
Precipitation on reservoir [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Temperature on reservoir [°C]	n.a.	n.a.		
Evaporation [mm]	n.a.	n.a.		
Other Meteorological Variables	n.a.	n.a.		

REFERENCES

References are listed in the deliverable main report.